

**CONTACT METAL PERMEATION EFFECTS AND
POTENTIAL HYDROGEN STORAGE IN CARBON-BASED
MATERIALS**

A THESIS

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ABSTRACT

KEYWORDS: Graphene, metal permeation in graphene, vacuum annealing, hydrogen embrittlement, hydrogenation, dendrite structures, crumbled graphene, defected graphene, adatom adsorption in graphene, volumetric capacity, hydrogen storage, graphite, palladium black, contact metal permeation, palladium nanoparticles, graphitic carbon nitride, palladium-cobalt alloy nanoparticles, magnesium-nickel alloy nanoparticles, palladium nanoparticles on graphene, magnetic properties of graphene, diffused metals, stone wales defects in graphene, corrugations in graphene, graphite hydrogen storage, contact metal diffusion in graphene, magnetism in graphite, reduced graphene oxide.

Owing to its unique 2D structure, graphene has become a potential material not only for technological applications but also a testing tool for the fundamental aspects of condensed matter physics. Even though graphene possesses many remarkable structural, physical and electronic qualities; fabrication of almost all the graphene-based devices need to incorporate metal contacts in order to experience these trademarks. Metal-graphene interaction is of an immense importance since every area of application of graphene has to be contained with metals directly or indirectly. In short, the presence of metal atom can influence and manipulate almost all the properties of graphene; since the hybrid interface between graphene and metals will exhibit interesting physics, hence one of the major studies concerned about the defects in graphene is the graphene-metal interaction study. However, our practical knowledge about the concerned subject is limited.

Thus, in this scenario, many studies are focused on different metal adatom adsorptions on graphene and their effects; of which most of them are based on some theoretical models such as Monte Carlo, Molecular dynamics (MD) or Density functional theory (DFT). Nevertheless, unintentionally, depending on the approach used for calculations and choice of parameters, boundary conditions will limit the experimental

implementations of these calculations and occasionally the results will be inconsistent. In practice, as bulk amounts are needed for industrial production, several other unanticipated parameters need to be considered.

The present thesis is focussed on the effect of contact metal permeation through container metal interfaces on the surface of graphite, graphitic carbon nitride, and graphene; when subjected to vacuum annealing followed by high temperature hydrogen treatment within the proximity of container metals. Thus, the present study introduces a novel experimental procedure to observe the indirect contact metal permeation on the surface of carbon materials through container metal surface. The effect of metal permeation on the properties of carbon materials are demonstrated via morphological studies, magnetic response and electrochemical analysis.

Besides, apart from the main base materials like pristine graphene or any other support material; numerous other metal contributions will be included together or within the framework to improve or facilitate various properties. Consequently, there is a scope for the investigation arises where the contact metals can affect the performance of the entire system by affecting the other accessory metals included in the framework.

Accordingly, the current thesis has explored the contact metal permeation effects in Pd metal nanoparticles incorporated on the surface of graphene/graphite systems. Moreover, an investigation is done on the effect of present experimental conditions on the growth morphology and characteristics of pure metal systems such as Pd metal nanoparticles, which in succession lead to the formation of novel Pd black dendrite structures having peculiar properties.

Though hydrogen has turned out as the most desirable alternative energy source for the depleting fossil fuels and hence several means for its storage has become significant for the last few decades; the attempts to make an ideal hydrogen storage material are still under research. Despite some significant advances in certain properties, no materials have been developed, which can accommodate all the features of an ideal hydrogen storage material. High surface area, highly porous carbon materials have long been identified as efficient hydrogen storage materials by modifying them with hydrogen anchoring sites such as nitrogen or with the help of catalyst decoration. But the cumbersome synthesis processes, high cost, low energy range, unfavourable temperature range, slow kinetics, etc., make them impractical. Moreover, most of them

possess a very poor volumetric capacity due to their high specific surface area, even though their gravimetric capacity is good.

In this scenario, the present thesis addresses these important issues related to hydrogen storage. Again, the efforts to bring in the catalytic activities of noble metals like palladium is facing the challenges such as high cost or poor stability due to hydrogen corrosion. Therefore, in present work, alloying of cobalt with palladium in conjunction with nitrogen incorporation is done through some simple in-situ modification techniques which could improve the synergic interaction of catalyst centres with the support material and provide an efficient hydrogen spill over. However, attempts are again made to implement non-precious alloy nanocatalyst such as magnesium-nickel alloy, to support the idea of 'cost effective hydrogen storage material'.

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ABBREVIATIONS

0D	Zero dimensional
1D	One dimensional
2D	Two dimensional
3D	Three dimensional
BE	Binding energy
BET	Brunauer- Emmett- Teller
BJH	Barrett- Joyner- Halenda
CE	Counter electrode
Ch	Channel
CHNS	Carbon-Hydrogen-Nitrogen-Sulphur
CNT	Carbon nanotube
CV	Cyclic voltammetry
CVD	Chemical vapour deposition
DFT	Density functional theory
DI	De-ionised
DoE	Department of Energy
DSC	Differential scanning calorimetry
DTA	Differential thermal analysis
EDX	Energy dispersive X-ray
EG	Ethylene glycol
FC	Field cooled
FTIR	Fourier transform infra-red
FWHM	Full width half maximum
GC	Glassy carbon
g-C₃N₄	Graphitic carbon nitride
GD	Gravimetric density

GO	Graphite oxide
Gr	Graphite
HEG	Hydrogen exfoliated graphene
HRTEM	High resolution transmission electron microscopy
HRSEM	High resolution transmission electron microscopy
ICP-OES	Inductively coupled plasma – optical emission spectroscopy
IR	Infra-red
LN₂	Liquid nitrogen
IUPAC	International Union of pure and applied chemistry
MD	Molecular dynamics
MOF	Metal organic framework
PBS	Phosphate buffer solution
PC	Pressure- composition
ppm	Parts per million
RE	Reference electrode
r-GO	Reduced graphene oxide
rpm	rotations per minute
RT	Room temperature
sccm	Standard cubic centimetre per minute
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
SQUID	Superconducting quantum interface device
SS	Stainless steel
SSA	Specific surface area
SW	Stone Wales
SWCNT	Single walled carbon nanotubes
TEG	Thermally exfoliated graphene
TEM	Transmission electron microscopy
TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
TPD	Temperature programmed desorption
UV	Ultra violet
VD	Volumetric density
VdW	Van der Waal's
VSM	Vibrating sample magnetometer

WE	working electrode
Wt%	weight percentage
XPS	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
XRD	X-ray diffraction
ZFC	Zero field cooled

NOTATIONS

Φ	Hydrogen permeability
ϵ	Depth of energy level
T	Temperature
P	Pressure
V	Volume
R	Universal gas constant
E_p	Physisorption Energy
E_c	Chemisorption Energy
r_i	Intermolecular distance
V	Potential
P_{eq}	Equilibrium pressure
ΔH	Change in enthalpy
ΔS	Change in entropy
P_0	Initial pressure
λ	Wavelength
D	Diffusivity
θ	Peak position
t	Crystallite size

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Carbon has proven its versatility and inevitability in the universe by abundance and its unusual ability to make diverse compounds. Not only being the biological made of everything in nature, Carbon has been the best support- milestone for the mankind to advance their technologies and culture through ages by its diversifying effects. The bondage of carbon with other metals will be an important matter of study to expand the standard of life in general. Here in this thesis, the metal-carbon interaction is probed to improve the quality of present available device technologies by examining the foreign contact-metal permeation effects in carbon-based systems and utilize the metal-carbon interaction application to meet the global energy demand.

Based on a comprehensive literature review, this chapter introduces a general overview of the need for metal-carbon interaction study in present scenario, focusing on the contact metal permeation on the surface of the carbon nanomaterials owing to extreme conditions like high temperature, high vacuum or hydrogen assisted interactions within the proximity of metals as well as its consequences in their properties, and through catalyst metal-carbon interaction to avail the hydrogen storage. Subsequently, the motivation, objectives and scope of the work will be discussed in detail.

1.1 Introduction- General

Owing to its unique 2D structure, Graphene has become a potential material not only for technological applications but also a testing tool for the fundamental aspects of condensed matter physics(Xu and Buehler, 2010a) . Even though graphene possesses many remarkable structural, physical and electronic qualities; fabrication of almost all the graphene-based devices need to incorporate metal contacts in order to experience these trademarks. Metal –graphene interaction is of an immense importance since every area of application of graphene has to be contained with metals directly or indirectly (Singh and Kroll, 2009). The metal catalyst activity in carbon is also a metal-carbon interface interaction, which affect the chemistry of material considerably and in effect can lead to the utilization of carbon in various catalyst aided reactions. Again, the substrate holding the graphene can also affect the sensitive physical properties like spin

distribution of graphene and can induce the proximity effects in the system such as proximity induced magnetism (X Liu et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2013). Thus, there should be a clear idea about the metal- graphene interface interaction so that one can choose the most suitable metal for the application, which will not disturb the performance of the proposed devices in any circumstances. Furthermore, the influence of the interfacing metals can affect the properties of other metals (other than the base material like graphene) or metal accessories within the system (device in practical). Comprehensively, the quality of contact metal is necessary for any device fabrication or fundamental studies associated with any material.

Moreover, efforts are being undertaken globally to push in hydrogen based energy systems to get rid of the present world energy crisis which has been arisen from the over dependence of fossil fuels. The safe and efficient storage is the most crucial technological issue in finalizing Hydrogen economy. Despite some significant advances in certain properties, no materials have been developed, which can accommodate all the features of a good hydrogen storage material. A wide literature support from various part of the world is existing for the use of carbon nanomaterials as effective hydrogen storage media. High surface area carbon nanomaterials such as activated carbon, carbon nano tubes, Graphene etc. are already well employed in this field. Catalyst aided chemisorption is reported to be the best solution for improving the storage efficiency of carbon materials. Here, again the metal- carbon interaction is an important parameter. Thus, a clear idea about the reaction mechanisms in metal- carbon contact interface can improve the hydrogen storage research.

Basically, a material will exhibit its unique physics in various manifestations through its interface interactions. Consequently, in general, the metal- interface interaction studies are the investable part of the fundamental studies associated with any material.

Accordingly, here we are analysing the various metal interaction reactions with carbon materials due to various conditions. In particular, proposing a novel experimental method to explore the indirect contact metal permeation in carbon based systems through container metal interface with various alloys/metals when the system is exposed to certain experimental conditions like high vacuum annealing and high temperature hydrogenation. Also, an investigative study is done to analyse the contact metal permeation effects in the other accessory metals associated within the framework through the experiments on palladium based systems. Again, in the present

work, attempts are done to employ the catalyst alloy/metal – carbon interface interactions to meet the global energy demand through novel hydrogen storage materials with unique capabilities.

1.2 Carbon- metal interface; a review:

Since from the experimental realization of 2D graphene, a major part of the research in the world started revolving around this promising material. Graphene research may be divided into three areas mainly- (i) studies based on the physical properties originating from the peculiar 2D nature of the material and its unique band structure (ii) implementation of the potentials of this material to the device applications and (iii) the material science of graphene – the various types of synthesis, modifications, graphene derivatives and various forms, deformation of graphene or doping with impurities and interface formation with graphene and other dissimilar materials (Batzill, 2012). In all these research endeavours, either for practical application or theoretical verification, graphene has to interface with various other metal surfaces.

1.2.1 Mechanism:

A noticeable property of graphene is its strong ability to adsorb due to its high specific surface area and high polarizability (Tao et al., 2018). Mainly two kinds of adsorption are observed in graphene interface with other foreign surfaces- namely, physisorption interfaces (e.g., Ag, Al, Cu, Cd, Ir, Pt or Au) and chemisorption interfaces (e.g., Ni, Co, Ru, Pd or Ti) (Gong et al., 2010a). Physisorption is a weak interaction of van der Waal's forces which can cause distortion in graphene surfaces, while chemisorption is a strong interaction which lead to the chemical bondage with graphene, causing little distortion to the surface. The detailed explanation for physisorption and chemisorption interaction is available in later sections.

1.2.2 Positions of interaction

Transmission electron microscopic studies have been carried out to analyse the morphological and structural variation of graphene with the defects induced by foreign impurities (Ramasse et al., 2012). The experimental microscopic studies would predict the positions of the interaction, though more studies should be done to explore the effect on other properties. The possible predicted sites of the foreign atom attachment in graphene would be the following as per calculations – 'H sites' (centre of the hexagon)

for Fe and alkaline metals such as K, Na, Cs and Ti while ‘T sites’ (top of the carbon atom) for Au, Cu, Ni, Sn and F whereas ‘B sites’ or Bridge sites (on the top of C-C bond) may be occupied by Pt, Cl, Cr, S,O, N and P (Faye, 2012; Xiaojie Liu et al., 2011)A detailed view of the interaction sites is as shown in Fig. 1.1.

Fig. 1. 1 The possible predicted sites of the foreign atom attachment in graphene- ‘H sites’ (centre of the hexagon), ‘T sites’ (top of the carbon atom) and ‘B sites’ or Bridge sites (on the top of C-C bond).

1.2.3 Stone Wales (SW) defects

A common type of defect occurs in graphene or other graphene derived carbon nanomaterials are Stone- Thrower- Wales defects (STW defects) or simply SW defects. SW defects are typically formed by the simple rotation of C-C bond in 90° and consists of 5 to 7 atoms ring. Many studies have observed SW defects experimentally, proving that they can modify the chemical reactivity of graphene and create a new energy band gap. Clustering of SW defects is predicted to be the first process in graphene melting.

Since the C-C bonds associated with the SW defects are more reactive than the normal hexagons, the adatom impurity sites will generally prefer the SW defects than the pure surface, as it provide a less energy barrier to the approaching species. It is also proven

that hydrogen adsorption and storage can also be promoted considerably with SW defects or curvature in general.

The presence of SW defects induces a local curvature on graphene geometry, as the rotated C-C bond length is compressed from 1.42 Å of intrinsic graphene to 1.32 Å, which contributes a compressive strain. SW defects are predicted to be having a strong impact on the atomic chemisorption on graphene. In addition to the three positions of interaction mentioned above in Fig 1.1, there will be several other sites introduced by the SW defects which will act as the preferred sites for the foreign impurities and hence the total reactivity of the system will be improved considerably. The following Fig. (Fig 1.2.) indicates some examples for the newly created possible reaction sites for the foreign species. (Chen et al., 2010; L. Chen et al., 2011; Johll and Low, 2014; Lu et al., 2009; Podlivaev and Openov, 2015)

In the present study, experiments are designed to create clusters of SW defects in graphene derived materials and hence observe the possibility and effects of contact metal permeation with the help of these newly created SW defects. The details of the study are available in the Chapter-3 and Chapter-4.

1.2.4 Metal - graphene interface – some practical aspects

Digging through the never-ending literature popping up in the field of graphene related research, one can conclude that interfacing of graphene with other metals is an investable part of the business. Unraveling many prominent studies available, a few examples are being pointed out here; where we can observe the direct metal interaction with graphene surface. Graphene- metal interaction can be unswervingly observed in graphene substrates, contacts in electronic/spintronic fabrication, tailoring the shapes/etching process, lithography and fabrication techniques, nano cutting in presence of metals, catalyst centers, porous structures and nano particles, sandwich structures and metal films, electrochemical and photochemical area, Hydrogen storage-evolution, production, purification and detection, tunneling processes and device applications, sensing and memory applications, energy storage devices, anti-corrosion coatings and crack detectors and many more.

Fig. 1. 2 Illustration of chemisorption sites. (a) Three different chemisorption sites: the top, bridge, and hollow site in intrinsic graphene; (b) top site for H chemisorption on the STW defect; and (c) bridge site for N or P chemisorption on the STW defect (L. Chen et al., 2011).

Since all the bio materials contains carbon, the process of cooking in metal containers or any other metal- made can lead to the contact metal permeation effect in the carbon content of the food materials. Thus, our present study will be probing light to the various aspects of daily life.

1.3 Role of hydrogen in metal permeation process

Hydrogen molecule can be adsorbed on metal surface and dissolved into atomic hydrogen. The process of dissolution and subsequent diffusion to the metals may follow two strategies to form a hydrogen containment structure - (i) hydrogen can permeate through the structure successfully and (ii) hydrogen can interact with the micro structure of the material or react with the chemical structure of the material, causing detrimental changes to the mechanical properties of the material. The mechanism of the second phenomena is collectively referred as hydrogen embrittlement (Gavin Walker, 2008).

Fig. 1. 3 Hydrogen permeability of different alloys as a function of temperature: - the solid lines represent the range of temperature over which the measurements were made, and the dotted lines are extrapolations of exponential form to room temperature (298 K). The austenitic Fe is an average relationship for a number of austenitic stainless steels (Solid state hydrogen storage- Materials and Chemistry; edited by Gavin Walker, 2008.)

The hydrogen permeability is a property of the material and is a function of temperature, can be represented by the following equation,

$$\phi = \phi_0 \exp(-H_\phi/RT) \dots\dots\dots (1.1)$$

The parameters are as follows: ϕ_0 - a constant dependant on the material, H_ϕ – the activation energy for permeation, T- the temperature and R- the universal gas constant. It is very clear that the magnitude of permeation depends on the type of material. Thus, metals with fcc crystal structure such as austenitic stainless steel, copper, gold, nickel and aluminium tend to have low permeability compared to the bcc structured metals

such as low- alloy and carbon steels. The non-ferrous alloys and gold exhibit very low hydrogen permeability. The permeability variation for different metals according to temperature is as shown in Fig 1.3.

Considering this scenario of hydrogen-metal interaction, efforts are being taken care to include hydrogen permeation in our present study of contact metal permeation effects in carbon materials. We have carefully chosen those metals/ alloys for our experiment such that they may be commonly used in the graphene (or any other material in general) based device industry as contact metals/substrates, as well as permeable to hydrogen at the same time. Therefore, experiments are done on the metal permeation process with metals like Fe, Ni, Cu, Al, Pd, Pt, etc. and alloys like stainless steel. Correspondingly, the present work analyses the experimental effects in details for palladium in its metallic form as well as nano particle forms. Consequently, the formation of a peculiar Pd dendrite structure - Pd black is also explored. For hydrogen storage experiments, alloy nano particles are taken as catalyst to improve the capacity and reduce the hydrogen embrittlement, and hence could improve the cycle life of the material.

1.4 Hydrogen adsorption process in materials

Hydrogen adsorption is the enrichment of hydrogen density on or near the surface of the material either in atomic or in molecular form; or hydrogen adsorption is the incorporation of atomic hydrogen within the crystallographic structure or bulk of the material (Kopsakangas-savolainen, 2011). According to IUPAC standards, definition for the adsorption measurement the terminology is as follows. The non-adsorbed free gas (hydrogen) is known as the *adsorptive*; the adsorbed gas as the *adsorbate*; and the adsorbing material is the *adsorbent*. *Sorption* is the term used for the gas intake and the reverse process is described as *desorption*. Fig. 1.4 gives a brief comparative description of various hydrogen storage systems available with their storage capabilities. The solid-state hydrogen storage i.e., storage in materials has its due importance because of its several advantages over other technologies.

1.4.1 Basic interaction

Hydrogen sorption interaction with solid surface can be either physically bound form as hydrogen molecule-physisorption or chemically bound form as hydrogen atoms – chemisorption.

Fig. 1. 4 The volumetric versus mass densities for various hydrogen storage technologies. (Ref: Hydrogen fuel-production, transport and storage- edited by Ram B. Gupta)

Both of these interactions are having entirely different nature and due importance by virtue of their properties. However, for a hydrogen good storage material, both the interactions are necessary.

1.4.1.1 Physisorption

Physisorption or physical adsorption is the mechanism by which a gas is stored in the material in molecular form without dissociation on the surface of the solid. The weak dispersive van der Waal's forces are responsible for the interaction. These forces are derived from the interaction between temporary dipoles which are formed due to the fluctuations in charge distribution in molecules and atoms.

Along with this Van der Waal's attraction, the short range repulsive interaction between a gas molecule and an atom on the surface of the adsorbent results in a potential energy which can be described by Lennard Jones potential as follows in equation (1.2); where

' ϵ ' is depth of the energy well, ' r_i ' is the distance between hydrogen molecule and a generic atom 'I' on the surface, ' σ ' is the value of r_i in which potential is zero.

Hydrogen storage in solids

Fig. 1. 5 Hydrogen adsorption mechanism in solid materials- physisorption and chemisorption potentials. (Ref. <http://h2.gntech.ac.kr/index.php?mid=h2storage>)

The curve is exhibited in Fig. 1.5. The minimum position of the curve corresponds to 2-3 Å. Adsorption is an exothermic process, owing to the low polarizability of the hydrogen molecule. The interaction is weak having a low value for the heat of adsorption, usually between $E_p = 10- 20$ kJ/mol of H_2 .

$$V(r_i) = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r_i} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r_i} \right)^6 \right] \dots\dots\dots (1.2)$$

Physisorption is a completely reversible process without any losses. In this process hydrogen molecule is adsorbed only on the surface of the material, i.e., a complete surface phenomenon, hence porous materials with high specific surface area (SSA) are suitable for this reaction (Hirscher, 2010).

1.4.1.2. Chemisorption

If the hydrogen molecule is dissociated into hydrogen atoms, (at the intersection of both curves, Fig. 1.5) prior to the interaction, a completely different interaction occurs which will allow the material to adsorb the hydrogen atoms into the bulk of it making bonds (either covalent or ionic) and the phenomenon is known as chemisorption. Since the dissociation energy has to be spent on the system first, the potential on the curve starts $E_{\text{dis}} = 435$ kJ above the zero level, on the right-hand side of the diagram. Chemisorption, which is either covalent or ionic (the 1S atoms of the hydrogen will make bonds with the solid) in nature occurs at a distance of $0.5 - 1$ Å, with a heat of chemisorption, $E_C = 100 - 200$ kJ/mol of H_2 . The hydrogen molecules having very high kinetic energy will get physically adsorbed first and then shift over to the second curve at the intersection point and then dissociates to form hydrogen atoms and finally chemisorbed. Spontaneous adsorption occurs without any activation energy while activated chemisorption needs an initial activation energy to start the adsorption (K. Christmann, 1988).

1.4.2 Catalyst effect

It is well experimented from decades that hydrogen can be stored as metal hydrides both in physisorbed as well as chemisorbed form. In the carbon nano structures, due to their specific bonding structure and physical properties, normally physisorption is only happening. As mentioned earlier, the gravimetric density of stored hydrogen only due to physisorption is very less, even if the complete saturation occurs. Therefore, it is advisable to employ chemisorption to the reaction to improve the capacity of the material. Consequently, metals having high affinity towards hydrogen can be used for this purpose to initiate the chemisorption in carbon-based storage systems. The capacity of transition metals will be improved considerably with the reduction of their grain size. These catalyst metals can be included in their nano form as nano particles or nano clusters of different size and shape to the carbon matrix. Many models like 'Kubas interaction' or 'spill over mechanism' can be used to avail the catalyst-based hydrogen interaction in carbon systems. The present study will be focussing on the catalyst spill-over based interaction in which catalyst nano particles are decorated over the carbon surfaces.

1.4.2.1 Spill over mechanism

Spill over is a critical mechanism in heterogeneous catalysis for hydrogen adsorption. Spill over is defined as ‘the transport of active species that have adsorbed or formed on a first surface, migrated onto another surface that does not sorb or form active species under the same conditions’. The hydrogen spill over involves three major steps, as explained in the Fig. 1.6: (i) chemisorptive dissociation of hydrogen molecule into hydrogen atom at the transition metal site (ii) subsequent migration of the hydrogen atoms to the substrate and (iii) further diffusion of hydrogen atoms into the bulk of the substrate. As shown in figure, the mechanism can be effectively explained as a bridge formed between the secondary receptor and the spill over source. Once the mechanism has started, it will be acting as a pumping process of hydrogen atoms until the equilibrium is reached. Generally, transition metal nano particles are being used as the catalyst nano particles for the spill over. The subsequent sections in chapter-5 will be explaining the experiments in detail, where the spill over mechanism is utilized efficiently for improving the hydrogen uptake capacity of carbon systems. The present work mainly uses Pd/Pd-Co alloy and magnesium-nickel alloy nano particles to employ the catalyst spill over technique (Gross et al., n.d.; Lachawiec et al., 2005).

1.4.3 Importance of Pd in hydrogen assisted reactions

Palladium is considered as unique material in the hydrogen related reactions and the hydrogen storage industry as it is having the highest affinity towards hydrogen, both as a catalyst and as an adsorbent. Apart from the bulk counterpart, the nano sized palladium will show exemplary qualities for hydrogen storage such as rapid charging-discharging kinetics, extended cycle lives, and size- tunable thermo dynamics. Accordingly, many literatures from various part of the world are available projecting Pd nano particles as the best catalyst for hydrogen storage industry.

The hydrogen adsorption in Pd results in the formation of two phases- (i) at low concentration (solid solution), α - phase occurs, whereas (ii) at high concentrations, β - phase occurs. When the two phases co-exist, a plateau at constant pressure is observed, the width of which determines the hydrogen storage capacity of a material. This plateau pressure can be correlated to the change in enthalpy (ΔH) and change in entropy (ΔS) by the following Van't Hoff equation (equation 1.3). The detailed view of the evolution of metal- hydrogen interaction can be obtained from the Fig. 1.7.

$$\ln\left(\frac{P_{eq}}{P_0}\right) = \frac{\Delta H}{RT} - \frac{\Delta S}{R} \dots\dots\dots (1.3)$$

Enthalpy determines the strength of the metal hydrogen bond while entropy is a measure of the change from molecular hydrogen to metal hydride.

Fig. 1. 6 Hydrogen spill over in a supported catalyst system: (a) adsorption of hydrogen onto a supported metal nanoparticle; (b) low-capacity receptor; (c) primary spill over of atomic hydrogen to the support; (d) secondary spill over to the receptor enhanced by a physical bridge; (e) primary and secondary spill over enhancement by improved contacts and bridges. [(Gross et al., Lachawiec et al., 2005)]

Fig. 1. 7 (Left) Pressure-composition isotherm plot of metal to metal hydride phase transition. (right) Van't Hoff plot related to the phase transition from metal to metal hydride. Schematic representation of alpha-phase (left) and beta- phase (right) of metal hydride are also shown (Bhat et al., 2009; Konda and Chen, 2015).

The present work utilizes Pd nano catalyst to exploit the spill over based chemisorption in carbon materials. Since the inclusion of Pd will increase the total cost of production of the material and is suffering from the hydrogen corrosion, in the present work, efforts are done to utilize alloy-based nano catalyst, which could improve the storage efficiency, cycle life and reduction in cost of the material. The experimental details with results and discussion are available in Chapter-5.

Moreover, the effect of contact metal permeation and diffusion in Pd nano particles associated within the carbon system is studied in presence of hydrogen. The specific experimental conditions to form a novel dendrite structures for palladium black is also analysed. The detailed study is presented in Chapter-4.

1.4.4 Surface morphology effect

The surface morphology of material will have the greatest influence in hydrogen adsorption reactions. High surface area, highly porous materials are ideal for hydrogen sorption process. In the case of metal hydrides, the nano structured materials will be having far better performance than their bulk counter parts. Consequently, the uniform distribution of metal nano particles can be well served as catalyst for hydrogen storage reactions. Considering the case of graphene derived systems, multi-layered graphene is more preferable than pristine single- layered graphene.

Studies on the effect of hydrogenation on graphene shows that rippled graphene is more suitable for all hydrogenation reactions. The local curvature of graphene has a great influence on hydrogen reactions, as the convex surfaces enhances the reactivity towards hydrogen by reducing the chemisorption barrier. The nanoscale corrugations have improved the hydrogen uptake capacity considerably. It is highly interesting to note the new mechanism of reversible hydrogen storage by controlling graphene curvature proposed by Valentia Tozzini and Vittorio Pellegrini (Boukhalov and Katsnelson, 2009; Tozzini and Pellegrini, 2013a). The following Fig. 1.8 shows the variation of potential barrier according to local curvature; available from the literature.

Fig. 1. 8 Calculated C–H binding energy versus the local curvature. Fig. reference: (Tozzini and Pellegrini, 2013a)

In this Fig. 1.8, the local curvature is measured by the puckering distance d of a given C atom with respect to the plane formed by its three first neighbours before H binding (see balls and sticks representation on the X axis). The variation of binding energy with respect to the flat graphene is reported on the left Y axis. The black dots correspond to the binding energy of isolated H evaluated on sampled C sites of the corrugated graphene sheet, shown on the right, with the convex parts in red and the concave ones in blue. The fitting black line is $\Delta E_{\text{bind}} [\text{eV}] = 4.449 d [\text{\AA}]$. Binding energy profiles are shown for three sample sites on the convex (red), flat (black), and concave (blue) regions, respectively, as indicated by the arrows on the right (in this case the Y axis reports the absolute binding energy using as a reference system the graphene plus isolated detached atomic H). The arrows on the left indicate the corresponding dots in

the main graph. The red squares correspond to literature data of the binding energy on C₆₀ and on nanotubes of different lengths. The structure of graphene sheets hydrogenated on convexities is also indicated by balls and sticks (gray = C, orange = H) (Tozzini and Pellegrini, 2013a).

Thus, in conclusion, the hydrogen binding energy is tunable according to the local curvature. The considerable variation in H- binding energy makes chemisorption, a favourable process in convex sites and desorption, a favourable process in concave sites. Here in the present work, we have exercised the idea of this local curvature effect to study the metal permeation process in presence of hydrogen experimentally, the details of which are explained in Chapter-3 and Chapter-4.

1.5. Carbon materials- a brief historical review

Biologically, being the basis of the life of our planet, carbon is the 15th most abundant element in Earth's crust, the 4th most in the universe and the second most in human body; perhaps the most interesting element in the periodic table. Physically existing in diverse forms such as the soot common in chimneys, as graphite in pencils and diamonds in jewellery. Its peculiar structure and repetitions resembles the mathematical models such as Euler polyhedron, variety of benchmarks arises mainly due to the fundamental abilities such as hybridization and catenation. Hybridization is the ability to make mixed or hybrid orbitals which in effect lead to the formation of different allotropes of carbon, while catenation is the peculiarity of carbon atoms to form long chain compounds by binding with other carbon atoms.

Though the search for carbon history will pop up many remarkable ideas of great souls from ages, the latest one in brief suitable for the current discussion is the discovery of 'Buckminsterfullerene' or 'Bucky ball', consists of 60 carbon atoms arranged in the form of a soccer ball. This was in 1985, a group comprising of Kroto, Smalley, Curl and others observed a stable cluster of 60 carbon atoms when graphite was vaporized using intense laser beam in helium atmosphere (Kroto et al., 1985). Subsequently, a group of similar structures were observed and are collectively termed as 'fullerenes'; considered to be zero dimensional (0D), as they are extremely small in size. This pioneering discovery, winning the Nobel prize (1996) is considered as the beginning of the science of carbon nano structures, in general.

Since then a variety of carbon nano structures have been discovered, among which the breakthrough was the carbon nano tubes (CNTs)- the 1-dimensional (1D) form of carbon, discovered in 1991 by S. Iijima in the soot of carbon arc deposit (Iijima, 1991). Following this discovery, the carbon nano research has undergone several noticeable metamorphosis with the advancing technological face of the scientific world. The 2-dimensional (2D) form of carbon, Graphene had remained in the theoretical abstracts for until its extraction in 2004 (Novoselov et al., 2004). This ground-breaking discovery of Geim and Novoselov were awarded the Nobel prize in Physics (2010); following which a new era of research has been started.

1.5.1 Carbon nano structures

Carbon, occupying the 6th position in the periodic table is having an electronic configuration $1S^2 2S^2 2P^2$ or $1S^2 2S^2 2P_x^1 2P_y^1 2P_z^0$. When the system is approached by another atom, the interaction energy will promote one 2S electron to the $2P_z$ level, resulting in a temporary excited state C^* giving rise to four orbitals of similar energy, leading to a configuration of $1S^2 2S^1 2P_x^1 2P_y^1 2P_z^1$. Due to the similarity in energy, these orbitals can mix up in different proportions to form hybrid orbitals. If one 2S and three 2P orbitals mix, four SP^3 hybridized orbitals are formed, which will be arranged in tetrahedral symmetry. If one 2S and two 2P orbitals mix, three SP^2 hybridized orbitals arise which can be arranged in planar structure with P_z orbitals spread above and below the plane. Again, one 2S and one 2P orbitals can mix together to give the two SP hybridized orbitals of the same energy.

The SP hybridized orbitals can easily form long linear molecules, but not solids. The solid allotropes of carbon are generally formed from SP^2 or SP^3 hybridized carbons. The classical examples of SP^2 and SP^3 hybridized solids are graphite and diamond, which are regarded as the 3-dimensional bulk allotropes. The SP^3 hybridised carbons in diamond lack P orbitals and hence do not possess conductivity and is not suitable for electronic applications whereas the SP^2 graphite has been used as conductor for many applications.

The defect free graphene consists of planar SP^2 symmetry while fullerenes and CNTs have a hybridization intermediate between SP^2 to SP^3 . In general, these materials have SP^n hybridisation, where $2 \leq n \leq 3$. Fig. 1.9 represents the different allotropes of carbon pictorially. The carbon nano structures are also existing in various other forms such as nano ribbons, nano coils, nano foams, nano platelets, wrinkled structures, etc. The detailed characteristics of the materials which are employed in the present study will be discussed in the following sections. Fig. 1.10 pictorially represents different nano allotropes of SP^2 carbon related to present investigations. Apart from the above-mentioned carbon nano structures such as graphite or graphene, a special graphitic form of carbon- graphitic carbon nitride (g- C_3N_4) is also explored in the present studies.

Fig. 1. 9 Schematic representing the concept of hybridization in carbon namely, (A) SP³ hybridization, (B) SP² hybridization and (C) SP hybridization (Ref:<http://www.smusd.org/cms/lib3/CA01000805/Centricity/Domain/1992/BioChem/Chapter>)

1.5.2 Graphene

Single planar sheet of SP² bonded carbon atoms corresponds to basal plane of graphite is termed as graphene (Robert A. Varin, 2009). Fig 1.11 is a representation of pristine graphene sheet having no defects. Graphene, the 2D arrangement of carbon hexagons, is considered as the mother of all other carbon allotropes including graphite, carbon nano tubes and fullerenes. It is the basic structural unit as it can be wrapped into 0-

dimensional fullerenes or rolled into 1-dimensional carbon nano tubes or stacked into 3-dimensional graphite.

Graphene is having unusual electronic, thermal, optical and mechanical properties which make it a promising candidate for wide range of applications. The pristine graphene provides a specific surface area (SSA) of $2,622 \text{ g/m}^3$ for two sides of graphene. Since graphene possess finite and small dimensions, filling the empty SP^2 orbitals with electrons from hydrogen atoms can stabilize dangling bonds along the periphery of graphene sheets. The highest degree of hydrogenation C_6H_{20} stabilizes graphene. Besides, graphene exhibits excellent electro catalytic activity towards various compounds which makes it a preferable candidate in electrochemistry. Besides, the ability to be doped by hetero atoms like N, F or B enhances its properties.

Fig. 1. 10 Allotropes of sp^2 carbon materials- (A). Graphene 2D (B). Graphite 3D (C). Nanotubes 1D and (D). C_{60} 0D (Lu et al., 2012)

Moreover, the defected graphene or other graphene derivatives are the favourite subject for researchers than the pristine graphene. Above all, graphene's extraordinary physics is suggesting it as a testing tool for the fundamental aspects of condensed matter state physics. In the present work we will be analysing the morphology changes and defect formation as a consequence of the thermal annealing or hydrogenation and examine the effect of foreign adatom adsorption on graphene derived materials.

Fig. 1. 11 Graphene sheet- the hexagonal arrangement of carbon rings in 2D form (Created via 'ACD/ChemSketch').

1.5.3 Graphite

Graphite is a polymorph of carbon formed by stacking of 2D graphene sheets of carbon hexagons. The stacking of hexagon basal planes ($a \times b$) along the c -axis lead to the formation of 2D sheets to 3D graphite. The crystallographic unit cell is hexagonal as shown in the Fig. 1.12. The theoretical density of graphite is 2.25 g/cm^3 , while it can be reduced by 1.85 g/cm^3 by methods such as mechanical milling. Graphite is a good conductor and is having several excellent properties. Here we are attempting to explore the hydrogen storage in graphite through the reactions aided by metal alloy nano catalyst. Again, another section of the experiments is dedicated to analyse the adatom impurity permeation in graphite through contact metal interfaces. In both cases, graphite-metal interface interaction is discussed in detail. (Robert A. Varin, 2009)

The synthetic graphite sheets exhibit a specific surface area of $1-7 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, as a contribution from various porosity such as macropores, mesopores and micropores. The interplanar distance of the regular graphite is 0.3354 nm , which is too small for a hydrogen molecule of diameter 0.406 nm to insert inside. Thus normally, spontaneous

physisorption will be less in graphite. Thus, the reported hydrogen storage happens due to chemisorption mainly. Even though carbon atoms in the planes are strongly bonded, the planes are held together via weak Van der Waal's forces, which make graphite to shear easily. Also, graphite is very brittle because ($\sigma + \pi$) bonds hold the atoms very strongly, but bonds breaks and crystal fractures, when get strained. Consequently, it can be powdered easily and is extremely opposite to diamond in hardness. Thus, the collection of sliding hexagonal planes, and is having a high susceptibility to the brittle fracture; graphite possesses infinite possibility to change it to various other nano forms. Therefore, it being used as the base material for the synthesis and production of the other nano allotropes such as graphene, CNTs, fullerenes and several other derivatives. Again, the constituent graphene planes can act as catalyst support centres for various nano catalysts.

Fig. 1. 12 Structure of graphite, pointing to 3D hexagonal unit and covalent bonds between carbon atoms, and Van der Waals bonds between graphene planes and hydrogen [ref. (Robert A. Varin, 2009)]

1.5.4 Graphitic carbon nitride

Similar to graphite, graphitic carbon nitride ($g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) is a layered material made of stacked planes of covalent C-N bonds hold together by Van der Waal's force. Each ring consists of tri- S- triazine ring units connected by planar amino groups. Since tri-S- triazine ring structure is a polymer with high thermal stability (600°C in air) and

chemical stability in both acidic and alkaline media, g-C₃N₄ is regarded as the most stable allotrope. This oldest reported polymer possessing the general structural formula (C₃N₃H)_n has been used as heterogeneous catalyst for decades. g-C₃N₄ possess a very heavy content of nitrogen supplied by the pyridinic and graphitic nitrogen within its structure. The highly porous nature of the material can make it as a preferable candidate for gas adsorption and storage. The heavy nitrogen content can provide the facilities for catalyst anchoring sites and hence make g-C₃N₄ as one of the best catalyst support material for various applications. Fig 1.13 shows the structural schematics of g-C₃N₄ along with melamine. The attractive attributes like effortless production, low cost, environment friendliness, heavy nitrogen content, high porosity and surface area, extremely good stability, unique optical characteristics, etc., make g-C₃N₄ a promising member in the application-based research industry.

The present experiments explore the gas adsorbing properties of g-C₃N₄ and project it as a promising material for the hydrogen storage industry. Its ability to act as a catalyst support medium has allowed the alloy nano catalyst facilitated high capacity solid state hydrogen storage through the synergic interaction. The present work uses the bulky g-C₃N₄ synthesised by the thermal condensation of melamine.

1.6. Motivation and objectives

By virtue of its exceptional 2D nature, Graphene has become a testing probe for many of the advanced presumptions of condensed matter physics along with many sided technological endeavours (Xu and Buehler, 2010a) . Albeit, graphene is endowed with many remarkable structural, physical and electronic qualities are; fabrication of almost all the graphene-based devices requires to include metal contacts in order to experience these attributes. Graphene-metal contact is an inevitable phase in the graphene-based device industry.

In general, the performance of any device can directly be affected by the quality of metal contacts e.g.; the presence of magnetic metals can perturb a spintronic device and it follows that the choice of contact metal is a key to the successful device fabrication.

Fig. 1. 13: The structure of g-C₃N₄ and melamine (Zhang et al., 2013)

Again, the substrate holding the graphene can also affect the sensitive physical properties like spin distribution of graphene and can induce the proximity effects in the system such as proximity induced magnetism (X Liu et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2013). Thus, there should be a clear idea about the metal- graphene interaction so that one can choose the most suitable metal for the application, which will not disturb the performance of the proposed devices in any circumstances.

Moreover, some metals such as Zn, Ni, Ag and Co have been used to tailor graphene or graphite shapes by either oxidation or hydrogenation. Nano cutting of graphene is also reported in presence of Nickel (Ci et al., 2008). Thus, in this scenario, many studies are focused on different metal adatom adsorptions on graphene and their effects; of which most of them are based on some theoretical models such as Monte Carlo, Molecular dynamics (MD) or Density functional theory (DFT) (El-Hilo, 2012; Tang et al., 2011; Zan et al., 2012). Nevertheless, unintentionally, depending on the approach used for calculations and choice of parameters, boundary conditions will limit the experimental implementations of these calculations and occasionally the results will be inconsistent. In practice, as bulk amounts are needed for industrial production, several other unanticipated parameters need to be considered. In addition, the fundamental interactions between metal and graphene influences the chemistry of graphene as well, e.g.; the catalytic activities (Gong et al., 2014; Vanin et al., 2009b).

In short, the presence of metal atom can influence and manipulate almost all the properties of graphene; since the hybrid interface between graphene and metals will exhibit interesting physics, hence one of the major studies concerned about the defects in graphene is the graphene- metal interaction study. However, our practical knowledge about the concerned subject is very limited.

The above discussed technical problem is not only related to graphene, but a recurrent issue faced by any material under research and application. Thus, it is evident that the emphasis in study must be given not only to graphene but also to other materials involved in various technologies. Hence, we are focusing the effect of metal permeation in different forms of carbon such as graphite, carbon nano tubes, graphitic carbon nitride, etc. along with graphene. The present study will be introducing a novel experimental procedure based on vacuum annealing and high temperature hydrogenation within the proximity of metal containers to examine the effects of indirect contact metal permeation on to the surface of carbon materials through container metal surface interfaces, which can be generalized to study the contact metal diffusion effects on all carbon derivatives. Furthermore, the studies available in the literature are having a main focus on the positions of adatom permeation than the effects caused by the diffused impurities. In practice, the extremely sensitive properties like magnetism or charge transport, catalytic activities and other electronic, thermal or optical characteristics will be affected considerably by the adatom permeation. Therefore, the present study analyses the effect of metal permeation on various properties such as magnetic behaviour and electrochemical performance along with morphological modifications. The details of the study are presented in chapter-3.

However, in most of the practical implementations, apart from the main base materials like pristine graphene or any other support material; numerous other accessory metal contributions will be included together or within the framework to facilitate various properties. Consequently, there is a scope for the study arises where the contact metal permeation can affect the performance of the other accessory metals (other than the main base material like graphene) associated with the system. Accordingly, we have explored the contact metal permeation effects in the Pd metal nano particles incorporated in the graphene/graphite systems. Moreover, an investigative study is done on the effect of present experimental conditions on the growth morphology and other properties of the Pd/Pt metal nano particles separately, which in succession lead to the

formation of novel Pd black dendrite structures having peculiar properties. Chapter-4 will be dedicated for this discussion.

Though hydrogen has turned out as the most desirable alternative energy source for the depleting fossil fuels and hence several means for its storage has become significant for the last few decades; the attempts to make an ideal hydrogen storage material are still under research. Despite some significant advances in certain properties, no materials have been developed, which can accommodate all the features of a good hydrogen storage material. High surface area, highly porous carbon materials have long been identified as efficient hydrogen storage materials by modifying them with hydrogen anchoring sites such as nitrogen or with the help of catalyst decoration. But the cumbersome synthesis processes, high cost, low energy range, unfavourable temperature range, slow kinetics, etc., make them impractical. Moreover, most of them possess a very poor volumetric capacity due to their high specific surface area, even though their gravimetric capacity is good. The most desirable two-dimensional material graphene is predicted as a good material for hydrogen storage, but being a quasi- two-dimensional system, the volume density is not well defined for pristine single layered graphene.

In this scenario, the present work addresses these important issues related to hydrogen storage. Besides, the present one- step synthesis method is highly practical and scalable because it directly uses the natural materials. Again, the efforts to bring in the catalytic activities of noble metals like palladium is facing the challenges such as high cost, poor stability due to hydrogen corrosion, etc. Therefore in present work, alloying of cobalt with palladium in conjunction with nitrogen incorporation is done through some simple in- situ modification techniques which could improve the synergic interaction of catalyst centres with the support material and provide an efficient hydrogen spill over. However, attempts are again made to implement non- precious alloy nano catalyst such as magnesium -nickel alloy, to support the idea of cost effective material. Hence the present work (discussed in chapter-5) can be a promising insight to the impending hydrogen energy technology.

1.7 Scope of the work

The scope of the work is to investigate the effect of contact metal permeation in carbon-based systems and other metals incorporated within the system (with the example of Pd

based systems); and catalyst metal- carbon interactions aided hydrogen storage in low surface area carbon materials

More specifically,

- To observe the indirect contact metal permeation from containers in carbon-based materials through vacuum annealing and high temperature hydrogenation reactions within the proximity of container metals- development of a novel experimental technique.
- To investigate the effect of contact metal permeation in morphological modification and magnetic response, verified with electrochemical detection.
- To study the influence of contact metal diffusion in other metals involved in the system through the investigations on Pd nanoparticles incorporated in carbon-based systems.
- To explore a new optimised procedure for the synthesis of novel palladium black dendrite structures having unique characteristics.
- To identify the potential low-cost, high capacity, compact hydrogen storage materials by catalyst aided hydrogen adsorption studies in low surface area carbon materials.

CHAPTER 2

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES AND MODIFICATIONS

The experimental strategies adopted and instruments used for the study are described in this chapter. General procedures involving the synthesis, characterization, application and other investigational studies of different materials used are explained in brief. The indigenously fabricated basic set up for gas adsorption-desorption studies and its modification to accommodate the newly proposed experimental procedure is described elaborately with principle of operation.

2.1 Synthesis techniques and procedures

A brief outline of the synthesis techniques adopted for different materials employed in the experimental studies are given. In general, we have predominantly utilized low temperature thermal condensation techniques, high temperature thermal reduction and low temperature hydrogen reduction for basic material synthesis; and catalytic chemical vapour deposition and ethylene glycol reduction for nanoparticle synthesis as well as decoration; of which all are dry techniques except the last one which is solution based.

The following sections will be covering the detailed procedures for each synthesis technique, wherever necessary in connection with the concerned synthesised material. Fig. 2.1 and 2.2 depicts the general set up used for the material synthesis.

2.1.1. Synthesis of Graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) based composites:

Materials used:

Melamine powders, Palladium (II) chloride (99%), Cobaltous Chloride hexa- hydrate (CoCl₂.6H₂O), Ethylene glycol (99%) and Sodium Hydroxide pellets (all purchased from Sigma Aldrich), high purity Nitrogen gas (99.999%) were used. De- ionized water is used according to the need.

Fig. 2. 1 Schematic representation of the indigenously fabricated chemical vapor deposition unit used for various synthesis purposes.

Fig. 2. 2 Photographic representation of the indigenously fabricated chemical vapor deposition unit used for various synthesis purposes.

2.1.1.1. Synthesis of g-C₃N₄ powders

For g-C₃N₄ powder synthesis, we adopted simple, cost effective method known as low temperature thermal condensation of melamine (Zhang, Y, et al., Sci Rep.) Around 2 g of well ground melamine powders were taken inside an alumina boat, which was placed in the central part of a tubular furnace for heat treatment. As the temperature reaches 600⁰C, high purity nitrogen gas (99.999%) was allowed in to the furnace at a

flow rate of (75-150) sccm for 4 hours. However, the nitrogen gas may contribute to the anticipated nitrogen content of the product; one can use argon atmosphere also. The furnace was then allowed to cool down to room temperature and the product was taken out and ground to fine powders. This yellow powder is labeled as g-C₃N₄. One can use urea instead of melamine for the same material synthesis.

2.1.1.2. Synthesis of Pd/ g-C₃N₄ and Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ powders

The Pd or Pd₃Co nanoparticles decoration on g-C₃N₄ was done by ethylene glycol (EG) reduction method. At first, for both synthesis, around 250 mg of well ground g-C₃N₄ powder was dispersed in 200 ml of EG by 10 minutes ultra-sonication followed by 12 hours mechanical stirring. Then, the following procedures may be adopted for each material.

Pd/ g-C₃N₄:

The required amount of 1 wt % PdCl₂ solution is added to the stirring medium in a drop wise manner and allowed to stir for next 24 hours. After that the pH of the solution as adjusted to 11 by adding NaOH (0.5 M on EG) solution followed by a 6-hour refluxing at 125⁰C. Water is avoided during the entire reaction, in order to ensure the proper reaction of g-C₃N₄. The final product is washed with DI water, filtered out and dried in vacuum oven 60⁰C for 12 hours. The dark-grey coloured sample is collected and labelled as Pd-g-C₃N₄.

Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄:

The required amount of precursors PdCl₂ and CoCl₂.6H₂O (1 wt % standard solutions) were then added in a drop wise manner simultaneously according to proportion. NaOH (0.5 M on EG) solution was added to make pH of the solution to 11 followed by 6 hours refluxing at 125⁰C. The final product was washed with DI water, filtered out and dried in vacuum oven 60⁰C for 12 hours and labeled as Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄, which is dark-grey in color.

2.1.2. Synthesis of Graphite based composites:

All the graphite-based synthesis discussed here involves a simple single step process of catalytic chemical vapour deposition using tubular furnace.

Materials used:

Graphite powder (<45 μ m size), melamine powder, Boric acid powder, palladium (II) chloride (99%), cobaltous chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Magnesium chloride ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Nickel chloride ($\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (all from Sigma Aldrich), high purity hydrogen gas (99.99%) and deionized water.

2.1.2.1. Pd₃Co- N- Gr and Pd₃Co- B- Gr

As purchased graphite powders were mixed with melamine in (1:1) ratio using sufficient amount of DI water by a mechanical stirring of 15 minutes; following which the required amount of metal precursors (1 wt% standard solutions of PdCl_2 and $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to satisfy the 20 wt% of the targeted loading of Pd and Co in 3:1 ratio) were added and continued the stirring for 6 hours and finally the mixture was dried overnight in a vacuum oven at 60 $^\circ$ C.

The dried mixture is well ground and uniformly loaded in a quartz boat placed in the central part of a tubular furnace, flushed with Argon gas for 10 minutes and started the heat treatment. As the temperature of the sample reaches by 250 $^\circ$ C, hydrogen gas is allowed to the system for 30 minutes. Then the temperature of the system is raised to 700 $^\circ$ C and kept for 30 minutes more. The furnace was then cooled down to room temperature and the product was carefully taken out and labelled as Pd₃Co- N- Gr.

For the synthesis of Pd₃Co- B- Gr, the above procedure is repeated by replacing required amount of boric acid in place of melamine.

For comparison of the performance, we have used Pd₃Co- Gr. The synthesis procedure is the same as described above except that the base material is the as purchased graphite itself without melamine/boric acid. The catalyst nano particles are decorated directly over the graphite.

2.1.2.2. Mg₂Ni- N- Gr and Mg₂Ni- B- Gr

The procedure involved here is the same as before. The as purchased graphite powders were mixed with melamine in (1:1) ratio using sufficient amount of DI water by a mechanical stirring of 15 minutes; following which the required amount of metal precursors (1 wt% standard solutions of MgCl_2 and $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to satisfy the 20 wt%

of the targeted loading of Mg and Ni in 2:1 ratio) were added and continued the stirring for 6 hours and finally the mixture was dried overnight in a vacuum oven at 60°C.

The dried mixture is well ground and uniformly loaded in a quartz boat placed in the central part of a tubular furnace, flushed with Argon gas for 10 minutes and started the heat treatment. As the temperature of the sample reaches by 250°C, hydrogen gas is allowed to the system for 30 minutes. Then the temperature of the system is raised to 700°C and kept for 30 more minutes. The furnace was then cooled down to room temperature and the product was carefully taken out and labelled as Mg₂Ni- N- Gr.

For the synthesis of Mg₂Ni- B- Gr, the above procedure is repeated by replacing required amount of boric acid in place of melamine.

2.1.3. Synthesis of reduced graphene oxide(r-GO)

Materials used:

Graphite (Aldrich, 99.99% purity; < 100 ppm impurity); Potassium permanganate (KMnO₄, 99.5%), concentrated Sulphuric acid (98%), Sodium nitrate (NaNO₃, 99.5%) purchased from Rankem Chemicals, India; Hydrogen peroxide (30%) procured from S D Fine – Chem Ltd. India were used. Deionized (DI) water was used for all reactions.

2.1.3.1. Synthesis of Graphitic Oxide (GO):

Graphitic Oxide was prepared by Hummers' method. 2 g of graphite was added to 46 ml of conc. H₂SO₄ under continuous stirring in an ice bath. 1 g NaNO₃ and 6 g KMnO₄ were added gradually and successively. The ice bath was removed and suspension was allowed to come to room temperature. 92 ml of DI water was then added to above mixture. After 15 min, the above mixture was diluted to 280 ml using warm water. Following this, 3 % H₂O₂ was added till the solution turned bright yellow. The suspension was filtered and the filter cake was washed with warm water, repeatedly. The residue was diluted using water and the resulting suspension was centrifuged. The final product was dried under vacuum and stored in vacuum desiccators, until further use.

2.1.3.2. Synthesis of thermally exfoliated graphene (TEG):

Thermally exfoliated graphene (TEG) was obtained by exfoliation of GO at 1050 °C under Argon atmosphere. A small amount of GO was taken in a quartz boat and introduced into a preheated (1050 °C) tubular furnace. Argon atmosphere was maintained inside the furnace. The sudden increase in temperature (~ 2000 °C/min) resulted in exfoliation of GO to graphene.

2.1.3.3. Synthesis of Hydrogen exfoliated graphene (HEG):

Hydrogen exfoliated graphene (HEG) was synthesized as follows (Adarsh Kaniyoor et al.). The quartz tube with GO placed inside a furnace was flushed with Ar for 15 min, followed by H₂ for 5 min at room temperature (30°C). The temperature was raised to 200°C in the presence of H₂. At 200°C, exfoliation occurred immediately but the flow of H₂ was continued for another 30 min. The furnace was allowed to cool naturally to room temperature.

2.2. Characterization tools

After synthesis process, different type of material characterisation techniques has been availed to test the material quality before exploiting to the designed experiments. The crystal structure, surface morphology, size and distribution of the particles, elemental composition and distribution, chemical state, decomposition temperature, catalyst loading, structural stability, surface area and porosity, purity testing, etc. are analysed using different experimental tools. Again, certain physical property changes before and after the experiments are also examined using different well-known techniques. The following session gives a brief explanation of the different instruments and methods used in the present study.

2.2.1. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

The preliminary characterisation tool for any material is the X-ray diffraction profile as it can be the signature of the crystal structure and composition. As the atoms of a crystalline material are arranged periodically (with an inter atomic distance, d), when a coherent monochromatic beam of X-rays (wavelength λ) incident on the sample specimen at an angle θ , the diffraction of X-rays can occur when Bragg's law is satisfied, i.e.; $n \lambda = 2d \sin \theta$, where θ can be varied either rotating the sample stage or

the incident angle. The diffracted waves interfere constructively to give an intensity distribution pattern. On plotting this intensity distribution versus 2θ or d- spacing, the XRD pattern is obtained. From this XRD profile of the material, the information regarding crystal structure, crystallite size, lattice spacing, elemental composition, etc. can be derived.

The present experiments employed PANanalytical X'Pert Pro X –ray Diffractometer (operates in 40 kV potential and 30 mA current) with Ni- filtered Cu K_{α} ($\lambda = 1.54\text{\AA}$) as the X-ray source. The diffraction patterns were recorded in ambient conditions, by varying 2θ in step size of 0.016 degree/min. in the range of 5° to 90° . The samples for measurements were prepared in the form of powders pressed on the glass slides or aluminium plates.

The crystallite size (t) of the material is calculated using the Scherrer formula,

$$t = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \dots\dots\dots 2 \quad (1)$$

where θ is the reference peak position, λ is the wavelength of X- rays used, β is the full width half maxima (FWHM) of the reference peak and K is the dimensionless shape factor ranging from 0.9 to 1. The spectral analysis has been done using PANanalytical X'Pert High Score plus software and the crystal structure were found comparing with the PCPDFWIN database.

2.2.2. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy is a powerful spectroscopic analysis technique used to observe vibrational, rotational, and other low-frequency modes in a system; which in turn results the identification, quantification and classification of the materials. In this technique, the specimen is illuminated using a monochromatic light source such as laser and the scattered light is detected. Most of the incident beam is elastically scattered (Rayleigh scattering) while a fraction of beam is inelastically or Raman scattered due to their interaction with the vibrational energy levels of the specimen. As result the detected light will be appearing with shifted energy. A plot between intensity of the inelastically scattered light and the observed shift gives the Raman spectrum of the material, which will be a characteristic signature.

In the present experiments, the vibrational spectra of the samples were recorded via the Witec Alfa 300 Confocal Raman spectrometer, using the Nd:YAG laser of wavelength 532 nm (2.33 eV) as the excitation source. The studies were performed within the wavenumber range of 100- 3000 cm^{-1} with a typical resolution of 3 cm^{-1} . The laser spot size was kept at $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ and the intensities were kept low to avoid the laser induced damages to the samples. Each spectrum was averaged 50 times with an integration time set to 1 second. The samples for the study are prepared by pressing the powders on the glass slide.

2.2.3. Field Emission Scanning Electron microscopy (FESEM)

The surface morphological analysis is important in the case of nano level studies. SEM analysis is used to image the surface morphology of the materials. In this technique, a beam of electrons produced by thermionic field emission is accelerated towards the specimen by applying a positive potential (0.5 keV to 50 keV). The beam of electrons is then focussed using two condenser lenses to a narrow spot which then passes through deflection coils before impinging on the sample. These deflection coils enable the scanning of the sample surface along the X-Y axis. The primary electrons can be reflected elastically (high energy back scattered electrons), after interaction with the sample surface, which can lead to the emission of inelastically scattered secondary electrons (low energy $< 0.5 \text{ eV}$) and can also lead to the emission of characteristic X-rays. The secondary electrons are detected via Everhart- Thornley detector and converted to digital images through suitable hardware and software. The X-rays are detected by another dedicated detector and can be used for elemental analysis and mapping of the sample.

For the present work we have used Hitachi S4800 HR-SEM, FESEM, FEI QUANTA 400F and Inspect F50 high resolution FESEM. The sample preparation for the study is done by pressing a small amount of sample on a carbon tape pasted on an aluminum stub. Sputtering was done for certain samples wherever necessary. The stub is then attached to the sample holder and the imaging was done high vacuum for conducting samples and low vacuum for insulating samples.

2.2.4. Transmission Electron microscopy (TEM)

For the specific study of the morphological structure and modification in high resolution, transmission electron microscopic imaging is used. In this technique, a

highly energetic beam (100 to 400 keV) of electrons is passed through an ultra-thin layer of the sample. A shadow image is formed by the interaction of the transmitted beam which is magnified and focussed into photographic film or camera. Since the electrons passing through are used to image the sample, it is possible to 'see through' the sample. Contrast between regions of different thickness is created due to the difference in number of electrons passing through. The use of electron beam enables high resolution imaging of the samples since the electrons have very low wavelengths. The entire electron path in the column is kept under UHV conditions (10^{-11} mbar). For the present studies, we have employed transmission electron microscope FEITecnaiG²20 S-TWIN, 200 keV operated at 200 kV. The electron source is a Schottky field emitter made up of ZrO₂ coated tungsten with a high maximum beam current >100nA. The sample preparation was done by dispersing the material in ethanol and drop casted over the carbon coated copper grid (200 meshes) followed by drying overnight in ambient atmosphere.

2.2.5. Thermal analysis

Thermal analysis is study in which the property change of a sample is recorded over time with the temperature changes. Different techniques such as thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential thermal analysis (DTA), Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) are there. In TGA, the amount of weight loss of the sample is recorded as a function of the temperature.

This measurement provides information about the decomposition temperature of the sample, purity determination, etc. In DSC, the difference in the amount of heat required to raise the temperature of the sample and the difference is noted as a function of temperature. Through this method, the physical phenomena, such as phase transitions, absorption and desorption (exothermic or endothermic) as well as chemical phenomena including chemisorption or solid-gas reactions can be concluded. In the present work, TGA studies were carried out using NEZSCHanalyser and Q500 Hi-Res TGA instrument equipped with microbalance system, which is suitable for TGA and DSC measurements under Nitrogen/Air ambience from Room temp. to 1300 °C. Powder samples weighing ~ 10 mg were heated from room temperature at a heating rate of 20°C/ min and the weight loss was recorded and plotted using the suitable software. Different sample holders are provided with the instrument such as Al₂O₃, Pt or PtRu which can be used according to the nature of the samples.

2.2.6. Surface area/porosity measurements

The specific surface area and porosity of the samples are analysed using Micromeritics ASAP2020 analyzer. The Brunauer- Emmett- Teller (BET) and Barrett- Joyner- Halenda (BJH) theory provides the precise analysis of the specific surface area, pore size distribution and pore volume of the materials by multilayer nitrogen adsorption desorption isotherms recorded as function of relative pressure. According to BJH theory, porous materials are classified as microporous (pore size < 2-50 nm), mesoporous (pore size is in between 2-50 nm) and macro porous (pore size > 2-50 nm). BET theory explains the physical ‘multi-layer’ adsorption of gases on solids and is an extension of Langmuir ‘monolayer’ adsorption theory. When a specimen is exposed to gas (generally for practical measurements, non-reactive gases such as nitrogen is used.), a certain volume of the gas will be adsorbed. The amount of gas adsorbed on depends on a number of factors such as temperature, gas pressure and strength of the interaction between the gas and solid. Since gas interacts very weakly with solids, in order to get a sufficient adsorption to cover at least a monolayer, the temperature has to be reduced substantially. This can be achieved practically using liquid nitrogen (LN₂). As the pressure is increased, multilayer of the gas molecules is adsorbed on the surface. The total adsorbed amount and its relative pressure is determined and using BET equation, the amount of monolayer gas adsorbed is obtained which is then converted into the surface area of the material.

2.2.7. UV-visible Spectroscopy:

The optical absorption characteristics of the materials in the UV- visible regions were carried out using UV-visible-NIR spectroscopy. JASCO V-570 double beam spectrometer is used for the present analysis. The absorption and transmission spectra were recorded by dispersing the samples in ethanol and filled in quartz cuvettes.

2.2.8. Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FT-IR) Spectroscopy:

FT-IR spectroscopy is used for the determination of the functional groups in a sample. Functional groups are molecular orbitals formed between various atoms which vibrate at characteristic frequencies, whose energy difference falls on infra-red (IR) region. Hence similar to UV-Vis. Spectroscopy, the sample specimen can be irradiated with IR radiation and the information can be collected.

2.3. Electrochemical measurement:

Electrochemistry concerns the measurement of electrical quantities such as current, potential or charge and their relationship to chemical parameters. In contrast to the other chemical reactions, electrochemical reactions mainly occur at the electrode- solution interfaces.

2.3.1. Cyclic voltammetry:

Cyclic voltammetry is the most versatile and popular technique to analyse the qualitative information about the electrochemical reactions.

Through the rapid identification of redox potential of the distinctive electrochemical species, CV provides considerable information about the thermodynamics of a redox process, kinetics of heterogeneous reactions, and analysis of coupled electrochemical reactions or adsorption processes. In this technique, the potential of the working electrode is scanned by a triangular potential waveform shown in the Fig. 2.3.A. Here the potential is swept from E_1 to E_2 and the rate of scanning is the gradient of the line (measured V/s). If the potential is stopped in the first half, it is known as linear sweep experiment; and if it returns back to E_2 , then it is known as cyclic voltammetry. Depending on the requirement single or multiple cycle can be done. The potentiostat measures the resulting current due to applied voltage (potential), during the potential sweep. The plot of current versus potential is known as 'cyclic voltammogram' or CV; which can give insight to many physical and chemical properties of the reaction.

Fig. 2.3. B. shows a typical cyclic voltammogram curve; which has two major characteristics- the peak height (I_p) and the potential at which the peak occurs (E_p). For present measurements, the most common configuration for dynamic electrochemical experiments- the three-electrode system is used; (see Fig. 2.4 and Fig. 2.5. in for detailed view) which comprises three electrodes based electrochemical cell such as a glassy carbon electrode (GCE, area $\sim 0.07 \text{ mm}^2$) as working electrode (WE), Ag/AgCl electrode as reference electrode (RE) and a Pt wire as a counter or auxiliary electrode (CE).

Fig. 2. 3 The potential- time scan profile used for cyclic voltammetry and a typical cyclic voltammogram depicting the peak position E_p and peak height I_p . (Ref. D.A.C. Brownson, 2013)

These three electrodes are connected to the potentiostat which allows a potential difference between RE and WE to be controlled with minimal Ohmic interference (IR drop). In order to keep the applied potential between the WE and RE stable, the current through the RE is minimised by avoiding the polarization of RE. Fig. 2.4 shows a typical experimental setup and the schematic showing the process behind. Sodium/potassium phosphate buffer solution (0.1M PBS), NaOH solution, HCl solution (0.1M) were used as the supporting electrolyte.

In the typical procedure, in order to study the electrocatalytic activity of the materials, modified GCE has been prepared by drop casting the material on the shining surface of the electrode. All the analysis has been done using the CH Instrument (CHI 608C) electrochemical workstation as shown in Fig. 2.5.

Fig. 2. 4 A typical experimental set-up showing the three-electrode system- reference electrode (RE, Ag/AgCl electrode), the working electrode (WE) and the counter electrode (CE, a platinum rod) immersed into an electrolyte solution (A). A simple electronic circuit equivalent to the electrochemical cell (B). A potentiostat is needed for running electrochemical experiments. Note, all the resistances are equal except R_D which is variable. (Ref. D.A.C. Brownson, 2013)

Fig. 2. 5 The digital photograph showing the CH Instrument electrochemical workstation (A) and the detailed view of the three-electrode cell (B).

2.4. Magnetic measurement:

Being one of the most sensitive property of any material, magnetic response analysis is an extremely powerful tool for the research regarding either basic physics or application levels. Here in the present study, evolution of magnetic properties of the materials after execution of the proposed experimental procedures for contact metal permeation is investigated in detail. The fundamental magnetic response studies attempted here include the basic hysteresis curve (Magnetisation M versus magnetic field strength H) analysis at different temperatures and the temperature variation of magnetisation (M versus T) using field cooling (FC) and zero field cooling (ZFC) methods.

Quantum Design MPMS SQUID VSM (Fig. 2.6.); utilizes a superconducting magnet (a solenoid of superconducting wire), can supply a magnetic field up to 7 Tesla has been utilized in the present experimental studies. The SQUID, magnet and the sample chamber are cooled with liquid helium. To conserve liquid helium, the system is designed to use less costly liquid nitrogen to intercept heat bound for the liquid helium tank.

The powder samples are made into tiny pellets wrapped in Teflon and are mounted inside the system. The measurements were performed at regular intervals, following the typical procedures.

2.5. Hydrogen storage studies:

The solid-state hydrogen storage properties of materials are investigated using hydrogen adsorption/desorption studies. There are mainly two feasible methods reported for measuring the amount of hydrogen adsorbed or desorbed- gravimetric methods and gasometrical methods. In gravimetric method, the concentration of hydrogen stored in the material is extracted by measuring the changes in the weight of the sample due to hydrogenation and then dehydrogenation. But the precise and accurate measurement of the weight change is crucial in this method; as it can give a high error probability due to many factors like temperature change, buoyancy effect, effect of gas pressure and mechanical vibrations. While gasometric method overcomes these draw -back by employing a different method for calculation of stored hydrogen concentration. Here hydrogen concentration is obtained by volumetric or pressure reduction methods. In volumetric method, the number of moles of hydrogen

adsorbed/desorbed (Δn) by the material is calculated from the change in volume (ΔV) measured at constant pressure and temperature; where as in pressure reduction method, the hydrogen concentration is calculated from the changes in pressure (ΔP) measured at constant volume and temperature. For the present experiments, the pressure reduction method is employed with the utilization of Sieverts' apparatus.

Fig. 2. 6 The photographic view of the Quantum Design MPMS SQUID VSM system (Ref: <https://www.qdusa.com/>)

2.5.1. The Sieverts' apparatus:

According to Blach and Gray- 2007, Sieverts' apparatus is an experimental facility used for measuring gas uptake by solid sorbents at high pressure and is universally accepted as accurate, when practiced with reasonable care. The bloc diagram for the set-up is shown in Fig. 2.7. This indigenously fabricated set-up designed for manual operation consists of a measuring section and a reactor assembly. The measuring section consists of stainless steel (SS) tubes, needle valves, tee and elbow joints (NOVA SWISS, Switzerland). The SS tubes and tee and elbow joints can withstand up to a maximum pressure of 4000 bar and the needle valves are secured within 1000 bar. A strain gauge-based pressure transducer of range 0 - 100 bar (Syscon, India) is used to measure the hydrogen gas pressure inside the system. A digital photograph showing the complete set-up is as shown in Fig. 2.8. The reactor assembly part consists of a specially designed

sample cell assembly which can withstand high pressure and temperature and is kept inside a temperature-controlled furnace. The furnace is capable of heating up to 1200°C and the temperature is controlled by a PID controller-based temperature monitor facility with an accuracy of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. T_4 is used to isolate the sample cell from the measuring section.

Fig. 2. 7 The block diagram of the Sieverts' apparatus used for hydrogen adsorption/desorption studies.

Fig. 2. 8 The digital photograph of the experimental set up used for hydrogen adsorption/desorption studies.

The system is connected to the hydrogen cylinders using the valve T₁, to the standard volume cell using T₃ and to the sample cell assembly using T₄. High vacuum diffusion pumps (HIND HIVAC, INDIA) are connected to the system through T₂ for achieving a high vacuum of 10⁻⁵ mbar.

2.5.2. The sample cell assembly:

Fig. 2.9. illustrates photograph and schematic of the sample cell assembly used for hydrogenation studies. The sample cell consists of a cylindrical copper block (18 mm diameter) tightly fitted to another cylindrical SS block (18 mm inner diameter and 28 mm outer diameter). A required hole of 10 mm is drilled at the centre of the copper block to place the sample tube. In order to avoid the reaction between sample and the sample cell, the sample is taken in an 8 mm quartz tube and is inserted into the bottom of the sample cell. To measure the sample temperature, a thermocouple (K- type chromel- alumel thermocouple) is positioned very close to sample through a pressure sealed assembly mounted on the upper flange. The sample cell assembly is kept inside a resistance furnace, fitted to a vertically movable stand. The reactor assembly is attached to the measuring section by adjusting the vertical distance using movable stand. A water jacket is connected at the top portion of the sample cell assembly to protect the O- ring, which lies between the top and bottom flanges.

2.5.3. Volume calibration:

Initially the sample cell volume V₁ was determined ($V_1 = 101.20 \pm 0.01 \text{ cm}^3$) by filling it with a measured amount of deionized water. The interconnecting tube volume V_d is obtained as follows. The whole system is evacuated to 10⁻⁶ mbar by opening valves T₂ and T₃ and closing the valves T₁ and T₄. Then the constant volume (V₁) and connecting tubes are filled with hydrogen gas (of 99.99 % purity) at pressure P₁. Hydrogen pressure (P₁) is allowed to stay only in the constant volume (V₁) by closing S₃ and the remaining part of the system was evacuated by opening T₂.

Fig. 2. 9 The schematic and photograph of the sample cell assembly used hydrogenation of the samples.

Fig. 2. 10 The plot obtained for the volume calibration of the sample cell at different temperatures.

Thus, the number of moles of hydrogen gas (n) present in the volume V_1 can be obtained using the ideal gas equation

$$P_1V_1 = nRT \dots\dots\dots 2 (2)$$

However, hydrogen gas molecules do not behave like an ideal gas at high pressure and hence van der Waals correction factors for the size of molecules (a) and the intermolecular force (b) have been applied to the ideal gas equation 2.(2):

$$\left(P_1 + \frac{n^2}{V_1^2} a \right) (V_1 - nb) = nRT \dots\dots\dots 2 (3)$$

Thus, the number of moles of hydrogen gas (n) present in the system is known from the equation 2.(4):

$$abn^3 - aV_1n^2 + (RT + P_1b)V_1^2n - P_1V_1^3 = 0 \dots\dots\dots 2 (4)$$

Where $a = 2.48 \times 10^{-5} \text{ J m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-2}$, $b = 2.66 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $R = 8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and T is the absolute temperature. After closing the valves T_1, T_2 and T_4 , the valve T_3 is opened so that the hydrogen will now occupy the unknown volume V_d resulting in a final pressure P_2 in the system. In this condition, n_1 moles of hydrogen will present in the volume V_1 as given by the equation 2. (5) and n_2 moles of hydrogen will be occupied by the interconnecting tubes of volume V_d as given by the equation 2. (6):

$$abn^3_1 - aV_1n^2_1 + (RT + P_2b)V_1^2n_1 - P_2V_1^3 = 0 \dots\dots\dots 2 (5)$$

$$n_2 = n - n_1 \dots\dots\dots 2 (6)$$

Knowing P_2 and n_2 , the unknown volume V_d can be calculated from the equation 2. (7):

$$P_2V^3_d - (RT + P_2b)n_2V^2_d + an^2_2V_d - abn^3_2 = 0 \dots\dots\dots 2(7)$$

The values of the constant volume used in the present experimental facility are as follows: $V_1 = 101.20 \text{ cm}^3$, $V_d = 5.19 \text{ cm}^3$, respectively. The error in the volume, measurement is $\pm 0.02 \text{ cm}^3$.

Volumes of a sample cell (V_a) are calibrated at various temperatures similar to the procedure given above to determine constant volumes. The temperature is measured by using a Chromel -Alumel thermocouple placed inside the reactor cell. The plot between

the temperature and volume of the sample cell is shown in Fig. 2.10 and the corresponding values are given in Table 2.1. The error in calibrated volumes is $\pm 0.02 \text{ cm}^3$.

Table 2. 1. Volume calibration data for the sample cell at different temperatures

Sl. No.	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Sample cell volume (cm^3)
1	0	31.58
2	34	27.52
3	50	26.46
4	70	25.63
5	100	25.01

2.5.4. Determination of pressure- composition (PC) isotherms:

As mentioned earlier, the hydrogen adsorption -desorption studies were performed in Sieverts apparatus using the pressure reduction method by applying the Van der Waals corrections for the hydrogen gas. Using the following typical procedure, PC isotherms of the sample of given mass 'm' can be obtained. Initially the sample is placed inside the quartz sample holder and flushed with hydrogen gas for several times. Further the sample is degassed under vacuum heat treatment before exposing it to hydrogen for getting activated for a fresh reaction. The process of degassing includes heating the sample to high temperatures ($\sim 300 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) under high vacuum conditions (10^{-5} mbar) for about 2 h in order to remove any dissolved gases that may be present in the sample. After that the sample is cooled down to the desired temperature before allowing the hydrogen of particular pressure to the sample chamber. At this temperature, PC isotherm is determined as follows.

Consider the three conditions of the system, where an initial pressure P_i occupies the initial volume V_i with the number of moles n_i , an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} at the initial volume V_i with the number of moles n_1 and an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} at the cell volume V_c with the number of moles n_2 . Applying the Van der Waals correction coefficients 'a' and 'b' for hydrogen, these three conditions will be evolved as the following gas equations.

$$abn_i^3 + aV_i n_i^2 + (RT + P_i b)V_i^2 n_i - P_i V_i^3 = 0 \dots\dots\dots 2(8)$$

$$abn_1^3 + aV_1 n_1^2 + (RT + P_{eq} b)V_1^2 n_1 - P_{eq} V_1^3 = 0 \dots\dots\dots 2(9)$$

$$abn_2^3 + aV_c n_2^2 + (RT + P_{eq} b)V_c^2 n_2 - P_{eq} V_c^3 = 0 \dots\dots\dots 2(10)$$

where T is the sample cell temperature and R is the universal gas constant.

The number of moles of hydrogen adsorbed can be calculated as follows:

$$\Delta n = n_i - (n_1 + n_2) \dots\dots\dots 2(11)$$

By knowing the value of Δn , the hydrogen concentration of the sample (wt %) for a given mass ‘m’ at an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} (gravimetric capacity) can be calculated as

$$Wt\% \text{ of } (H) = 2 * \frac{\Delta n}{m} * 100 \dots\dots\dots 2(12)$$

Thus, it shows the mass of hydrogen in 100 grams of the stored material. By knowing the value of the bulk density (ρ) of the material, we can find the volumetric capacity, i.e.; the amount of hydrogen present in the unit volume of the stored material as gram per liter (g/L).

The entire cycle can be repeated after degassing the stored hydrogen from the sample

The system is calibrated using the standard bulk Pd metal sample before measurements and the corresponding pressure - composition (P-C) isotherm plotted for 160°C temperature is as shown in Fig. 2.11. This obtained data is consistent with the literature data (Alefled et al., 1978).

2.6. Contact metal permeation studies:

The contact metal permeation studies for different type of materials are done with the help of Sieverts’ apparatus with a slight modification according to the requirement. We have adopted a new experimental procedure for facilitating the indirect metal diffusion to the desired samples through container metal interfaces in extreme conditions such as high vacuum, high temperature and hydrogen pressure. The sample cell assembly of the system is modified to perform the indirect metal diffusion reactions. The following section will be giving a brief outline of the experiment, while chapter -3 will discuss the experiment in detail.

Fig. 2. 11 The PC isotherm at 160°C of the standard Pd sample used for calibration of the system.

2.6.1. Experimental Hypothesis:

The experimental conditions must introduce the circumstances which can lead to the indirect contact metal permeation to the samples. Here the conditions under consideration are (i) high temperature vacuum annealing and (ii) high temperature hydrogenation, within the proximity of metal containers. The vacuum annealing will be introducing surface defects such as SW defects in the form of corrugations to the sample as well as allow the container metal to diffuse into the surface of the samples. The hydrogenation at high temperature will also aid the contact metal permeation process by diffusing the container metal into the sample surface. Moreover, the high temperature hydrogenation of the metal container will promote hydrogen assisted cracking or hydrogen embrittlement to the container metals and which in effect will induce contact metal permeation to the inside samples.

The more defects are created due to vacuum annealing, the more hydrogen will be attracted by the sample and hence the concentration of defects will be increasing and a chain process will be continuing after a few repetition of the number of cycles of experiment.

2.6.2. Experimental modifications:

We have modified the Sieverts' apparatus according to our present experimental need. The sample cell assembly of the setup is improved to withstand the new experimental conditions. The sample tube is carefully fabricated to allow the vacuum and hydrogen inside, so that the enclosed sample will be subjected to extreme conditions, which can affect its properties. In order to aid the reaction between sample and the diffused hydrogen, the sample is taken in a screw-threaded cylindrical sample holder made of nickel or 316 SS or Fe (the container metal, for which the contact metal permeation is to be studied) and is inserted into the bottom of the sample cell. The detailed view of the sample filling and the sample cell is as shown in Fig. 2.12 and Fig. 2.13. The significance of the present setup is that this can be generalized to perform the study related to any material with any metal contact by changing the metal/alloy of the sample cell - made.

Fig. 2. 12 Photograph showing the sample container and the method of sample filling. (a) and (b) shows the hollow sample container (6 cm length, 5 mm diameter and 1 mm thickness) with grooved lid made out of metal (here SS-316). (c) and (d) shows how the sample is filling inside the container.

To measure the sample temperature, a thermocouple is positioned very close to sample through a pressure seal assembly mounted on the upper flange. The sample cell assembly is kept inside a resistance furnace, fitted to a vertically movable stand. The reactor assembly is attached to the measuring section by adjusting the vertical distance using movable stand. A water jacket is connected at the top portion of the sample cell assembly to protect the O- ring, which lies between the top and bottom flanges.

2.6.3. Experimental procedure:

The present experimental procedure is designed for the contact metal permeation studies on materials based on the literature support and some novel ideas.

Fig. 2. 13 The photograph showing the sample cell assembly and the method of inserting the sample cell. (a) the sample tube is inserting into the sample cell, (b) the full view of the sample cell assembly with copper bottom to withstand the hydrogen diffusion at high temperatures, (c) and (d) shows how the close view of the final stage of the sample insertion.

The typical procedure followed consists of (i) vacuum annealing process and (ii) hydrogenation process. The details of the procedure are given in chapter-3. The temperature and allowed hydrogen pressure are varied accordingly with different samples. The analysis of the samples is done at each stage such as with vacuum annealing and without hydrogenation or with vacuum annealing and hydrogenation, etc. The experiment is repeated using different samples, different number of cycles of vacuum annealing and hydrogenation, different hydrogen pressures, various temperatures, various container metals/alloys, etc.

NB: All magnetic data presented in this thesis are the direct data obtained from the measurement. No diamagnetic corrections are incorporated.

CHAPTER 3

OBSERVATION OF CONTACT METAL PERMEATION ON TO CARBON MATERIALS

Contact metal permeation study is the foremost part of the present thesis work. This chapter elaborately explains the observation of indirect contact metal permeation on to the surface of different carbon materials through container metal interfaces, investigated using a specially designed novel experimental procedure. The newly developed experimental practice can be generalized to study the above-mentioned phenomenon in any materials using several metals or alloys as contact interface. However, the present discussion mainly focusses on the indirect contact metal permeation on to the surface of carbon-based materials with the most common alloy, stainless steel, as the contact surface. The effects of metal diffusion on materials are characterized by different physical property change studies such as morphological effects, magnetic response and electrochemical response. All the results are explained in details with special emphasis on graphene-based experiments. Furthermore, the experimental studies have been performed in other carbon supports such as graphite, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphitic carbon nitride and a brief discussion of the conclusive findings are also included in the corresponding sections.

3.1. Introduction

Several phenomena of fundamental and technological importance choose to occur on surface of materials; among which adsorption is one of the most distinguished process. The diffusive behaviour of different atoms across the surface is a fundamental study associated with any material as it is the basis of all characteristic features shown by the materials and has a wide range scope in all applications related to the concerned material

Straight away from the first time experimental isolation of single layer; by virtue of its unique 2D structure, Graphene has conquered the scientific world and industry as a prospective material not only for technological applications, but also a testing tool for the fundamental aspects of solid state physics(Xu and Buehler, 2010b). Albeit its numerous extraordinary structural, physical and electronic qualities; manufacturing of

any graphene-based device must necessarily incorporate metal contacts to benefit these hallmarks. Meanwhile, every area of applications has to be contained with metals directly or indirectly; metal –graphene interaction is a significant matter of research (Singh and Kroll, 2009). Failure and degradation of contacts is a major issue with all semiconductor devices, which could be improved by new barrier materials such as graphene (Morrow et al., 2016). Consequently, graphene diffusion studies will find applications in increasing the reliability of metal contacts. Since the hybrid boundary between graphene and metals will exhibit interesting changes in its physics, the presence of metal atom (in general any foreign impurity) can affect almost all the properties of graphene;(Xu and Buehler, 2010b), and hence one of the major research concerned about the defects in graphene is the graphene- metal interaction study.

It is an inevitable fact that the quality of metal contacts has a key role in the performance of any device as the contact metal will be having at least a weak interaction with the surrounding environment, e.g.; the presence of magnetic metals can perturb the performance of a spintronic device and it follows that the choice of contact metal is crucial to the efficacious fabrication of a device. Moreover, the substrate consisting of the graphene will also affect the extremely sensitive physical properties like spin distribution of graphene and may induce the proximity effects in the system such as proximity induced magnetism (X Liu et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2013). Accordingly, there must be a clear understanding about the metal- graphene interaction so that the most suitable metal for the concerned application can be chosen, which will not interrupt the performance of the proposed devices in any circumstances. Furthermore, metals such as Zn, Ni, Ag and Co have been used to tailor graphene or graphite shapes using either oxidation or hydrogenation. Reports are also available for ‘nano cutting’ of graphene in presence of Nickel (Ci et al., 2008). Consequently, in the present scenario, many studies have focused on different metal adatom adsorptions on graphene and their influence in graphene behaviour; of which most of them are based on some theoretical models such as Monte Carlo, Molecular dynamics (MD) or Density functional theory (DFT)(Giovannetti et al., 2008; Tang et al., 2011; Vanin et al., 2009a; Zan et al., 2011) but seldom experimental studies are only available. However, unintentionally, depending on the assumptions used for calculations or choice of parameters or many undefined and unidentified factors or boundary conditions or software limitations can hinder the experimental implementations of these calculations and sporadically the results may be inconsistent in many situations. In practice, for any material, as bulk

quantities are needed for industrial production, several other unanticipated parameters need to be incorporated practically. Therefore, a better experimental understanding about the concerned problem is a prerequisite.

3.2. Metal- graphene interaction; a review:

Adsorption of metallic or insulating impurities on the freestanding graphene will alter the position of the Fermi energy from the conical points. Thus, depending on the impurity, the nature of conductivity will change as p- type or n- type. Since the transport measurements require yet again metallic contacts, it is essential to examine the physics behind metal- graphene interaction (Giovannetti et al., 2008). In addition, the fundamental interactions between metal and graphene influences the chemistry of graphene as well, e.g.; the catalytic activities (Gong et al., 2014; Vanin et al., 2009a). Thus, in all applications, the contact metal should be selected effectively, which enhances the metal- carbon interfacial strength without introducing any deterioration in the physical or mechanical properties (Matter and Argonne, 2016).

The metal- graphene interface interaction can be either physisorption with a charge transfer or a chemisorption with a hybridisation (Gong et al., 2010b). Generally, it is formulated that transition metals (TM) will do covalent bonds with graphene surface, causing considerable lattice distortion whereas alkali metals will form ionic bonds causing little distortion. It is demonstrated experimentally that metals will tend to cluster on the hydrocarbon-based contamination rather than attaching on the cleaned perfect graphene surface (Vanin et al., 2009a). Thus, we can trap metal atoms to the graphene layers by deliberately introducing defects. Some studies show that gold will cluster around the graphene defects and exhibit coalescence after vacuum annealing and hydrogenation. Catalytic hydrogenation in presence of metal atoms will produce etching of graphene sheets (Zan et al., 2011). It is predicted that the presence of Al, Ni, Co or Fe impurities can favour further defects in graphene by reducing the energy barriers and create large holes on graphene sheets leading the destruction of graphene easily; emphasizing the need of metal- graphene interaction study in device fabrication.

3.2.1. Basics of interaction

Transmission electron microscopic studies have been done to analyse the morphological and structural variation of graphene with the defects associated with

metal permeation (Ramasse et al., 2012). The experimental microscopic studies would predict the positions of the interaction, but much studies should be done to explore the effect on other sensitive physical properties. The possible predicted sites of the foreign atom attachment in graphene would be the following as per calculations – ‘H sites’ (centre of the hexagon) for Fe and alkaline metals such as K, Na, Cs and Ti ; while ‘T sites’ (top of the carbon atom) for Au, Cu, Ni, Sn and F whereas; ‘B sites’ or Bridge sites (on the top of C-C bond) may be occupied by Pt, Cl, Cr, S,O, N and P(Faye, 2012; Xiaojie Liu et al., 2011). Many theoretical models have been proposed to explain the basic interaction of graphene with metals among which the noticeable recent one is modelling of physisorption of graphene on metals by Jianmin Tao, et al.,(Helgee and Isacsson, 2016; Tao et al., 2018). Edit E. Helgee and Andreas Isacsson are proposing in their work on ‘adsorption of metal atoms at a buckled graphene grain boundary’ that ‘bond- order potentials’ are more preferable than ‘Lennard-Jones potentials’ for the explanation of metal- graphene adsorption reaction.

3.2.2. Interaction of graphene with different interfaces, a survey

Theoretical calculations show that in comparison with alkali and Group -III metal adatom adsorption, 3D transition metal interaction with graphene is the strongest (Xiaojie Liu et al., 2011). Substrate- graphene interaction is a very crucial metal-graphene interaction in which choice of substrate is very important, because graphene is extremely sensitive to a single adsorbed species than graphite. Since the lattice parameters (nearest neighbour distance in graphene layer, 1.42 Å is very close to the characteristic distance of Nickel Ni(111) surface, $a_{Ni}/\sqrt{6} = 1.44 \text{ \AA}$, where $a_{Ni} = 3.52 \text{ \AA}$, the measured lattice parameter of Ni fcc lattice.) are matching, Nickel can be considered as an ideal substrate for graphene growth, but the metal/carbon interface interaction will alter the magnetic properties of graphene (Bertoni et al., 2005; Cattelan et al., 2016; Dedkov and Fonin, 2010; Series,)

As per first principle prediction, the interaction between transition metals like Pd, Ni, Co, Fe can alter graphene band structure considerably; but the Al, Ag, Cu, Au and Pt interaction is much weaker and causes little distortion (Matter and Argonne, 2016). But almost all the industry uses different forms of Ni, Cr, Fe or their prominent alloy stainless steel (SS) for device fabrication. Furthermore, many studies are supporting the growth of graphene on/with SS. Thus, here in the present discussion, we are

investigating the effect of the above-mentioned metals/alloys especially in the magnetic behaviour of graphene.

Even though the pristine graphene in its pure form is non-magnetic as lack of localized magnetic moments due to π bonding networks, there are many efforts to use graphene as a prime spintronic material (Gullapalli et al., 2011; John et al., 2011; Xiaojie Liu et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2013). Proximity induced magnetism is already reported in transition metal (TM) substituted graphene; in which the presence of nearby magnetic atoms induces a magnetic state in graphene and changes the local electronic and spin states (Karpan et al., 2007; Lee et al., 2015; Sevinçli et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2012, 2015; Yang et al., 2013). Taking this into account, the unwanted metal diffusion or adsorption through contacts and substrates at the graphene interface which can perturb the magnetic state of the system will certainly be the subject of interest (D. W. Boukhvalov and Katsnelson, 2009a; Chan et al., 2008; Li Chen et al., 2011; Crook et al., 2014; El-Hilo, 2012; Yamada et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013; Zólyomi et al., 2010). The graphene-metal interaction study can also give a new insight to anticorrosion coating studies of graphene grown on Ni or stainless steel surfaces (Coating, 2012; Dumée et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2015; Pu et al., 2015; Qian et al., 2015). The corrugations in r-GO can act as the sites for the metal deposition and can store hydrogen effectively (Tozzini and Pellegrini, 2013b). Graphene is used as a protective barrier against hydrogen embrittlement in metals, which utilizes the strong metal-graphene interaction and the impermeable nature of graphene to gases. Hydrogen will be adsorbed in graphene as SP^3 C-H bonds and can be stored. In addition, in ambient conditions, graphene is chemically stable up to 400°C and can protect the underlying substrate metals from corrosion and oxidization. Thus metal interaction of graphene in presence of hydrogen will be a matter of serious study (He et al., 2014; Hempelmann, 1984; Lee et al., 2015). Hence the present work focuses on the study with the surface treatment under hydrogen pressure.

Metallic impurities can dramatically affect the electrochemical behaviour of graphene. It is already demonstrated that the metallic content in the case of carbon nanotubes are heavily affecting the electrochemical performance even in 'ppm' levels. The metallic impurities can be detected electrochemically and the graphene layers can be purified using electrochemical etching.

Above all, we are concerned about the following bio-related situations which we couldn't find in literature. Since all the bio-related materials contain carbon, the various cooking process of food materials at different temperatures or in different medium or with different utensils or even in vacuum will suffer a metal-carbon interaction. Also, the human body cells contain carbon as its one of the major constituent, prolonged contact to metals such as jewellery, or other house-holds or belongings such as mobile phones; in various situations or environments can induce metal diffusion into the cells which can affect all the properties including the highly sensitive magnetic behaviour, which in turn can affect the brain sensitivity; since human brain can detect a magnetic field of nano tesla (nT). Thus, our present study will be highly impressive in concern with the bio systems.

3.2.3. Effect of curvature of graphene on metal interaction

Local curvature has an influential effect on the chemical reactivity of graphene. Danil W. Boukhvalov and Mikhail I. Katsnelson report through their DFT study that chemical activity of corrugated graphene shows an enhancement if the ratio of height of the corrugation (ripple) to its radius is larger than 0.07 (Boukhvalov and Katsnelson, 2009, 2009a, 2009b, 2011). The convex surfaces of the ripples will attract foreign impurities and promotes chemisorption by reducing the energy barrier. They have calculated the chemisorption energy for hydrogen atoms at the rippled surface as follows.

$$E_{\text{chem}} = E_{(\text{graphene with ripple} + 2\text{H})} - E_{(\text{graphene with ripple})} - E_{\text{H}_2} \dots\dots\dots 3 \quad (1)$$

Nanoscale corrugations in graphene will always improve the general reactivity of graphene (Rossi et al., 2015). The SW defects are responsible for the local curvature in graphene surface and hence accountable for the enhanced chemical reactivity. SW defects are the point defects occur in graphene, mainly responsible for general adsorption including metals and hydrogen (Botari et al., 2016; Cao et al., 2013; Carlsson and Scheffler, 2006; L. Chen et al., 2011; Chen, 2012; Cheng et al., 2012; Cortijo and Vozmediano, 2007; Eletsii et al., n.d.; Guobiene et al., 2014; Han et al., 2001; Hu et al., 2016; Jia et al., 2015; Johll and Low, 2014; Kumar et al., 2013; Lu et al., 2009; Lu and Bhattacharya, n.d.; Ma et al., 2009; Openov and Podlivaev, 2015; Podlivaev and Openov, 2015; Vicarelli et al., 2015; Waghmare, n.d.; Wang and Ding, 2013; C. G. Wang et al., 2013; J. Wang et al., 2013). Reversible hydrogen storage is reported in graphene via controlling the local curvature (Tozzini and Pellegrini, 2013b,

2011). Thus, in the present work efforts are made to create excess amount of SW defects in graphene in order to promote the adsorption of foreign species.

Fig. 3. 1 Change of the energy levels due to the local graphene curvature. Convexities (red) stabilize the chemisorbed H and slightly destabilize the physisorbed H_2 . Concavities (blue) act in the opposite way. Convexity causes the complete elimination of chemisorption barriers and the reduction of the dissociative adsorption barrier, concavity eliminates the associative desorption barrier, and favours the physisorption at very low temperatures. [Fig. is adapted from (Tozzini and Pellegrini, 2013b)].

3.3. Hydrogenation and metal interaction:

Interaction of hydrogen molecule with metals can be of different strategies- can be adsorbed on metal surface and dissolved into atomic hydrogen and can be spread over the bulk of the metal, i.e., the chemisorption of hydrogen into the metals and subsequent diffusion. The metal hydride will be in the solid form of hydrogen. The process of splitting, and subsequent diffusion and migration to the bulk of the metals may lead to the following consequences- (i) appear as a ‘hydrogen-leak through’ in the metal surface because of the successful diffusion of hydrogen through the structure and (ii)

the hydrogen will be strongly interacting with the structure of the material by forming bonds which can cause corrosive decay to the material by making changes to its mechanical properties. This corrosion phenomena are collectively known as hydrogen embrittlement (Darren P. Broom, 2011).

In most of the situations, either for industry or fundamental experiment based; a device may have to interfere the hydrogen atmosphere for various reasons. All the materials, including metals associated with the device can behave differently in hydrogen atmosphere as hydrogen will directly affect them. Likewise, prolonged exposure of the set-up to hydrogen environment may lead to the corrosion of the metal surfaces and hence any metal accessories related to the implementations, in effect can affect the device performance. Keeping all these situations into consideration, we have analysed the metal permeation experiments in presence of hydrogen.

3.4. Motivation to the present work

Though we have seen several theoretical models available, the perturbation caused by these impurities on physical properties of graphene must be investigated thoroughly through experiments, since it will directly reflect on the device performance. In all the observed experiments, the metal presence is introduced into the graphene layers purposefully using evaporation techniques. Thus, here we are imposing a different problem, the container effect; i.e.; if graphene (any material in general) is sitting in a metal container or graphene-based system is placed nearby a metal-based system; it can be an outer casing for the device itself or surrounding metal-based devices or other accessories related to the devices, etc. Is there a possibility of interfering these metals into graphene layers and alter the graphene properties in any circumstances? Any device or experimental set up can suffer various environments like high vacuum, high or low temperatures, exposure to other gases such as hydrogen. Then there is every possibility that these conditions can affect the interface reactions of the material and the associated accessory materials of the particular device under concern. Hence, there should be a vivid idea and prior knowledge about the behaviour of the device material in the inevitable circumstances mentioned above; which will be helpful to accommodate changes in the device fabrication such that it can withstand any the situation. The present study is focusing on this aspect. Here we are not allowing the direct metal diffusion to graphene by evaporating metal targets, but r-GO is taken in

the metal containers and examined the permeation effects in the interface of the container surface.

Similarly, the curvature in the graphitic surface plays an important role in filling metal/carbon interface interaction. Various imperfections in crystal lattice such as Stone-Wales defects (SW), vacancies, substitutional atoms, etc. were experimentally used as the attractors for impurities. The impurities will try to turn cluster around the graphene defects, e.g.; SW defects will decrease the hydrogen chemisorption barrier and hydrogenation of SW defects would create magnetic graphene (D. W. Boukhvalov and Katsnelson, 2009b) . Strong spin flip relaxation and π -orbital polarization have been observed in TM metal -graphene interface.

Experimental creation of SW defects in graphene is attempted in the present work through high vacuum annealing. Several reports are claiming that high temperature annealing will produce more corrugation in the graphene-based materials (Bernal et al., 2017; Bon et al., 2011; Cao et al., 2013; Guobiene et al., 2014; Han et al., 2001; Jia et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2013; Lei et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2012; Luan and Wang, 2014; Tetlow et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2011). Moreover, several theoretical/simulation and a few experimental reports are available for various metal interacting with graphene, of which the notable experimental observations are the diffusion of gold metal to the graphene layers (Malola et al., 2009; Zan et al., 2012, 2011). Here we have mainly considered the most common TM impurities in graphene such as- Fe, which will be the most propagated metallic impurity in all carbon systems, particularly in graphite; and then Ni, the most commonly used graphene substrate (Addou et al., 2012; Boukhvalov, 2011; D. W. Boukhvalov and Katsnelson, 2009a). Generally, Fe atoms will prefer the edges as well as SW defect sites in graphene (Robertson et al., 2013). The well-used alloy form of these transition metals – stainless steel SS, is already used in many works as a promising substrate for graphene synthesis as well as a highly preferred material for many industrial applications, device fabrication, device parts, etc. (Azam et al., 2017; Gullapalli et al., 2011; John et al., 2011; Sawama et al., 2015). Apart from that, these metals and alloys are a favorite subject for the hydrogen interactions; and hence we have performed our experiments with and without hydrogen presence. Therefore, in our study we have used mainly the interface between graphene and stainless-steel to study the metal diffusion effects. When graphene will be subjected to suffer extreme conditions like high temperature, high vacuum, surface treatments like hydrogen pressure is examined experimentally in this particular work. For comparison purpose,

we have investigated the container permeation effects of the metals Fe and Ni separately, under the same experimental conditions. Here we have use the standard alloy SS-316L for our studies.

Graphene oxide (GO), which is normally considered as an insulator; will become zero band gap semi-metal graphene nano sheets after getting reduced thermally or chemically- i.e., reduced graphene oxide (rGO) (Liu et al., 2013). Studies have reported the magnetic properties of graphene based on r-GO based samples (Matte et al., 2009a).

Similarly, if the magnetic behavior of the graphene is perturbed, it can alter the total magnetic behavior of the system. Therefore, we are focusing on the r-GO based studies in the present discussion.

3.5. Experimental procedure

As discussed in chapter-2, we are implementing a novel experimental procedure for observing the indirect contact metal permeation through containers. The major hypothesises of the newly developed experiment are: (i) the metal contact to the concerned material is achieved indirectly through the container in which the material is taken; i.e; the container metal itself is diffusing into the inside material. (ii) the vacuum annealing will promote the metal diffusion form the container metals (iii) the vacuum annealing will create morphological defects such as corrugations, which in turn will attract the impurities (iv) the presence of hydrogen will aid the metal diffusion process in general (v) combined procedure of vacuum annealing and hydrogenation will promote the metal diffusion as a chain reaction.

As mentioned earlier, high temperature vacuum annealing and high-pressure hydrogenation is done with Sieverts' apparatus. The main modification to the experiment is done to the sample cell fabrication. The sample cell is fabricated as a small hollow container of approximate dimensions as 6 cm length, 5 mm diameter and 1 mm thickness; with a grooved lid made out of the metal (here SS-316) which is to be diffused into the concerned sample (here, r-GO). The sample is carefully packed inside the sample holder which can allow the diffusion of hydrogen through it. The sample holder is inserted into the sample cell assembly and is inserted in the furnace of the system. The details of the procedure with photographs are disused in chapter-2.

3.5.1. Vacuum Annealing

The sample cell assembly is evacuated to 10^{-6} mbar using the diffusion pump attached with the set up. The vacuum annealing of the system is done by keeping the furnace at 350°C for 2 hours and cooled down to room temperature under vacuum. Vacuum annealing in the metal container is done to induce the curvature based morphological defects in the sample. As thermal treatment is an unavoidable process in the graphene-based device fabrication and application industry, many studies are available focussing on the effect of thermal treatment on graphene (Bernal et al., 2017; Bon et al., 2011; Cao et al., 2013; Guobiene et al., 2014; Han et al., 2001; Jia et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2013; Lei et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2012; Luan and Wang, 2014; Tetlow et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2011). Yunhao Cao et al., reported the curling of graphene ribbons through thermal annealing. They have reported that the typical process is happening between 300°C to 450°C . Since the prolonged vacuum annealing is done in the metal container, the metal will start diffuse into the container, where the sample is filled.

3.5.2. Hydrogenation

Hydrogenation of the sample is done by allowing 40 bar hydrogen pressure to the vacuum annealed sample cell assembly. The process is repeated for 3-4 cycles to get better results. The container metals are selected such that they can allow the passage of hydrogen either through a ‘leak through’ or causing corrosion to the container material.

Fig. 3. 2 Digital photograph of the sample container (A) the removal of sample after the experiment with vacuum annealing and hydrogenation and (B) the appearance of the sample container before and after the experiment of vacuum annealing and

hydrogenation. The disappearance of the metallic lust of the container is an indication of the reaction.

The proximity contact surface of the material inside the container will receive the hydrogen passing through the container. The diffused hydrogen will promote the diffusion of the container material and will be getting deposited in the defect centers of the interfacing material. The SW defects and curvatures created by the vacuum annealing will be attracting the diffused metals by reducing the energy barrier for the adsorption. Thus, the container metal atoms will be getting deposited and forms clusters around the SW defect centres. It is reported that hydrogen will cause coalescence to the deposited metal particles (Helgee and Isacson, 2016; José-Yacamán et al., 2005; Liang et al., 2017; Zan et al., 2012, 2011). Consequently, since the sample is subjected to long term hydrogenation, the diffused metals will undergo coalescence and re- size and re- position the clusters. The metal clusters will again attract more hydrogen to diffuse in and again which in turn will promote the metal diffusion. Thus, in short, hydrogenation will be inducing a chain process of defect formation and metal diffusion. As shown in Fig. 3.2., the colour of the metal container is changing after the process and is visible to the naked eye; is a clear indication of the reaction of the metal container which in effect will lead to the metal permeation to the inside sample.

3.6. Experiments with r-GO (TEG)

The major discussion concerned with metal diffusion in the present thesis work is done with graphene-based experiments. But the proposed experimental procedure can be applicable generally to any material with the diffusion of any metals or alloys. Since the unique 2D allotrope of carbon, graphene is the fundamental structure among all carbon nano allotropes, the study based on graphene is more fundamental. The single layer graphene contained in the substrate is already in contact with a metal and hence the present experimental conditions with container metal will induce metal to metal diffusion in the system; which can be further more complicated; yet concretely supports the idea of studying metal permeation as a sensitive phenomenon needs attention. Thus, we have chosen the widely used graphene material, reduced graphene oxide (r-GO) for our study.

Even though, practical reach of multi-layered graphene is mainly based on the graphene derived nanostructures such as graphene oxides and reduced graphene oxides, graphene

nano ribbons, graphite nano platelets, graphene nano fibers, multi walled carbon nanotubes, etc. or porous carbons which are generally manufactured as powders; reduced Graphene Oxide (r-GO); which is a collection of few layers Graphene- like sheets, is a matter of research along with the pristine Graphene because of its easy and large-scale production as well as Graphene like behaviour. Graphene can be replaced with r-GO in many cases including energy applications without any loss.

r-GO made through thermal exfoliation (thermally exfoliated graphene; TEG) or hydrogen exfoliation (HEG) is having high qualities competing with pristine Graphene. In addition, it can be made easily in large quantities for industrial applications. Thus, here the metal permeation process is investigated with TEG as the sample material with stainless steel (SS) containers.

3.6.1. Morphological Analysis

As mentioned earlier, the experiment is designed to induce morphological defects such as curvature or SW defects in the sample and hence observe the metal permeation. Thus, it is a well expected and consequential result that changes will be observed in the morphological structure of the sample. Here the morphological studies are done using transmission electron microscopy and the corresponding surface plots are analysed as shown in the concerned figures [Fig.- 3.3 (A) and (B), 3.4 (A) and (B), 3.5 (A) and (B)]. The SW defects are modelled for supporting the morphological changes as shown in Fig. 3.6 (A) and (B).

3.6.1.1. Microscopic studies

The transmission electron microscopic studies shown in the following figures explain the morphological modifications happened to the TEG samples at the different stages of the experiment. Since the samples taken are the thermally reduced graphene oxide, unlike pristine graphene, there will be small corrugations as a part of the structure itself as shown in 3.3(A). But the edges (grain boundaries, according to some models) will be straight compared to the modified samples in the consecutive figures. The curvature or SW defects are minimum in these pure samples before processing; which will be clearer from the surface plots shown in the corresponding images of Fig.3.3 (B).

Fig. 3.4. (A) shows the different views of the vacuum annealed TEG. It is evident from the images that the vacuum annealing has transformed the TEG to a fully crumpled

morphology. Numerous folds having a high degree of curvature has induced on the surface. This is a clear indication of the successful creation of large amount of SW defects; as what the vacuum annealing experiment was meant to be.

Fig. 3.3 (A) TEM images of pure TEG: (a) image showing slightly folded few layered graphene sheets. (b), (c) and (d) HRTEM images showing the edges of the sheets. As a guide to the eye, the straight nature of the edges is marked in red color. Here the corrugations and convex surfaces are minimum.

The 3D surface plots exhibited in Fig. 3.4 (B) understandably show the curvature defects induced in the samples are having convex surfaces within them. This is a pronounced indication of the creation of successful SW defects in the sample with vacuum annealing experiment.

Fig. 3.3. (B) The 3-D surface plots corresponding to the TEM images of Fig. 3.3(A) of pure TEG: (a) image showing slightly wrinkled few layered graphene sheets. (b), (c), and (d) the images are highlighting the individual edges. Here one can see that the grooves are almost straight with few corrugations exist within them. i.e., the SW defects are minimum in these pure samples.

Fig. 3. 4 (A) TEM images of vacuum annealed TEG: (a) and (b) images showing fully crumpled few layered graphene sheets after vacuum annealing process. Here one can observe the highly corrugated graphene layers. (c) and (d) images are focused on a few wrinkles indicating the nature of corrugation. In the image (d), the curved nature of corrugation is marked. Convex shaped projections are clearly visible in the images which are the newly created SW defects assembly due to vacuum annealing.

The corrugations produced during vacuum annealing will help the process of hydrogenation. The hydrogen will be reacting to the container metal interface and leak through the surface to get inside the sample. The prolonged exposure to hydrogen will lead the embrittlement of the container material. Thus, the metal particles will be escaping out from the surface along with the hydrogen gas. Since the container is not sealed as gas proof, the sample inside the container will also be suffering with the same

applied conditions as that of the container, such as hydrogen pressure or vacuum. Therefore, after a required time interval, a dynamic equilibrium will be created and the diffused metal will be carried away by the hydrogen gas (as the metal is having high affinity towards hydrogen) to the sample surface and will be deposited uniformly along the defect sites.

Fig. 3.4. (B) – The 3-D surface plots corresponding to the TEM images of Fig. 3.4(A) of vacuum annealed TEG: The images (a) and (b) showing highly corrugated few layered graphene sheets after the process of vacuum annealing. (c), and (d) the images are focusing on the nature of the corrugations. The corrugations are having concave convex surfaces within them, which can act as the reaction centers to foreign atoms in graphene sheets. The array of SW defects is visible, which makes the corrugations in the sheets.

Fig. 3. 5 (A) TEM images of TEG after processing under hydrogen pressure: (a), (b) and (c) images are the different views of the highly wrinkled surface of the few layered

graphene sheets. (d), (e) and (f) are the HRTEM images focused on the nature of wrinkles. In the image (d), the wave like nature of corrugation (concave and convex ripples) can be directly observed. The close observation on (e) and (f) shows the deposition of metals on the top hilly surface of the wrinkles, which is marked in red.

The hydrogen treatment will aid the deposition of the container material, which in turn will increase the quantity of the adsorbed adatom defects in the sample. These foreign impurity deposition defects will again attract more hydrogen towards them, leading further metal diffusion from the containers and hence the concentration of the defects will automatically increase. Thus, the repeated cycle of hydrogen treatment can, in effect, produce more and more defects in the system.

It is already evident that metal diffusion has occurred through vacuum annealing in presence of the metal container and has deposited in the corrugations inside the sample.

Energetically favourable conditions for the diffused metal atoms are to form clusters and reports are there for the observation of coalescence in metal clusters. Thus the metal clusters will change its size, shape and orientation; and form new arrangements in presence of hydrogen (Zan et al., 2011) (Zan et al., 2012)(José-Yacamán et al., 2005). Fig. 3.5 (A) represents the images of the samples after hydrogen treatment. From a close observation of the images, it is visible that the metal clusters are distributed in the upward projected areas of the corrugations. The surface plots of Fig. 3.5 (B) depict the nature of corrugations and metal deposition on the top of the convex surfaces. In presence of hydrogen, the metal clusters show coalescence, which lead the uniform distribution of the clusters. This uniform array of the deposited metal clusters will contribute to the observed changes in magnetic property of the material.

3.6.1.2. Stone Wales (SW) defects

The observed morphological defects in the form of corrugations which are collectively responsible for the observation of a high degree of metal diffusion can be attributed to the point defects in graphene, namely Stone- Thrower- Wales defects (STW defects) or simply SW defects.

Fig. 3.5. (B) – The 3-D surface plots corresponding to the TEM images of Fig. 3.5(A) of TEG processed under hydrogen pressure: The images (a), (b) and (c) are showing the surface of highly corrugated few layered graphene sheets with lots of wrinkles on them and the wrinkles constitute projected convex surfaces on them. (d) focuses on the exact wave -like rippled nature of the wrinkle. (e) and (f) shows the ripples on the

surfaces where the metal clusters are being deposited. Red colours may be the projection from the metal cluster deposition.

The formation of SW defects can be modelled as follows by considering a perfect graphene sheet as shown in Fig. 3.6 (A) and (B). Fig. 3.6 (A)- a) shows the unit cell considered for the construction of the graphene sheet shown Fig. 3.6 (A)- b). Fig. 3.6 (A)- c) shows the creation of a perfect SW defect by rotation of the selected C-C bond at 90° . The subsequent figures in Fig. 3.6 (A)- d) and Fig. 3.6 (A)- e) shows the creation of assembly of SW defects, which in practice will appear as wrinkles in the graphene sheet.

Fig. 3. 6 (A) Modelling of Stone Wales defects in graphene sheets: (a) the unit cell considered (b) the perfect graphene sheet without any defect. The marked (in green) is the C-C bond under consideration to make the rotation. (c) The first SW defect created by rotating the C-C bond in 90° (marked in green) (d) The modified SW defects created

by further rotation (marked in green) (d) The series of SW defects are created by consecutive rotation of nearby C-C bonds (marked in green) which in effects forms the line defects and can be appeared in the morphology of the graphene sheet as folding or corrugations and (e) The behavior of the assembly of SW defects to the foreign impurity- when a foreign impurity (Fe here, shown in orange colour) approaches the system, it will be finding the preferable position to the center of the defect than a perfect surface, as shown (marked in red)

Fig. 3.6. (B) The behavior of Stone Wales defects in graphene sheets with the passivation of hydrogen: (a) the perfect graphene sheet without any defect- the hydrogen will prefer the edges (b) in presence of a single SW defect- the hydrogen will find the SW defect as the attractive site (c) The array of SW defects will be occupied by the hydrogen (d) When the SW defect is already occupied by a foreign impurity, the hydrogen will bind with the new impurity site also.

The thermal energy given by the vacuum annealing process will lead to the bond rotations and hence the creation of these defects. Here in the present experimental condition, as the powdered sample is filled as bulk quantity inside container, the control and quantification of the defects formation is difficult. But the prolonged uniform treatment will give the natural average distribution of the defects uniformly along the surface of the sample. These SW defect centers are the center of attraction for any approaching foreign impurity to the system. As shown in Fig. 3.6 (A)- f), the diffusing metal atom will show the tendency to position in the defect center.

Similarly, the model exhibited in Fig. 3.6 (B) explains the behavior of the SW defects in samples during the passivation of hydrogen. As shown in Fig. 3.6 (B)- a), when a perfect graphene sheet having no defect will subject to a hydrogen atmosphere, the edges will attract the incoming matter whereas the cleaned surface having no defects will have no affinity towards hydrogen. Meanwhile, when a SW defect is existing in the surface, the hydrogen will find these sites as more attractive and secure a place on them as well as in the edges as shown in consecutive figures of Fig. 3.6 (B)- b), Fig. 3.6 (B)- c). Correspondingly, the diffused metals will also cluster around the SW defects and in effect will attract more hydrogen around them as shown in Fig. 3.6 (B)- d).

In brief, the morphological changes in the form of SW defects have evolved as corrugations in the graphene sheet and attract the incoming foreign impurities in the system. The entire processes can be visualized using the simple schematics as shown in Fig. 3.7.

Fig. 3. 7 Schematics showing the morphological changes in r-GO samples. (a) as synthesized TEG having a few folds on the sheets. (b) The more corrugated sheet after vacuum annealing (c) The diffused metal clusters are distributed over the curved defects in the sheets. (d) After hydrogenation, hydrogen will find it easier to adsorb in the metal clusters as well as curved carbon defects causing more and more metal to be diffused in.

3.6.2. XRD analysis:

Fig. 3. 8 The XRD pattern of pure TEG and TEG processed after vacuum annealing and hydrogenation.

The normalized X-ray diffraction patterns shown in Fig. 3.8 are a strong proof to the observed morphological changes in the sample. The as synthesized TEG sample is exhibiting a broad peak C (002) near $2\theta = \sim 25^\circ$, which is an indication of the exfoliated graphene sheets. The broadness of the peak is an indication of the absence of long range order in the system. After processing under high vacuum, the nature of the peak has changed abruptly. The peak is shifted towards 25.5° i.e., towards graphitic nature reminding the ordered nature of the sample. The corrugations and defects will collectively reflect to form the comparatively more intense (not as high as graphite, but a little more than the pure TEG) peak having a narrow width. Here it is important to note a point that the changed nature of the peak can mislead to the impression that the graphene structure is restacking back to the graphite. But in fact, this peak is the indication of the worst form of corrugations suffered by the graphene sheet, which cannot be restacked to a perfect graphitic form in the present situation. Since the quantity of diffused metals will be in the ppm level, which cannot be detected individually in the XRD analysis and hence there is no observed impurity peak in the spectra.

The whole process including the synthesis procedures involved can be summarized with the following schematics, in brief, as shown in Fig. 3.9.

Fig. 3. 9 The schematics representing the series of different processes that the r-Go samples are undergoing (a) the synthesis of graphic oxide (GO) using Hummer's method (b) the reduction of GO to r-GO using thermal reduction- TEG (graphene like sheets) (c) The highly corrugated sheet after vacuum annealing (c) After hydrogenation, metal clusters are diffused over the curved surfaces in the sheets.

3.6.3. Magnetic response

As mentioned before, the proximity of any magnetic metal can perturb the spintronic response of the device. To analyse this situation, we have chosen the magnetically active contact metals for the present experiment. The magnetic response analysis shows that the metal permeation has introduced ferromagnetic properties to the samples.

Fig. 3.10 and Fig. 3.11 show the magnetic signal response of different samples discussed in the experiment. The analysis is compared with graphite samples, details of the experiments will be discussed in later sessions. Fig. 3.10 shows the variation of magnetisation of the material with applied magnetic field and Fig. 3.11 shows the temperature variation of magnetisation for different samples under discussion.

The as synthesised TEG is not magnetic similar to graphite as shown in Fig. 3.10 (a). The small deviation from the ideal graphite magnetism can be attributed to the intrinsic nature of graphene. During the chemical synthesis process from graphite, many moieties can be intrinsically present to the graphene sheets such as -OH groups, -N or

surface oxygen, hydrogen etc. Theoretical calculations have predicted the presence of ferromagnetic states at the edges of graphene sheets, while anti-ferro magnetic states in the sheets. The unusual magnetic properties exhibited (see Fig. 3.10 (a) and Fig. 3.11 (A)) by the reduced graphene oxide samples are due to these intrinsic species. All the samples show divergence in field cooled (FC) and zero field cooled (ZFC) data, comparable to magnetically frustrated systems such as spin glasses and superparamagnetic materials. The magnetic anomalies exhibited by the TEG samples may happen when antiferromagnetic correlations compete with ferromagnetic order.

Fig. 3. 10 Magnetic response of different samples showing the effect of metal permeation a) TEG pure, b) TEG after vacuum annealing, c) TEG after processing under hydrogen pressure in the metal container and d) graphite sample processed under the same conditions of sample c; recorded using SQUID -VSM, Magnetization M as a function of the applied field B at different temperatures – 5K, 50K and 300K.

Fig. 3. 11 Magnetic response of different samples- A) TEG pure, B) TEG after vacuum annealing, C) TEG after processing under hydrogen pressure in the metal container and D) graphite sample processed under the same conditions of sample C. Temperature versus magnetization of the sample recorded between the temperature ranges of 5K - 350K with an applied field of 500 Oe in field cooled (FC) and zero field cooled (ZFC) methods. Inset is the zoomed portion of the curves B and C, showing the temperature at which, the maximum magnetization occurs (T_{max}).

The application of high field can align the ferromagnetic clusters in order and hence decrease the divergence between FC and ZFC data. This magnetic response indicates a percolation type of situation, where different types of magnetism can co-exist. Comparing the Fig. 3.10 (a) and Fig. 3.11 (A), the anomalous behaviour at low temperature; around 5K; a spontaneous magnetisation is occurring. The ferromagnetic clusters in this case is not associated with the global ferromagnetic transition temperature, but a phenomenon similar to the one reported in microporous carbon

(Kopelevich et al., 2003). It is already observed that clusters of both ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic centres will be existing in curved graphene sheets, which is perfectly consistent with our present experimental results. Thus, the total magnetic behaviour of the present sample is the cumulative contribution from various faculties.

The Fig. 3.10 (b and c), and Fig. 3.11 (B and C) are the magnetic response from the samples subjected to metal permeation. Here the magnetic behavior will be from the contribution of the combination of various diffused metals and that of intrinsic reduced graphene oxide. Since we have used stainless steel as the diffusing metal, the main contribution is from Fe, which surpasses all other contributions and is being observed as the average behavior. The highly corrugated graphene will normally exhibit a feeble ferromagnetic behaviour. Moreover, the hydrogenated graphene will be magnetic as the bond structure will change from sp^2 to sp^3 , as per reports. The CHNS analysis of the present samples indicates ~10 to 15 wt% hydrogen within it. Hence, we can conclude that the total magnetic behaviour exhibited by the present samples are the collective contribution of all sorts of available magnetism constituted by various factors. But comparing the Fig.s, 3.11 (B) and 3.11 (C); the shift in the position of the temperature corresponds to the peak magnetisation (T_{max}) may be an indication of the changes in the particle size, shape and re- distribution of the metal clusters due to the coalescence induced by the presence of hydrogen (Dho et al., 2002; Matte et al., 2009b).

For a comparative study, here the magnetisation plots of graphite subjected to the similar experimental condition are included. Surprisingly, the graphite shows no such magnetic behaviour observed in graphene sheets, which is a very important result that proves the many theoretical claims that graphite is less vulnerable to the defects formation and impurities. The details of the graphite study is discussed in the later section.

3.6.4. Electrochemical response

As mentioned earlier, the metal diffusion will be affecting the fundamental structure of the material and hence can observe changes in all atomic and subatomic levels. Here, the effects on charge transport of the material is analysed via electrochemical response measurements. Since graphene derived materials are the mandatory part of the electrochemistry-based industry such as electrochemical energy storage, the present study is having a relevant scope. Hence, attempts are made to detect the defects and

metal permeation in graphene via electrochemical response and hence can determine the purity of the material based on it. Also, the electrochemical etching or cleaning can remove the contaminations of the material.

3.6.4.1. Cyclic voltammetry

Cyclic voltammetry can provide the qualitative information about the electrochemical interactions observing at the surface. It is well proven that the interaction of transition metals with graphene may alter their electronic properties. Ambrosi et al., have demonstrated experimentally that the intrinsic metallic impurities present in the graphite acquired during the manufacturing can influence the electrochemistry of the graphene synthesised from it. (Ambrosi et al., 2012). Also, it is very clear that the different intrinsic structural moieties acquired during the chemical synthesis of reduced graphene oxide can affect the charge transport phenomenon through it. Thus, all these effects will be protruding in the electrochemical characteristics of the material.

In the following sections of cyclic voltammetry, we will be demonstrating the effect of impurities and defects induced in the reduced graphene oxide samples using hydrazine as a molecular probe.

Fig. 3. 12 Cyclic voltammogram of different samples (as synthesized TEG, vacuum annealed TEG and hydrogenated TEG within the metal container) showing the effect of metal permeation. The experiment is done using modified GC electrode with the concerned material, 50 mM phosphate buffer solution (PBS) of pH = 7.2 as the electrolyte and reference electrode as Ag/AgCl with a counter electrode of Pt wire.

Fig. 3. 13 Cyclic voltammogram of different samples (as synthesized TEG, vacuum annealed TEG and hydrogenated TEG within the metal container) recorded using 5mM hydrazine as a molecular probe, showing the effect of metal permeation. The experiment is done using modified GC electrode with the concerned material and 50 mM phosphate buffer solution (PBS) of pH = 7.2 as the electrolyte; reference electrode as Ag/AgCl with a counter electrode of Pt wire.

Fig. 3.12 represents the cyclic voltammograms of the TEG samples recorded in the alkaline media with phosphate buffer (pH = 7.2) as the electrolyte. The initial peaks between -1.5 to -0.5 V (vs Ag/AgCl) are due to the surface moisture and other surface contaminations in the sample, as the samples were kept in ambient atmosphere and are found to be disappearing in the consecutive cycles. Since the diffused impurities are present only in 'ppm' levels, the specific oxidation/reduction peaks due to the catalytic activities of the adsorbed adatoms are not detectable here. However, reduction in the total area of the curves compared with pure sample is an indication of the large quantity of surface defects in the samples such as SW defects or foreign adatom adsorption. The area of the curve is again found to be decreased in the hydrogen treated samples than in the vacuum annealed samples. The reduction in these catalytic activities may be attributed to the reduction in the specific surface area of the samples due to the newly experienced highly corrugated nature. Likewise, the pores of the samples may be sealed due to the extreme conditions in the experimental procedure, which they have undergone.

Fig. 3. 14 The hydrazine detection peaks, which is the collective indication of the defect in the sample is projected in the figure. As mentioned in the previous figure (Fig. 3.12), Cyclic voltammograms are recorded using 5mM hydrazine as a molecular probe. The experiment is done using modified GC electrode with the concerned material and 50 mM phosphate buffer solution (PBS) of pH = 7.2 as the electrolyte, reference electrode as Ag/AgCl with a counter electrode of Pt wire. The marked lines (marked in violet) indicate the shift in peak of the two curves.

Since hydrazine is known to be sensitive to metallic impurities which results in the lowering of its oxidation potential, we have analysed the effect of metallic impurities towards the oxidation of hydrazine. Fig. 3.13 shows the representative voltammograms of the same samples discussed above using hydrazine as a molecular probe. Since our container material is stainless steel, the diffused metal clusters will be having the combination of different metals of which Fe will be maximum however, Ni particles can also be present. In Fig. 3.14, the detailed view of the hydrazine detection peaks is exhibited. The defected samples, i.e., the vacuum annealed and hydrogen treated samples are showing the metallic peak in presence of hydrazine as expected and consistent with the observed magnetic response. A peak shift is observed in the two samples of vacuum annealed and hydrogenated. This may be due to the re-distribution, re-sizing and coalescence of the diffused metal clusters in presence of hydrogen. The hydrogen can change the grain size of the diffused metals and redistribute them to form different metal compositions, which can again lead to a new solid solution etc.

Therefore, the electrochemical studies confirm the induced morphological defects and metal permeation process in the reduced graphene oxide materials.

3.6.5. Conclusion

From the experimental analysis of contact metal permeation in reduced graphene oxide, one can conclude that through high temperature vacuum annealing, we could effectively manage to create high quantities of SW defects in the samples, which in turn has appeared as corrugations in the morphology. The wide spreading effect of metal permeation has been observed through magnetic response studies and electrochemical performance studies. The following sections will be describing the studies that have been done with other materials such as graphite and graphitic carbon nitride in brief.

3.7. Experiments with graphite

As discussed in the previous chapters, graphite is a polymorph of carbon formed by stacking of 2D graphene sheets of carbon hexagons. In fact, graphite has been known to the scientific world far before the recently disclosed nano allotropes of carbon such as graphene and CNTs. Thus, graphite will be used as the base material in the production of the new barrier materials such as graphene, industrially. Hence in the present work also, conventional procedure utilizes the commercially available graphite for the synthesis of reduced graphene oxide sheets. During the synthesis process, a large amount of energy from harsh chemical reactions are needed (during the synthesis of GO and the subsequent thermal reduction) to exfoliate graphene sheets from the well-ordered graphite structure.

There are several reports available claiming that graphite is less vulnerable to impurities and defects compared to graphene. Here through our experimental observations, this fact is once again confirmed.

We have adopted the same experimental procedure, discussed previously in the case of reduced graphene oxide, to test the metal permeation process in graphite. Here, with the same experimental conditions, graphite is less sensitive to the surface induced defects. Or in other words, creating morphological modifications such as SW defects in graphite needs very high energy. As the most sensitive quality, we have analyzed the magnetic response of the graphite in detail.

3.7.1. Magnetic response

The representative magnetic responses of the graphite samples are plotted in Fig. 3.15 (a and b), Fig. 3.10 (d) and Fig. 3.11. (D). It is clear that the magnetic behaviour of the samples has not changed after the experimental procedure. However, the effort to create the defect in graphite through high temperature vacuum annealing at 1000⁰C has created a small variation in the response as shown in Fig. 3.15 (b). The well oriented crystal structure is responsible for the observed behaviour in graphite.

Thus, considering the defect vulnerability, graphite is a better material than graphene. Or, in a better way of stating the observations positively as graphene is a far better sensitive material to defects or any other forms of energy/forces compared to graphite; which makes the former as a unique material for all the applications including sensing or other competitive physical and chemical reactions.

Fig. 3. 15 Magnetic response of the graphite samples showing the effect of metal permeation a) Graphite as purchased, b) Graphite after vacuum annealing at 1000⁰C. Also, see Fig. 3.10 (d) and Fig. 3.11. (D).

3.8. Experiments with graphitic carbon nitride

Referring to the previous discussion; similar to graphite, graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) is a layered material made of stacked planes of covalent C-N bonds hold together by Van der Waal's force. Apart from graphitic nature, g-C₃N₄ is enriched with

numerous pores and innate nitrogen content within it. Because of these nitrogen content, it can act as an attractive material for the reactions which need chemical attractive centers. Thus, in short, compared to graphite, g-C₃N₄ provides a better environment for the approaching impurities. Here we have tested the metal permeation ability of g-C₃N₄ using the similar experimental conditions as the previous examples. Here, the vacuum annealing and hydrogenation is done at 250⁰C as the g-C₃N₄ will start evaporation in lower temperatures compared to graphene. Here we have used the bulk g-C₃N₄ synthesized via low temperature thermal condensation of melamine.

In correlation with the previous studies, we have tested the effect of the metal permeation experiments using magnetisation responses.

3.8.1. Magnetic response

Fig. 3.16 and 3.17 show the representative magnetic response of the g-C₃N₄ samples treated under different experimental conditions. Here we are discussing one more possibility of the present experiment by changing the material of the metal container- using Ni based container along with the SS container for comparison. Furthermore, different amount of hydrogen pressure is also considered as g-C₃N₄ is explored as an excellent hydrogen storage material by virtue of physisorption itself; suggested by our own previous studies discussed in chapter-5.

Fig. 3. 16 Magnetic response of g-C₃N₄ samples showing the effect of metal permeation A) g-C₃N₄ pure, B) g-C₃N₄ processed under hydrogen pressure (40 bar) in the Ni container

Fig. 3. 17 Magnetic response of g-C₃N₄ samples showing the effect of metal permeation A) g-C₃N₄ processed under hydrogen pressure (1 bar) in the SS container B) g-C₃N₄ processed under hydrogen pressure (10 bar) in the SS container

From the analysis of Fig. 3.16, it is clear that pristine g-C₃N₄ has an anomalous magnetic response as expected from the conclusion derived from the previous studies (Kopelevich et al., 2003) on porous carbon materials (Dho et al., 2002; Matte et al., 2009b). Hydrogen treatment in presence of nickel container has imposed the magnetic properties of nickel into the samples, which is an indication of the metal permeation effect.

Fig. 3.17 shows the response of metal permeation from stainless steel containers on magnetic properties with different amount of hydrogen pressure. It is evident from the figure that as the applied hydrogen pressure has increased from 1bar to 10 bar, the amount of diffused metals has increased considerably, which in practice reflected in the magnetic property. As mentioned elaborately in chapter-5, g-C₃N₄ has a very high affinity towards hydrogen by virtue of its special intrinsic porous structure with a high amount of nitrogen. Therefore, as the applied hydrogen pressure increases, the material will show more affinity towards hydrogen; which in effect will lead to more metal permeation, as the container metals will be reacting towards hydrogen and hence will be diffusing through the container to the inside material. Also, it is reported that g-C₃N₄ is a good catalyst support material for the metal catalyst, at the same time. Thus, the diffused metals will find an easy way to get deposited on the g-C₃N₄ matrix. This metal deposited g-C₃N₄ will again attract more hydrogen and hence the process of metal decay and permeation will be continuing. In short, the innate nitrogen content and the peculiar

porous structure will make g-C₃N₄ a special material, which in practice will accelerate the metal permeation process as well.

3.9. Summary and conclusion

Fig. 3. 18 The schematic showing the summary of the metal permeation process and the effect observed on graphene-based materials.

A novel experimental procedure for the observation of indirect contact metal permeation in materials is developed. The idea of creating the defects through vacuum annealing and high temperature hydrogenation is successfully implemented. The creation of SW defects in the graphene system is successfully implemented through vacuum annealing procedure of the experiment. The role of hydrogen in the metal permeation process is analysed. The consequential effects of metal permeation are demonstrated through the studies of magnetic and electrochemical response of the material. The schematic shown in Fig. 3.18 explains the entire process in a single frame. The experimental procedure has successfully implemented for reduced graphene oxide, graphite and graphitic carbon nitride.

CHAPTER 4

EFFECTS OF CONTACT METAL PERMEATION IN OTHER ACCESSORY METALS INCORPORATED IN THE CARBON SYSTEMS

As the continuation of the previous discussion in chapter 3, the present chapter is dedicated to the investigative studies related to the effect of contact metal permeation in other accessory metals associated within the carbon system, using the novel experimental technique based on vacuum annealing and high temperature hydrogen treatment within the proximity of container metal interfaces. Thus, with the newly developed experimental procedure discussed in the last sessions, we could successfully analyse the above-mentioned effect in several metals with different container metal interfaces. For sake of convenience and smooth-running connected discussions, we are considering the representative results and conclusions drawn from the experiments with the palladium-based system as it is again used for the hydrogen storage studies in the present thesis.

Specifically, we are dealing with the effect of container metal permeation in formation, decoration and morphology of Pd nanoparticles incorporated in reduced graphene oxide. Similarly, a few studies on Pd nanoparticles with graphite is also mentioned briefly. Again, as an indication of the effect of diffused metals, the magnetic response of the systems is analysed. Moreover, these metal systems are studied independently, i.e., the palladium systems without carbon support; which in succession lead to the formation of interesting, novel dendrite structures of Pd black having peculiar properties. Some of interesting morphological characteristics and a few magnetic responses of the newly formed structures are discussed briefly.

4.1 Introduction

In general, solid state diffusion barriers require several qualities such as thermodynamic stabilities, strong adhesions, low contact resistance, free from mechanical and thermal stresses, etc. Graphene has been predicted as an interesting material for diffusion barrier applications; by virtue of its unique peculiar properties. The interfacing contact properties with the diffusing species or with the contact surface will determine the

quality of graphene in any diffusion barrier application. Generally, for 3D metals, substitutional diffusion which is dominated by the concentration of vacancies or interstitial diffusion which is dependent on the kinetic energy of the diffusing species can happen. The strong C-C bonding in graphene will be acting as a high barrier to the diffusion process and the hexagonal atomic layer in graphene will prevent the diffusion of substitutional atomic migration of large diameter bimetallic alloys. The basal plane in the case of graphite will provide a strong barrier to all species except boron (Morrow et al., 2016).

Thus, for surpassing the activation barrier provided by graphene, the approaching species should possess sufficient thermal energy. By applying Boltzmann's energy distribution probability, the standard thermal diffusion relationship is as follows.

$$D = D_0 \exp\left(\frac{-E_b}{k_b T}\right) \dots\dots\dots 4.1;$$

where E_b is the activation energy, D is the diffusivity, D_0 is the material dependant pre-factor, k_b – the Boltzmann's constant and T - the temperature of the system. In typical 3D diffusion barriers, annealing at high temperature or increasing the exposure time of the reaction can improve the solute diffusivity within the barrier. Considering these factors, we have developed a new experimental procedure to observe the contact metal permeation in different materials from container metal interface. As seen from chapter-3, the experimental procedure has introduced the surface modified defects such as SW defects through prolonged vacuum annealing and has promoted the metal diffusion in presence of hydrogenation. The experimental procedures were verified using several carbon-based materials such as reduced graphene oxides, graphite, graphitic carbon nitrides, etc. with different metals/metal alloys as container metal interfaces such as Fe, Ni, Cu, Al, Pd, Ag, Au, SS alloys, etc. The present chapter is dedicated to observe the contact metal permeation in other accessory metals (here in the form of metal nano particles inside the system) associated with the system. Here the studies will be performed using Pd based experiments predominantly.

4.2. Palladium based systems; a brief outlook

Owing to both its catalytic activities and high affinity towards hydrogen, Pd is considered to be a unique material for the hydrogen-based reactions. Apart from the hydrogen-based technologies, several investigative studies have been carried out in the

Pd based systems from the field of fundamental science and technology. In contrast to their bulk counterparts, nano structured Pd have been used in many application-based studies; where the catalytic activities have been made use of. Many hydrogen storage-based studies have been exploring Pd as the best catalyst material for hydrogen storage industry (see chapter-5). Carbon materials are known to be the finest catalyst support material for many metal particles including Pd based systems. Thus, the present experimental studies for contact metal permeation effect are dedicated to the Pd system as an accessory material part of the carbon systems. (Adams and Chen, 2011; Bhosale et al., 2016; Vara et al., 2017).

Fig. 4. 1 Schematic energy diagram for hydrogen absorption and desorption into Pd lattice that shows the reason for the difference between $H\beta/\alpha$ and $H\alpha/\beta$. It is hypothesized that in the presence of carbon support, the chemisorbed hydrogen spills over from Pd surface to H-trapping sites on carbon. With increasing Pd–carbon contact and number of H-trapping sites, the effectiveness of hydrogen transfer (‘pumping power of support’) increases and thereby destabilizes β -PdH_x. In the figure, energy of hydrogen dissociation (E_{DIS}), physisorption (E_{PH}), chemisorption (E_{CH}), subsurface states (E_{SS}) and diffusion (E_{DIF}) are shown along with $H\alpha/\beta$ and $H\beta/\alpha$. The figure is adapted after (Bhat et al., 2009; Konda and Chen, 2015).

As mentioned, the reaction affinity of Pd towards hydrogen is unique. The adsorption of hydrogen in Pd results the formation of two phases according to concentrations (solid solutions) - α and β , with low and high concentrations respectively. Carbon is known to be the best support material for palladium as its surface thermodynamics allows the palladium nano particles to be embedded in the system. Therefore, for hydrogen reactions, the carbon supported Pd embedded systems will show an efficient hydrogen affinity by 'pumping' more and more hydrogen into the β - PdH_x phase. The details of reaction are described in Fig. 4.1.

Accordingly, in the present experimental study, we have adopted the Pd based systems individually as well as embedded in carbon support with the help of hydrogen aided reactions.

4.3 Experimental procedure

The proposed experimental procedure discussed in chapter-2 and chapter-3 are used here for investigating the effect of metal permeation in the nanoparticles incorporated within the carbon-based matrix. As discussed earlier, in order to observe the contact metal permeation effects from different metals, the containers made out of the corresponding metals/alloys are used. Since we are examining the diffusion effects in palladium-based systems, we have tested our samples with the sample containers made out of pure palladium metal. Thus, the foreign impurity permeation in the process is avoided and the results are compared with the other samples.

The nano particles are created from the corresponding precursors added with the carbon support. Here we have tested the palladium nano particles with different loading (such as 0.25 wt%, 0.5 wt%, 1 wt%, 5 wt%, 10 wt%, 20 wt%, 30 wt%, 50 wt%) in different carbon supports- TEG, graphite, g-C₃N₄, etc.; a few of the important representative results are discussed in consecutive sessions. In the typical procedure, the required amount of precursor needed for the nanoparticle loading is calculated and mixed with the carbon support by mechanical stirring. This sample is filled inside the container and repeated the same procedure as discussed in chapter-3. During the first cycle of vacuum annealing process, the metal atoms will be released from the precursor and will be attached to the carbon matrix. The coming cycles of vacuum annealing and hydrogenation will modify these metal nano particles. For comparison, we have tested the experiment with separately- prepared samples, having the same loading of

nanoparticle dispersion. i.e., the nanoparticle decorated samples prepared using catalytic chemical vapor deposition techniques in tubular furnace are filled inside the metal containers and studied the metal permeation. Most of the effects are observed to be consistent.

4.4 Experiments with Pd nanoparticles on TEG

The effect of contact metal permeation on decoration of Pd nanoparticles on TEG is observed with different metal/alloy containers. Here the Pd nano particles are created using PdCl₂ as the precursor. As synthesised TEG (procedure is given in chapter-2) is well mixed with the required amount of precursor using mechanical stirring for 12 hours and dried in the vacuum oven. This dried sample is carefully taken and filled in the sample container (here SS container is under discussion). Then the sample container is inserted in the sample cell assembly of the experimental set-up (as mentioned before in the previous experimental sessions of TEG in chapter-2) and performed the cycles of vacuum annealing followed by hydrogenation. After completing the proposed number of cycles, the sample is removed and taken for analysis. The observation of morphological changes and magnetic responses of the samples having 1 wt% Pd loading, Pd(1%)-TEG and 20 wt% Pd loading, Pd(20%)-TEG are discussed in the following parts.

4.4.1. Morphological analysis

The effects of metal permeation can be well understood from the morphological analysis of the system; as the process is facilitated by morphological defects such as SW defects. The surface features of the samples were analysed using the microscopic techniques such as TEM, SEM, EDX with elemental mapping, etc. As discussed in the previous chapter, the proposed experiment was aimed to introduce SW defects in the system and then observe the metal permeation through these defects. Here the Fig. 4.2 and Fig. 4.3 show observed TEM images of Pd (20%)-TEG and Pd (10%)-TEG respectively.

From these figures one can observe the highly corrugated TEG with numerous folds in it, which are the attractive locations for the metal nanoparticles. The Pd nano particles of special structure are arranged in a linear fashion throughout the wrinkles. This observation supports the theoretical assumptions discussed before, as SW defects

provide reduced energy barriers for any incoming impurities or foreign species. Thus, the Pd atoms will find it easier to bind on the array of SW defects and form nanoparticles. Consequently, the nanoparticles are distributed on the SW defects as well as the edges of the layers. In Fig. 4.2 (c) and (d), the wrinkles are marked in red for a better understanding of the nature of particle distribution. Therefore, instead of getting a uniform random distribution of nanoparticles throughout the layers, a confinement is observed in the SW defects. This seems to be an important evidence for the behaviour of graphene curvature or surface defects towards the foreign species. Curvature improves the chemical reactivity of graphene by reducing the formation energy of the particles.

Fig. 4. 2 TEM images of Pd (20%)-TEG after processing with vacuum annealing and hydrogenation (40 bar) in SS container: (a) and (b) images showing highly corrugated graphene sheets; decorated with special structures of Pd island arrays on the

corrugations as well as edges. (c) and (d) are showing the same images where some of the corrugations and edges are marked in red, as a guide to the eye. In all the images, nanoparticle islands of different geometrical shapes are arranged in one by one order along the convex surfaces of the SW defect arrays.

Fig. 4. 3 TEM images of Pd (1%)-TEG after processing with vacuum annealing and hydrogenation (40 bar) in SS container: (a) and (b) images showing the highly corrugated graphene sheets; decorated with special structures of Pd island arrays on the corrugations as well as edges. (c) and (d) are focusing on the nature of individual particles. The nanoparticles are islands of different geometrical shapes, arranged in order along the convex surfaces of the SW defect arrays or the edges of the sheets.

Again, by a close observation of the images, the Pd nanoparticles obtained here are of a special core-shell structure. From the HRTEM images shown in Fig. 4.4, the structures of the individual particles are evident. All the particles are observed to be possessing a symmetrical structure having an outer coating shell and an inner core. The outer thin shell is a covering made of metal coating, which can be formed by the diffused metals from the containers. The inside Pd shell portion is of concentric rings

with the particular geometrical shape. The combined effect of vacuum annealing and hydrogenation helps the nucleation of Pd particles in the form of particular converging rings, which will remind the Newton's rings in shape. In Fig. 4.3, the number of particles is less as it contains 1 wt% of Pd loading. Fig. 4.5 exhibits the SEM images focussed on the edges of the graphene layers. The edges are observed to be curled; which supports many other studies of curling and buckling of graphene with thermal or hydrogen treatment. Consequently, the edges are more defective and could accommodate more particles as well as diffused moieties.

Fig. 4. 4 HRTEM images of the Pd nanoparticles decorated in Pd (20%)-TEG after processing with vacuum annealing and hydrogenation (40 bar) in SS container: (a) the Pd nano island of a rectangular symmetry having an outer coating of rectangular shape with the diffused metals from the SS container and a special structured Pd inner core of converging rectangular rings. The rectangular island is having a width of ~ 20 nm and a length of ~ 50 nm. and (b) a hexagon island of core -shell particle having the diffused metal coating as shell and a Pd inner core of converging hexagon rings.

The interesting features observed in the morphology of the Pd nano particles decorated TEG, created due to the metal permeation experimental process is summarised in the schematics as shown in Fig. 4.6. The nano particles are arranged in the corrugations in order. The morphology of the individual nanoparticle is shown in the right side of the figure. All the core-shells are having different geometrical structure (rectangle, circle, oval, hexagon, pentagon, square, etc.); no irregular shape is observed. Here a

representative oval shape is depicted. The outer coating is due to the diffused metals from the containers while the inner Pd core is having a ringed structure.

Fig. 4. 5 SEM images of the Pd (1%)-TEG after processing with vacuum annealing and hydrogenation (40 bar) in SS container, showing edges of the layers. The layers are curled on the edges to create the SW defects. The diffused metal atoms are attached in the form of clusters in the edges.

Fig. 4. 6 The schematics showing the nature of the particle decoration in the graphene layers as observed from the microscopic studies. The core-shell particles are observed to be attached in the corrugations. The right side of the image shows the nature of the core-shell. The inner core is made up of Pd with a special concentric geometrical shape while the outer coating is formed by the diffused contact metal particles. All the core-

shell particles are having different geometrical shape; here an oval shape is shown as a representation.

4.4.2. Magnetic response

In order to verify the effect of the diffused metal impurities in the spin distribution of the system, the magnetic responses were analysed. The following figures (Fig. 4.7 to Fig. 4.10) show the magnetic characteristics of the mentioned samples. The analysis shows that magnetic properties are induced into the system through the permeated container metal entities. Consequently, the total magnetic behaviour of the system is the sum of the contributions from different individual faculties as well as their combined synergic effects.

Fig. 4. 7 Magnetic response of Pd(20%)-TEG samples showing the effect of metal permeation; after vacuum annealing followed by processing under hydrogen pressure in SS container, recorded using SQUID -VSM- Magnetization (M) as a function of the applied field B at room temperatures – 300K.

Fig. 4.7 shows the variation of magnetisation with the applied field, for Pd (20%)-TEG at room temperature. From the figure, it is clear that a large hysteresis is observed compared to the other studies of corrugated graphene in chapter-3 or the Pd black structures of later discussions. This can be attributed to the core shell particles in the system. Since the ferro magnetic contribution is coming from the diffused metal particles from the containers, which are in the form of the outer shell of the Pd nano particles. Here the grain size will be more since every individual structure is appearing

as a covering on the respective Pd shells. Also, from a close observation, the hysteresis curve has a slight difference from that of the Fe system. In fact, the curve is having a paramagnetic contribution derived from the Pd particles as well. The temperature variation of magnetisation of the Pd (20%)-TEG is exhibited in Fig. 4.8. Similarly, Fig. 4.9 and Fig. 4.10 show the variation of magnetisation with applied field and temperature variation of magnetisation respectively, for the sample Pd (1%)-TEG. Fig. 4.9 is also showing the same kind of behaviour as that of Fig. 4.7. which can be attributed to the core-shell nano particles. Analysis of Fig. 4.8 and Fig. 4.10 shows that as the Pd content increases, the curve will be having more resemblance to the Pd magnetisation response. The curve in Fig. 4.10 shows the graphene behaviour similar to the reported ones.

Fig. 4. 8 Magnetic response of Pd(20%)-TEG after vacuum annealing followed by processing under hydrogen pressure in the metal container Temperature versus magnetization of the sample; recorded between the temperature ranges of 5K - 300K with an applied field of 500 Oe in field cooled (FC) and zero field cooled (ZFC) methods.

Generally, the divergence of FC and ZFC shows the co-existence of ferro and anti-ferro magnetic states or non-interacting super paramagnetic behaviour. During the harsh chemical synthesis process of TEG from graphite, many moieties can be intrinsically attached to the graphene layers such as -OH groups, -N or surface oxygen, hydrogen etc, which can show their magnetic contributions at low temperatures. Theoretical calculations have predicted the presence of ferromagnetic states at the edges of

graphene sheets, while anti-ferro magnetic states in the sheets. As the Pd content in the system is increased, the magnetic states will be more ordered and the weak graphene magnetism will be surpassed by the contributions from other diffused members; which is evident from the comparison of the two figures (Fig.-4.8 and Fig. 4.10). Again, the magnetic behaviour of the Pd black systems will be discussed in the later sessions, which will second this argument.

Fig. 4. 9 Magnetic response of Pd(1%)-TEG samples showing the effect of metal permeation; after vacuum annealing followed by processing under hydrogen pressure in SS container, recorded using SQUID -VSM; Magnetization M as a function of the applied field B at different temperatures – 5K, 50K and 300K.

It is clear from the Fig. 4.9 that the hysteresis contribution is coming from the graphene magnetism, which is strong at low temperatures, comparable to magnetically frustrated systems such as spin glasses and superparamagnetic materials. Also, the size and nature of the diffused metal particles play an important role here, as compared to the superparamagnetic curves observed in Pd black structures shown in the coming sessions (Fig. 4.24 and Fig. 4.25.). Here the diffused metal is appearing as the coating over the Pd nano particles than simply appearing over the graphene sheets or clustered on the top of the particle. Comparing with the Fig. 3.8 and Fig. 3.9 of chapter -3, here the hysteresis is more.

Fig. 4. 10 Magnetic response of Pd(20%)-TEG after vacuum annealing followed by processing under hydrogen pressure in the metal container Temperature versus magnetization of the sample; recorded between the temperature ranges of 5K - 350K with an applied field of 500 Oe in field cooled (FC) and zero field cooled (ZFC) methods

4.5 Experiments with graphite-based system

As observed and discussed in chapter-3, the pure graphite is less vulnerable to surface defects and approaching impurities. But there are many studies available where graphite has been used as a catalyst support material. The hydrogen storage studies discussed in the present thesis work also successfully used graphite as a catalyst support material for various catalyst nano particles. Accordingly, in the current work we are analysing the metal permeation effect in the catalyst nano particle formation, decoration and morphology of graphite.

The experimental procedure adopted here is the same as that mentioned in the above session of Pd- TEG samples. In brief, the catalyst nano particles are derived from the precursor material and is decorated in graphite during the process of vacuum annealing and hydrogenation. The PdCl₂ is used as the precursor here and the required amount is mixed with the as purchased graphite and then dried in vacuum oven. The sample is carefully taken and filled in the sample container (here SS container is under discussion). Then the sample container is inserted in the sample cell assembly of the experimental set-up (as mentioned before in the previous experimental sessions of TEG

in chapter-2) and performed the cycles of vacuum annealing followed by hydrogenation. After completing the proposed number of cycles, the sample is removed and taken for analysis. The observation of morphological changes and magnetic responses of the graphite samples are almost replicating the Pd-TEG samples. As in the case of Pd-TEG experiments, here also we have tested different Pd loading with graphite; all the results are comparable with that of graphene system as both phases the same metal-carbon interaction.

4.5.1. Morphological analysis

Fig. 4.11 shows the TEM images of the Pd (1%) -Gr sample picturing the distribution of Pd nano particles. Comparing with the figures of Pd-TEG samples, it is clear that SW defects cannot be observed directly here. Therefore, instead of being attached to the corrugations, the Pd particles are distributed randomly over the graphite matrix. With a close observation of the individual particles [Fig. 4.11 (d)], the nature of the particle is core shell type similar to the Pd-TEG samples. But the morphology is not as well defined as in the case of graphene support. This again emphasises the unique capacity of graphene to accommodate and maintain other foreign species into its own structure efficiently to showcase and complement its exceptional properties in a better way. As observed in the case of graphene, the diffused metals are coated as the shell structure in the Pd core-shell particles. Accordingly, it is clear that even though purer graphite is resistible to foreign species (as seen in chapter-3), graphite with other metal involvements can easily be subjected to adatom adsorptions. Similar kind of behaviour is observed in g-C₃N₄ samples as well. Obviously, the magnetic properties of the system are also getting affected. Therefore, care should be taken in the practical implementation of these kinds of materials.

4.6 Palladium black formation

As seen through the discussions, the efforts to observe the indirect contact metal permeation effects in materials through containers via a novel experimental procedure has successfully analysed many materials including the accessory metals such as metal nano particles decorated inside the system.

Fig. 4. 11 TEM images of Pd (1%)-Gr after processing with vacuum annealing and hydrogenation (40 bar) in SS container: (a) and (b) images showing the distribution of Pd nano particles in the graphite sheets. Here the nano particles of different sizes are distributed in the sheets as well as edges in a random manner. (c) and (d) are focusing on the nature of individual particles. The nanoparticles are islands of different geometrical shapes, arranged in the sheets as well as the edges.

The experiment is designed to duplicate the situations which can promote the contact metal permeation in the practical implementations. Thus, we have created the high temperature- high vacuum atmosphere and hydrogen exposure. These will produce the morphological changes inside the samples which will automatically promote the metal diffusion and its aftereffects. Consequently, it is quite evident that the sample morphology will be changed considerably due to the changes suffered during the experimental procedure. Hence our interest has finally driven us to observe the effects of the present experimental procedure in the Pd/Pt systems without the supporting

matrix. Thus, the concluding session of the contact metal permeation experiments are dedicated to the observational changes in the Pd/Pt systems with hydrogen aided reactions, which in effect materialized as the formation of a novel morphological structures of these metals- dendrite like morphology of Pd/Pt black. When the sample is heated under high vacuum, the molten state of the Pd atoms released from the precursors will form a special type of nucleation, which in turn will appear as beautiful morphological features in the samples. This nucleation can be affected by several experimental conditions such as duration of reaction, temperature, vacuum level, presence of hydrogen, etc. It is observed that temperature of the reaction and presence of hydrogen has influenced the structures considerably. These structures are predicted to be having very peculiar interaction properties such as fundamental, morphological as well as application based. They are noticed to be having high surface area, highly porous nature, distinguishing them as a separate existence in between that of bulk metallic and the nano Pd forms. Very few reports are available supporting the various unique properties of these structures compared to their bulk counterparts. The following sessions will be discussing a few selected representative results of Pd black samples obtained from the present experimental procedure.

4.6.1 Morphological analysis

Since the newly produced structures are having a unique morphology, the major analysis discussed here is based on the morphology studies. Since the structure exists as a form in between bulk and nano, SEM analysis is the best method for these materials. Here we are considering the Pd black structures – their morphology, influence of hydrogen reactions in the morphology, influence of metal container effects in the properties, etc. are discussed briefly. We have used both PdCl₂ and Pd- acetate as base material for the synthesis of Pd black; in order to avoid the ambiguities related to the chlorine presence and its impended reactions with metals from the precursor material. Surprisingly, both the precursors gave the same effects in the formation of the structures as well as in the corresponding contact metal permeation. In order to avoid the contact metal permeation effects through containers, we have used quartz containers and Pd- metal containers; so that we could obtain the pure Pd black structures. The different cases of the experiments are discussed below.

4.6.1.1. With vacuum annealing and hydrogenation

Fig. 4. 12 (a)- (f): SEM images of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation. The ‘fern forest’ like Pd black dendrite structures are visible in the images.

Here the experimental procedure adopted is the same as that used for TEG experiments in chapter-2. The precursor material powders were carefully filled in the metal containers and then the container is inserted into the sample cell assembly of the system; the normal vacuum annealing procedure and hydrogenation cycles were continued, and finally removed the samples and performed the analysis. The same experimental conditions were verified with both PdCl₂ and Pd- acetate precursors. Moreover, in order to analyse the effect of temperature in the morphology of samples we have performed the experiments with different temperatures. All the repetitions show that both PdCl₂ and Pd-acetate are giving the same morphology, while experimental conditions like temperature and hydrogen presence will be affecting the structure. The following discussions will be explaining the selected results from the analysis.

Fig. 4. 13 The elemental mapping of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation. The sample is observed as a ‘fern forest’ like structure. The blue flowers are the contributions of oxygen from surface oxidation. The green coloured sites show the diffused Fe particles from the container material and the profound red colour is the contributions from the Pd.

Fig. 4.12 shows the SEM images of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation. The sample is a ‘fern forest’ like structure observed from the images 4.12 (a) to (f). In the far view shown in Fig. 4.12 (a), the structure looks like a ‘cauliflower’ arrangement, but at a close observation, the fern leaves are visible. Fig. 4.12 (e and f) shows the nature of the fern leaves.

Fig. 4. 14 The EDX spectra of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation. The various constituents such as diffused Fe particles (green), surface oxygen (blue) and the palladium (red) are indicated in the figure.

In order to get a clear idea of contact metal permeation and the positions of the diffused metals, the elemental mapping of the system is done with EDX analysis. The elemental mapping shown in Fig. 4.13 beautifully shows the nature and positions of different components in the morphology of the system. As the samples are kept under ambient conditions outside, surface oxidation has occurred, which is appearing as the blue

flowers in the image. As seen, the intense blue colour of oxygen is appearing only at the top of the surface, due to the surface oxidation, which can be removed easily. The Pd components are marked in red, which is the base colour of the image. Again, the diffused metal clusters are marked as green, but can be observed as slightly yellow in the picture. This is because, the diffused metals have been deeply inserted into the bulk of the Pd structure, forming nano clusters with random distributions, throughout. Fig. 4.14 shows the EDX spectrum of the system with different constituent elements as represented in the table 4.1.; where the carbon contribution is coming from the carbon tape used for the measurements. The diffused Fe nano clusters occupies 0.78% of the total mass of the sample.

Fig. 4. 15 (a)- (d): SEM images of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in Pd container to avoid the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation. The ‘fern forest’ like Pd black dendrite structures are visible in the images. The (c) and (d) images show the narrow ring -like texture of the Pd in the system.

Table: 4.1. The constituent elemental distribution of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation.

Spectrum 1

Element	At. No.	Netto	Mass [%]	Mass Norm. [%]	Atom [%]	abs. error [%] (1 sigma)	rel. error [%] (1 sigma)
Carbon	6	2231	2.90	3.00	20.73	0.56	19.33
Oxygen	8	160	0.68	0.70	3.64	0.31	45.28
Iron	26	674	0.78	0.81	1.20	0.06	8.20
Palladium	46	125618	92.09	95.49	74.42	2.97	3.22
		Sum	96.44	100.00	100.00		

Fig. 4. 16 (a)- (d): SEM images of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in Pd container to avoid the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 100⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation for testing the

temperature effect. The nucleation is seemed to be incomplete with soft edges as observed from the figures.

For avoiding the contact metal permeation, we have repeated the experiment with the container of similar size and shape made from Pd metal. The observed morphology of the Pd- black systems are the same without metal permeation, as shown in Fig. 4.15. The fern leaves shown in Fig. 4.15 (a and b) share the same morphological arrangements as that of the previous sample. The HRSEM images shown in Fig. 4.15 (c and d) shows the appearance of Pd shape in the structure. These Pd structures are having a narrow ring kind of appearance, which will be in agreement with the ring structures appeared in the Pd inner core of the Pd core-shell particles, in the Pd- TEG and Pd- graphite samples. Consequently, it is very evident from this observation that the process of vacuum annealing and hydrogenation will be creating a new inner morphological structure in the Pd nano forms, which will be appearing as rings in the morphology. This may be due to the structural modifications happening in the Pd lattice, like SW defects in graphene system.

Fig. 4. 17 Elemental mapping of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in Pd container to avoid the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 100⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation for testing the temperature effect. The nucleation is seemed to be incomplete with soft edges as

observed from the figures. The blue spots are the contributions from oxygen, while the entire Pd system is appearing as red.

Table- 4.2: The constituent elemental distribution of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in Pd container to avoid the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 100⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation

Spectrum 1

Element	At. No.	Netto	Mass [%]	Mass Norm. [%]	Atom [%]	abs. error [%] (1 sigma)	rel. error [%] (1 sigma)
Carbon	6	2227	2.91	3.01	20.94	0.56	19.34
Oxygen	8	145	0.63	0.65	3.40	0.30	47.16
Palladium	46	124542	93.21	96.34	75.66	3.00	3.22
		Sum	96.75	100.00	100.00		

Fig. 4. 18 The EDX spectra of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in Pd container to avoid the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 100⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation for testing the temperature

effect. The constituents such as surface oxygen (blue) and the palladium (red) are indicated in the figure.

For testing the effect of temperature on the growth process, we have repeated the experiments with different temperatures. The SEM images of Fig. 4.16 show the morphology of the structures obtained at 100⁰C in Pd metal containers, with PdCl₂ as precursor. Here the structures are of sponge-like having numerous pores. But the close observation from the image of 4.16 (d), it is clear that the nucleation is not complete and the edges are soft and blunt; while the structures grown in high temperatures (350⁰C) are having sharp end points which indicates the completion of the nucleation process. The elemental mapping is shown in Fig. 4.17. As mentioned before, surface oxidation can be observed from the image.

The EDX spectrum shown in Fig. 4.18 shows the composition analysis of the sample as followed in table 4.2. As mentioned in the previous case, the carbon contribution is from the carbon tape used for the SEM analysis while, oxygen presence is due to the surface oxidation.

4.6.1.2. Without hydrogenation

Again, to check the effect of hydrogenation in the growth morphology, the experimental procedure is repeated without hydrogen. i.e.; only vacuum annealing process is performed. The SEM images shown in Fig. 4.19 is taken from the Pd black samples obtained from PdCl₂ in SS container with 350⁰C vacuum annealing, without any hydrogenation.

Comparing with the morphologies obtained from the previous samples with hydrogenation (Fig. 4.12, Fig. 4.15 and Fig. 4.16), here the nucleation is not perfect without hydrogen presence. The elemental mapping shown in Fig. 4.20 shows the different distribution of constituents in the morphology. Comparing with the image of Fig. 4.13 and Fig. 4.17, the presence oxygen is less; since the sample is not hydrogenated. The table 4.3 gives the percentage of constituents; where the oxygen presence is very less, 0.08%. The metal permeation from the SS containers are appearing as the yellowish green spreading into the bulk of the red palladium structures. The EDX spectra shown Fig. 4.21 shows the elemental contribution of the system with table 4.3.

Fig. 4. 19 (a)-(f): SEM images of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing without hydrogenation, for investigating the role of

hydrogenation in the morphology. The Pd black dendrite structures observed are different from the images of the samples with hydrogenation.

Fig. 4. 20 Elemental mapping of Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container, treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing without hydrogenation, for investigating the role of hydrogenation in the morphology. The blue flowers are the contributions of oxygen from surface oxidation. The green coloured sites show the diffused Fe particles from the container material and the profound red colour is the contributions from the Pd.

Table 4.3: The constituent elemental distribution of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing without hydrogenation.

Spectrum 1

Element	At. No.	Netto	Mass [%]	Mass Norm. [%]	Atom [%]	abs. error [%] (1 sigma)	rel. error [%] (1 sigma)
Carbon	6	630	0.94	0.86	6.98	0.27	28.60
Oxygen	8	17	0.08	0.07	0.45	0.11	136.93
Iron	26	2321	2.48	2.28	3.98	0.11	4.53
Palladium	46	129481	105.43	96.78	88.59	3.39	3.22
		Sum	108.93	100.00	100.00		

Fig. 4. 21 EDX spectra of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing without hydrogenation, for investigating the role of hydrogenation in the morphology. The various constituents such as diffused Fe particles (green), surface oxygen (blue) and the palladium (red) are indicated in the figure.

4.6.2. Magnetic Response

As discussed in earlier experiments, the contact metal permeation can affect the spin distribution of the material, which can be observed through the magnetic response analysis. The following sessions will be dedicated to the discussion of the magnetic studies performed in the Pd black structures. For a comparative analysis, the selected results from the response of two samples- one with contact metal permeation and the other without any permeation effect, are discussed here.

4.6.2.1 Without metal permeation

Fig. 4. 22 Magnetic response of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in Pd container to avoid the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation.; recorded using SQUID -VSM, Magnetization M as a function of the applied field B at different temperatures – 5K, 50K and 300K.

Fig. 4.22 and Fig. 4.23 are the magnetic characteristics of the Pd black samples obtained from Pd-based containers with 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation. The variation of magnetisation with applied field, shown in Fig. 4.22 shows the paramagnetic nature of Pd samples. However, at very low temperatures, a spontaneous magnetisation may arise due to the presence of frustrated structures derived from the peculiar high surface area porous structure of the Pd black. It is observed to be similar with the performance shown by the porous materials reported (Kopelevich et al., 2003). Fig. 4.23 shows the temperature variation of magnetization of the above-mentioned sample.

It is clear from the figure that the FC and ZFC structures have no considerable divergence, which is an indication of the ordered magnetic centres in the sample. However, at very low temperature, a minute difference is occurring due to the low temperature alignment of the porous structures and other moieties included from the synthesis procedure.

Fig. 4. 23 Magnetic response of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in Pd container to avoid the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation. Temperature versus magnetization of the sample recorded between the temperature ranges of 5K - 350K with an applied field of 500 Oe in field cooled (FC) and zero field cooled (ZFC) methods.

4.6.2.2 With metal permeation

Next, figures 4.24, 4.25 and 4.26 are the magnetic responses collected from the Pd black samples having metal permeation from SS containers. Here we have used the samples treated in SS containers with cycles of vacuum annealing and hydrogenation at 350⁰C.

The variation of magnetisation with the applied field shown in Fig. 4.24 is exhibiting the magnetic contribution of the container metal diffusion. Even though the observed magnetisation is the combined effect of all the component materials in the samples, the diffused Fe particles from the SS containers will be surpassing all other effects in the system. However, an interesting point is here to note that there is no hysteresis in the curves. This suggests the behaviour of the diffused Fe particles towards the super paramagnetic ordering. Here the diffused Fe particles will be extremely small in size so that their magnetic nature will be shifting towards the super paramagnetic response of Fe nanoparticles of extreme small size.

Fig. 4. 24 Magnetic response of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation.; recorded using SQUID -VSM, Magnetization M as a function of the applied field B at different temperatures – 5K, 50K and 300K.

Fig. 4. 25 The zoomed portion the magnetic response, showing the nature of hysteresis in the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation.; recorded using SQUID -VSM, Magnetization M as a function of the applied field B at different temperatures – 5K, 50K and 300K.

Fig. 4. 26 Magnetic response of the Pd black samples created from Pd -acetate processed in SS container to study the metal permeation effect. The sample is treated under 350⁰C vacuum annealing followed by 40 bars of hydrogenation. Temperature versus magnetization of the sample recorded between the temperature ranges of 5K - 350K with an applied field of 500 Oe in field cooled (FC) and zero field cooled (ZFC) methods.

Comparing with the magnetic nature of the Pd-TG/graphite samples shown in last sessions, the absence of carbon contribution may lead to the clustering of the diffused metals over the newly formed Pd- black structures, which can even form the Pd-Fe nano alloys of different compositions in the metal interfaces. In the Pd-TEG/graphite samples, the carbon support will change the reaction of formation of particles and convert them as Pd nano particles by providing different energy distribution barrier to the approaching particles and diffused metals and hence lead to the formation of the observed core- shell particles. This result emphasizes the advantage of graphene/graphite as a catalyst support material which may be useful in many field of applications; including the one discussed in the hydrogen storage studies (chapter-5) of the present thesis. Figure 4.25 shows the zoomed version of the curve showing no hysteresis in the response. The temperature variation of magnetisation is observed in the Fig. 4.26. The converging nature of ZFC and FC curves shows the magnetic ordering in the system. However, the small deviation towards low temperature region is due to the co-existence of ferro and anti-ferro magnetic states or due to the non-

interacting super paramagnetic states. The curve shows the combined contributions from both Pd system as well as the Fe system (Dho et al., 2002; Matte et al., 2009b).

4.7 Summary

With the newly proposed experimental procedure for observing indirect contact metal permeation from containers, the contact metal permeation effect in the accessory metals associated within the carbon network with the example of Pd nanoparticle systems has been analysed. More precisely, the effect of container metal permeation in formation, decoration and morphology of Pd nanoparticles incorporated in reduced graphene oxide, graphite, g-C₃N₄ are analysed. The effect of the experimental conditions- vacuum annealing and hydrogenation, and diffused metal particles in the surface morphology and magnetic response of the systems are discussed with a few selected representative examples of Pd (20%)-TEG, Pd (1%)-TEG and Pd (1%)-graphite samples. The metal permeation has affected the surface morphology and nanoparticle formation considerably while, the magnetic response of the system will be contributed by different constituents; though the diffused Fe contribution from the SS container metal will be dominating. With pure Pd precursor, novel dendrite structures of Pd black has been formed. Some of interesting morphological characteristics and a few magnetic responses of the newly formed structures are discussed. The microscopical studies revealed the ‘fern forest -like’ surface texture of the Pd black samples; while the magnetic response of the diffused Fe metal nanoclusters shows the superparamagnetic effect. Moreover, pure Pd black structures without any container metal diffusion is also synthesized and the properties are investigated in this work.

CHAPTER 5

LOW SURFACE AREA CARBON MATERIALS FOR HYDROGEN STORAGE.

The current chapter describes the solid-state hydrogen storage studies on low surface area carbon materials for compact hydrogen storage devices. It constitutes the work done in various low surface area carbon materials with the help of catalyst aided hydrogen reactions to serve as potential hydrogen storage materials. Hence, in this chapter, the characteristics of various materials synthesized, their gas adsorbing properties, mechanisms behind, advantages and practical applicability are discussed.

5.1. Introduction

The long-term reliance of humanity on the energy solely derived from fossil fuels, has led to a number of challenges including global warming followed by climate changes due to the release of huge amount of greenhouse gas CO₂. Most of the world energy requirement for transportation and heating; which is the 2/3rd of the primary energy demand, is derived from petroleum or natural gas. Unfortunately, the combustion of hydrocarbon fuel contributes over half of all greenhouse gas emissions and a large fraction of air pollution. Thus, the urgency of developing alternative fuels arises. Among various alternative energy vectors, hydrogen offers the highest potential benefits. For the past few decades, as a clean and sustainable energy carrier, hydrogen has been promoted as a solution to the global warming and air pollution and hence attracting the attention of scientific community (Xiao Y et al., 2014; Hirscher M. et al., 2010; Wu M et al., 2013; Yadav S. et al., 2014; Christmann K., 1988)

But the popularization of hydrogen economy is stunted by different obstacles; of which one of the most important ones is the safe and efficient storage of hydrogen, particularly for mobile and automotive applications. Of all possible solutions the most reliable one is the storage in solid media as hydrides; which is free from the drawbacks experienced by compressed and liquid hydrogen. The released hydrogen from metal via safe endothermic process is of very high purity and hence can be directly used to feed a Polymer Electrolytic Membrane fuel cell (Amouroux J, 2006; Ram. B Gupta, 2008; Gross KJ et al., Robert A Varin et al., 2009; Bai XD et al., 2001;)

5.2. Motivation of present work

In general, a desirable on-board hydrogen storage material should possess the following characteristics such as safety, durability, energy efficiency, high storage capacity, moderate operating temperature, fast kinetics, low cost and high reversibility. Even though several materials have been studied in the past few years in the field of hydrogen storage such as complex chemical hydrides and molecular hydrides, their derivatives, physisorbed systems such as carbon aero gels and metal organic frame works (MOFs), carbon nanomaterials and conducting polymer nano- systems; no materials have been developed which can accommodate all the features of a good hydrogen storage material (Suyetin, M. V et al., 2011; Wang, L et al., 2009; Baldi, A et al., 2014;). A feasible hydrogen storage material should store hydrogen in thermodynamically stable state; but with small increase of temperature, should release the stored hydrogen. Many complex metal hydrides and chemical hydrides fall under the conditions established by US DoE, in many of the reactions, dehydrogenated products are too stable resulting in the inefficiency. Magnesium based systems are also facing high operational temperature and sluggish kinetics (Tozzini, V et al., 2013; Au, Y. S et al., 2014; Jia, Y et al., 2011).

Carbon adsorbents have been used as a class of reversible hydrogen storage materials through physisorption of hydrogen molecules. But most of the measurements have been performed at 77K which exhibit limited practicability and thereby do not satisfy DoE norms (Hu, Y. H et al., 2010) In the case of carbon nanomaterials, the main limitations are in binding energy (4 -6 kJ mol⁻¹ for graphene) and too small specific surface area (Adams, B. D et al., 2010). Therefore, there is a need for developing chemically modified carbon frame works with high binding energy. To achieve a high capacity, two approaches can be made, of which the first is by tailoring the pore size, length and shape to maximize the pore volume and surface area. Introduction of highly interactive sites to hydrogen within the matrix to increase the adsorbate- adsorbent interactions is the second approach to increase the isotheric heat of adsorption (Lee, J. Y et al.,2011). In the present work both of these approaches have been made into practice by introducing novel nitrogen rich porous materials such as graphitic carbon nitride to the frame of hydrogen storage industry and effectively using the suitable catalyst nano particle support mechanisms.

Again, the efficiency of a hydrogen storage material is characterized by two parameters- gravimetric density (GD) and volumetric density (VD). GD is the weight percentage of

hydrogen stored in the total weight of the system while VD is the measurement of the stored hydrogen mass per unit volume of the system. The volumetric capacity can be derived from the gravimetric capacity, if the bulk density is known. For practical applications, both parameters are important because a hydrogen storage device must be light and compact. Thus, here attempts are done to focus on high volumetric capacity hydrogen storage along with gravimetric density by the proper utilization of highly favorable low surface area materials.

5.3. Solid state hydrogen storage- present scenario

Since hydrogen has turned out as the most desirable alternative energy source; several means for its storage has become significant for the last few decades; still the attempts to make an ideal hydrogen storage material are under research. As mentioned, the efficiency of a hydrogen storage material is typically measured by two parameters- gravimetric density (GD) and volumetric density (VD). Generally, the volumetric capacity can be calculated from gravimetric capacity and bulk density of the material. For a light and compact hydrogen storage device in many practical applications, both parameters are important (K. Spyrou et al., 2013; E. Masika et al., 2014; J. P. Singer et al., 2008; Weidenthaler et al., 2011; J. Yang et al., 2010). The following session will give a brief outlook of the topic with supportive literature.

The available storage systems can be compared and evaluated by plotting their GD and VD as exhibited in Fig. 5.1., where the most desirable ones occupy the upper right corner (V. Tozzini and V. Pellegrini, 2013). The Department of Energy- USA (DoE) targets expressed in terms of GD and VD are shown as green crosses in the Fig. 5.1 (according to the 2015 target, GD is 5.5 % and VD is 0.04 g/m³ which corresponds to a usable energy mass of 1.8 kWh/kg).

From the analysis, the compression of hydrogen tanks has the maximum GD (100%) but needs very low temperatures and high pressures leads to safety issues; also, the VD of the liquid hydrogen is not maximum possible. The density of liquid hydrogen in molecular form is 0.068 kg/l while in solid state form is further compact as the VD in transition metal hydrides and light metal hydrides are in between 0.08 and 0.15 g/m³. But they need extreme temperature and pressure for adsorption/desorption processes.

MgH₂ combined with transition metals displays a good hydrogen adsorption with fast kinetics.

Fig. 5. 1 The GD and VD diagram for various hydrogen storage systems are plotted. [Figure courtesy: V.Tozzini and V. Pellegrini, Phys.Chem.Chem.Phys.2013]

In the figure, the orange lines represent the reaction in carbon nanotubes; the dots indicate different sizes whereas the line values the liquid hydrogen for large sized nanotubes. Nano structured physisorption based graphitic systems will come under this line. The oblique shaped strip is for graphene multilayers having spacing double than that of graphite (i.e., density will be nearly one half). Corresponding to different pressure and temperature, different storage densities are shown. The vertical dark red strips are for decorated or functionalized graphene while the blue rectangular strip represents the chemisorption in graphene (Here mostly single layers are considered and hence only GD is well defined and VD is roughly calculated.). The systems based other than graphene (different metal hydrides such as MgH₂, hydrocarbons, N- and B-hydrides) are exhibited in the shaded areas in red, violet and green. The green stars indicate the DoE targets (for 2015 and ultimate), while the constant density lines are in grey. (V.Tozzini and V. Pellegrini, Phys.Chem.Chem.Phys.2013)

5.3.1. Prospective hydrogen storage in carbon nano materials

Carbon nano materials have been identified as one among the promising storage medium for hydrogen, since they possess the auspicious qualities such as high specific surface area, low density, tunable pore distribution, fast kinetics, stability and large-scale production. However, the new trend two-dimensional material graphene is predicted as a good material for hydrogen storage, being a quasi- two-dimensional system, the volume density is not well defined for pristine single layered graphene. Hydrogen can be adsorbed in carbon materials mainly in two ways – physisorption and chemisorption (see chapter-1 for details). Calculations based on post- Hartree Fock/empirical potentials and quantum treatments of hydrogen have shown that both GD and VD have improved for multi layered graphene system than single layered. From these studies, the highest value of GD and VD are obtained for an inter- layer separation of $\sim 6-8 \text{ \AA}$. Therefore, these studies point out that for hydrogen storage devices, multi layered graphene is more suitable than single layer. In graphene multi layers, the attractive Van der Waals forces of two combined layers will introduce a ‘nano pump effect’. Thus, the internal pressure between the layers will again increase, reaching a high level of compression (S. Patchkovskii et al., 2005; K. Spyrou et al., 2013; V. Tozzini et al., 2013; F. Bonaccorso et al., 2015).

5.3.2. Hydrogen storage in graphene single layers

As explained in chapter-1, hydrogen adsorption in graphene takes place in two ways – either physisorption i.e.; interaction via Van der Waals forces (VdW forces), or by chemisorption i.e.; via chemical bonds with C atoms. Physisorption happens with molecular hydrogen having binding energy in the range of 0.01 to 0.06 eV theoretically. This binding energy is weak and hence requires low temperature and high pressure to ensure storage. Thus, the most ideal coverage of H_2 in uniform compact monolayer of graphene corresponds to 3.3 % (doubled if two sides are considered) which is practically difficult.

Chemisorption on graphene sheet presents a high barrier of 1.5 eV; since it requires the dissociation of H_2 (dissociative adsorption) irrespective of the normally observed potentials 0.7 eV and 0.3eV for H binding energy and chemisorption barriers respectively. Recent studies have shown that the adsorption of first H atom on graphene

locally modifies the graphene structure by favoring further H atom binding easier through a collective stabilization effect. The formation of H ‘dimers’ on graphene surface shown ~ 1 eV gain in energy than isolated bound H. The completely hydrogenated graphene i.e., ‘graphane’ can store up to 8.3% ($=1/12$) which is even greater than the DoE target. The process of hydrogen adsorption in single layer graphene sheet is summarized in Fig. 5.2.

Fig. 5. 2 The energy level diagram for graphene- hydrogen system. The energy is given as eV per H atom (calculated from theoretical as well as experimental calculations). The reference level is pristine graphene plus unbound molecular hydrogen. [Figure is adopted from V.Tozzini and V. Pellegrini, Phys.Chem.Chem.Phys.2013].

5.3.3. Increased capacity by chemical modification:

Even though multilayered nano structured graphene can do good hydrogen storage job by employing physisorption, the DoE target is still far away. In order to enhance the hydrogen storage under ambient conditions, several approaches have been done to exploit the chemisorption in graphene by introducing chemical functionalization with various atomic species. Nitrogen/ boron doping, chemical functionalization with alkali

metals such as Li, Na and K or introducing transition metals such as Sc, Vi and Ti or decoration with Pd/Pt or Ca has improved the hydrogen uptake capacity of graphene derived materials considerably. But considering the cost of production, cumbersome synthesis process, volumetric density, etc. there are a lot more factors to improve. Again, hydrogen corrosion with these metals will be high and can lead to a very short cycle life for the material. Also, the desorption barrier is high for graphene-based materials. Thus, the present experiments aim to develop low cost, less corrosive, easily synthesized, high capacity, environment friendly materials having sufficient volumetric density, operating in ambient conditions.

5.4. Low surface area carbon materials for compact hydrogen storage:

Here we are investigating the hydrogen storage possibilities in low surface area carbon materials hence can provide good volumetric densities. Taking all the criteria such as low cost, easily available, effortless synthesis, long cycle life, safe from corrosion, ambient operating conditions, high capacities, fast kinetics, favorable heat of reactions, environment friendly nature, etc. into account, two major studies have been done based on two materials- a) the novel graphitic carbon nitride-based composites and b) graphite-based composites; which will be explained in the following sections with details.

5.5 Graphitic carbon nitride as a potential hydrogen storage material:

5.5.1 Background and motivation

A wide literature support from various part of the world is existing for the use of carbon nano materials as effective hydrogen storage media. High surface area carbon Nano materials such as activated carbon, carbon nano tubes, Graphene etc. are already well employed in this field (Sakintuna B et al., 2007).

It is already a proven fact that the presence of nitrogen on carbon materials enhances the hydrogen uptake capacities to a great extent. But the complexities involved in the procedure of nitrogen doping will make the process cumbersome. In this context, if a carbon material, which is already enriched with nitrogen, and the Physics and

Chemistry of it allows to store hydrogen will be a breakthrough. With this point of view, graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) is a promising candidate for hydrogen storage media. As discussed in chapter-1, the material itself is endowed with numerous meso/macro pores and is having high amount of nitrogen content, but comparatively low surface area [12, 13] (Lee JH et al., 2014; Tahir M et al., 2013)

The first- principles study of Guangyong Koh et al., predicted the high storage capacity of g-C₃N₄ nanotubes due to its peculiar nitrogen structures. But in practice, for g-C₃N₄ nano powders, the normal storage of hydrogen through physisorption cannot give the predicted efficiency (Koh G et al., 2012). Upon dissociation of hydrogen molecule, the hydrogen atoms are formed, which can interact independently with the solid surface; which is called chemisorption. In periodic table, the transition metals can promote chemisorption (Gross KJ, et al). From the first- principle theory, it is already predicted that the functionalization of metal atoms like Titanium (Ti) can improve the capacity of g-C₃N₄ nanotubes. But for Ti functionalized g-C₃N₄ nano tubes, the calculated energy barrier for a molecule penetrating into the tube interior is much higher than that of pristine tubes; which indicates that the hydrogen molecule faces difficulty to enter via pores (Koh G et al., 2012).

In this regard, we examined the mechanism of ‘spill over’ (see chapter-2 for details) to improve the kinetics of hydrogen storage and hence the storage capacity. It is already well reported that the spill over mechanism of Palladium (Pd) nano particles over Graphene (G) and nitrogen doped Graphene (N-G) can be used for hydrogen storage. (Parambath VB et al., 2012; Parambath VB et al., 2011; 2013) Here we are reporting an efficient and simple method of Pd and Pd alloy nano particles decoration over g-C₃N₄ powders and hence investigating its improved hydrogen storage capacity compared to the pure g-C₃N₄ powders.

5.5.2 g-C₃N₄ as a support for catalyst aided hydrogen storage

Here in the present work we have identified g-C₃N₄ as one of the best material for hydrogen storage through various characterization techniques and hydrogen adsorption/desorption experiments. For exploiting the catalyst aided hydrogen reaction mechanisms, it could act as one of the best catalyst support material by virtue of its structure and properties. The present discussion includes the studies on pure g-C₃N₄,

palladium nano particles decorated g-C₃N₄ (Pd- g-C₃N₄) and palladium- cobalt alloy nano clusters decorated g-C₃N₄ (Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄).

5.5.2.1 g-C₃N₄ and Pd- g-C₃N₄

The experimental investigation of pure g-C₃N₄ as a potential hydrogen storage medium, its capacity as a good catalyst support matrix for Pd nanoparticles and Pd nano catalyst induced spillover mechanism for the enhanced hydrogen uptake are discussed in the following sections.

5.5.2.1.1 Characterizations

The normalized powder XRD patterns of g-C₃N₄ and Pd- g-C₃N₄ samples are as shown in Fig 5.3. (A). The g-C₃N₄ shows two major peaks at 27.2° and 13.1° with a d-spacing of 0.319 nm and 0.681 nm respectively. In the Pd- g-C₃N₄ samples, the above-mentioned peaks are preserved in the same manner along with the prominent Pd peaks. This is an indication of the successful immobilization of Pd nano clusters over the g-C₃N₄ matrix without restacking the g-C₃N₄ structure. The sure presence of Palladium fcc structure is evident through its peaks from (111), (200), (220), (311) and (222) planes. The calculated average particle size of Pd is ~10 nm from the XRD patterns, using the Debye Scherer formula (Tahir M et al., 2013; Tahir M et al., 2014).

Fig. 5. 3 The normalized XRD patterns (A) and Raman spectra (B) of g-C₃N₄ and Pd- g-C₃N₄

The normalised Raman spectra of g-C₃N₄ and Pd- g-C₃N₄ after background correction are as shown in fig.5.3. (B). The Raman spectra of g-C₃N₄ are attributed to the vibrational modes of triazine rings (Zinin P V et al., 2009; Liu XR et al., 2010). The broad peak from ~ (1000-2000) cm⁻¹ is derived from the amorphous carbon. This indicates that the granular phases of melamine had changed to the amorphous g-C₃N₄, which is in agreement with the observed SEM- TEM images and XRD analysis. However, the strong fluorescent background of g-C₃N₄ makes most of the peaks ambiguous. But in Pd-g-C₃N₄, the fluorescence is less and the peaks are more visible. The assembly of peaks up to ~1700 cm⁻¹ are considered to be raised from the various vibrational (breathing) modes of triazine rings. Similar to graphite spectra, defects bands are seen and are more intense in the Pd-g-C₃N₄ spectrum, which indicates the presence of Palladium. However, all the peaks of g-C₃N₄ are repeating in Pd-g-C₃N₄, indicating that the tri-s-triazine rings are not deformed during Pd decoration and are more rigid than the C-C rings of graphite. Again, the 2D bands are more prominent in the Pd- g-C₃N₄ spectra, indicating the presence of Pd; which is consistent with the observed XRD patterns (Li J et al., 2012; Chu PK et al., 2006; Schmidt CL et al., 2010; Reich S et al., 2004;).

Fig. 5. 4 The SEM images of g-C₃N₄ (a, b) and Pd- g-C₃N₄ (c, d)

The surface morphologies of the samples were analyzed using the scanning and transmission electron microscopy techniques. The SEM images of g-C₃N₄ and Pd- g-C₃N₄ are shown in fig 5.4. The amorphous nature of g-C₃N₄ with numerous pores is evident from the SEM images. The Pd particle decoration does not affect much in the morphological structure of the sample, which is confirmed from the image of fig.5.4 and is consistent with observed XRD and Raman patterns. The porous structure of g-C₃N₄ is again confirmed from the TEM micrograph of Fig5.5. Melamine is a simple molecule having an s-triazine ring, which is the building block of g-C₃N₄. From a close observation of the TEM images, the presence of tri-s-triazine (C₆N₇) rings are quite clear in both g-C₃N₄ and Pd-g-C₃N₄ specimens. From the fig. 5.5. (c, d), it can be observed that the Pd nano particles clusters are distributed over the g-C₃N₄ matrix. The EDX spectra shown in fig 5.6 (a) and (b) reveal the elemental composition of the samples. The pure g-C₃N₄ sample is well enriched with nitrogen and the Pd-g-C₃N₄ samples shows 19 wt.% of Pd particles' presence which is quite close to the proposed 20 wt.% Pd particle decorations. Again, the TGA curve of the Pd- g-C₃N₄ sample of fig. 5.6(C) confirms the 20wt% of Pd decoration over the g-C₃N₄ samples.

Fig. 5. 5 The TEM images of g-C₃N₄(a, b) and Pd- g-C₃N₄(c, d)

The BET surface area and porosity analysis

The BET surface area and porosity analysis, Fig. 5.7 is an effective tool for identifying hydrogen storage materials. The BET surface area and pore size distribution of g-C₃N₄ and Pd-g-C₃N₄ samples were analyzed using nitrogen adsorption – desorption isotherms at 77K are shown in fig. 5.7 (A). The observed BET surface areas of the samples are ~28.8 m²g⁻¹ and ~26.8 m²/g for g-C₃N₄ and Pd-g-C₃N₄ respectively. The corresponding pore size distribution from BJH method is also exhibited in fig. 5.7 (B) which shows the range of pore diameter (2-120) nm. The isotherms were found to be of type IV according to Bruner –Deming –Deming –Teller classification with a hysteresis in the range of (0.45 -0.99) P/P₀, which is the characteristic of a meso porous material.

Fig. 5. 6 The EDX spectra of (a) g-C₃N₄ and (b) Pd- g- C₃N₄ and (C) the thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) plot for Pd- g-C₃N₄ sample.

This is in well agreement with observed SEM and TEM images. The pore size distribution is indicating the presence of meso pores (2-50 nm), which makes the material as a unique gas adsorbing media (Miranda C et al., 2013; Li J et al., 2012). Also, the Pd-g-C₃N₄ sample has less meso pores and smaller pore volume, because some meso pores were sealed with Pd or other chemical reactions in the process of Pd decoration and the subsequent reduction. Because of the same reason, the BET surface area of the sample is also finding to be reduced for the Pd-g-C₃N₄ sample.

5.5.2.1.2 The Hydrogen storage studies

Hydrogen storage performance study- the general procedure:

A high-pressure Sievert's apparatus was used to investigate the hydrogen adsorption/desorption studies and kinetic studies of the desired samples, in the ranges 0.1- 3 MPa and RT to 100⁰C. Initially the unit was calibrated using high purity hydrogen (99.99%). The volumes of the gas in the empty sample cell were accurately measured by allowing various initial pressures at different temperatures.

Fig. 5. 7 The BET surface area and porosity analysis of g-C₃N₄ and Pd-g-C₃N₄ samples – (A) the Nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms and (B) the pore size distribution

The samples were first degassed at 280⁰ C using high vacuum to remove moisture and any dissolved gases. Later activation process was carried out by first evacuated the sample cell up to 10⁻⁶ Torr and then heated at 250⁰C for 2 hours. The sample was then cooled down to 100⁰ C under high vacuum and pure hydrogen gas was allowed to react with the sample until equilibrium is reached. The sample temperature was reduced to 50⁰ C and RT step by step and each time, the equilibrium pressure was established. The pressure composition isotherms were obtained using the hydrogen storage weight percentage capacity calculated for different pressure drops. After each cycle, the sample was degassed for 2 hours at 250⁰C. The desorption studies were performed by cooling the samples from room temperature to ice temperature and then again to room temperature. During the experiments, the room temperature was maintained as 25± 1⁰ C.

The kinetics studies

The kinetics studies were done at 100⁰ C, 3 MPa pressure. Following the same procedure for degassing and activation, the sample was cooled down to 100⁰ C and then allowed a sudden exposure to hydrogen, noting down the progress of pressure reduction during reaction using a stop clock till equilibrium was reached.

Hydrogen storage studies of and g-C₃N₄ Pd-g-C₃N₄

Fig. 5. 8 and Fig.5. 9 show the pressure-composition (P-C) isotherms and kinetics plots of pure g-C₃N₄ and Pd- g-C₃N₄ samples respectively. The P-C isotherms are recorded in the temperature range of 3⁰ C to 100⁰ C and pressure range of (0.1- 4) MPa and the kinetic studies were done at 100⁰ C with a pressure of 4 M Pa. It is observed from the P-C isotherms that the hydrogen storage capacity of the sample increases as the temperature decreases, due to the reduced kinetic energy of gas molecules to escape the barrier potentials. The desorption isotherms at room temperature indicates a high reversibility, ensuring the possibility of getting back almost 90% of the adsorbed gas at the time of desorption. The kinetic studies show how fast the material is responding to the hydrogen gas at the time of fueling.

Fig. 5. 8 The hydrogen pressure – composition isotherms of (a) g-C₃N₄ and (b) Pd- g-C₃N₄

At 3 MPa pressure and room temperature, the gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity is found to be 1.8 wt % and 2.5 wt% for the pure g-C₃N₄ and the Pd-g-C₃N₄ samples respectively. Owing to the less surface area of the material, this capacity is quite higher

compared to the capacity reported for the high surface area materials such as Graphene in the similar conditions. In the case of pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ samples, even though they are having very small surface area compared to nitrogen doped Graphene (N-G); the storage capacity is far better compared to the already reported value of N-G. Thus, the volumetric capacity of the material will be quite high. The synthesis process is also very simple and cost effective compared to N-G and the material itself is biocompatible, pleasant color, odourless and stable in ambient conditions. The maximum storage capacity is observed as 3.8 wt% and 3.4 wt% for Pd- $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and 2.6 wt% and 2.2 wt% for $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ samples for ice temperature and room temperature respectively for 4 MPa pressure. In the same conditions and for the same gravimetric storage capacity of hydrogen, our material will occupy pretty less volume compared to Graphene based systems, which can make the material attractive to the fabrication of compact devices.

Fig. 5. 9 The kinetics curves of (a) $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and (b) Pd- $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ at 100°C

Comparing to high surface area materials such as Graphene and multi walled nano tubes (MWNTs); the gravimetric capacity of pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ is high because of its innate nitrogen rich background and meso/macro porous structure. From the theoretical studies it is revealed that the presence of doubly bonded nitrogen atoms at the edge of the pores and the particular porous structure of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ provides a unique feature for adsorption of hydrogen over other materials. The presence of nitrogen atoms can stretch the H-H bond and hence reduce the energy barrier. Jinhua Jiang et al., already reported that the storage capacity of hollow nitrogen containing carbon spheres is 2.2 wt% at 80 bars of pressure. But we could achieve the same capacity for the pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ samples with the application of half the amount of pressure. High surface area Boron Carbon

nitrides which needs high processing temperature also show very less hydrogen uptake capacity compared to our present material (Yang SJ et al., 2009; Portehault D et al., 2010).

The kinetics studies show that comparing to Pd-g- C₃N₄; the pure g-C₃N₄ samples have sluggish kinetics. It is clear from the fig. that the decoration of Pd will improve the speed of the reaction and hence reduce the time of saturation. Thus, the gravimetric capacity of the material is quite improved by the decoration of Pd. This improved performance can be attributed to the metal catalyst driven dissociation of hydrogen molecule into hydrogen atoms as well as the subsequent diffusion of H atoms through the matrix and the followed adsorption by the matrix. This phenomenon can be explained using the well-known mechanism known as ‘spill over’. The well dispersion of Pd catalyst nanoparticles over the g-C₃N₄ stuff can make the hydrogen molecule dissociate into hydrogen atoms and the hydrogen atoms will not stay in the Pd cluster; instead it may spill over to the supporting matrix. Thus, the chemisorption or more physisorption of hydrogen will be ensured (Anela D et al., 2004; Lachawiec AJ et al., 2005). A schematic depicting the mechanism underlying this process is shown in fig. 5.10. In fig 5. 10(a), the structure of g-C₃N₄ with tri-s- triazine rings are shown. After Pd particle decoration, the Pd nanoparticle clusters are spread around the g-C₃N₄ matrix is shown in fig 5.10 (b). The TEM images of fig 5.5 (a, d) are in well agreement with these schematics. The fig. 5.10(c) is intended to describe the adsorption of hydrogen though the spill over mechanism originated by the Pd nano particle sites. In all these figures; blue, cyan, grey and pink balls represent nitrogen, carbon, palladium and hydrogen atoms respectively.

The enhancement in the wt% due to spill over can be calculated by applying first approximation principle. The wt% enhancement at 25⁰C, 20 bar pressures can be calculated from the first approximation that

$$wt\%_{\text{spillover}} = wt\%_{\text{Pd-g-C}_3\text{N}_4} - (100 - n) \times wt\%_{\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4} - n \times wt\%_{\text{Pd}}; \dots\dots\dots 5(1)$$

where ‘wt%’ is the percentage of hydrogen stored in the respective samples and ‘n’ is the weight percentage of Pd decoration in the sample, in the present case it is 20 %.

By substituting the corresponding values, it calculated that the weight percentage enhancement due to spill over is 0.668. This value is slightly less than the already reported spill over enhancement in the case of Graphene. This is because the surface

area of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ sample is already very less compared to Graphene, and the further decoration of Pd nanoparticle clusters will reduce the surface area by $\sim 2 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, by sealing some pores, which is confirmed from the BET measurements. This suggest that the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ samples having very high surface area like sheeted structures can incorporate Pd clusters well and it can improve the capacity very well. But the spill over weight percentage enhancement shows that almost 35 wt% of the adsorbed hydrogen is due to spill over. The comparative kinetic study of pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and Pd- $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ samples fig 5.9 reveals that all the spill over happens in the very initial stage of the reaction and finally the reaction is getting a saturation level. In the case of Pd- $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ samples, as soon as the sample is exposed to the hydrogen gas, the weight percentage is getting increased while in the case of pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ sample, time delay is there to improve the weight percentage.

Fig. 5. 10 The schematic representing a) pure $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ structure, b) Pd- $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ structure and c) the spill over mechanism of hydrogen in Pd- $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ structure.

The Pd decoration and hence the spill over has improved the kinetics indicating the fast dissociation of hydrogen molecule into hydrogen atoms and improving the further adsorption. Guanyong Koh et al, first principles study reveals that for $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ nano tubes, the calculated binding energy for hydrogen atoms to be chemisorbed in pores is negative up to 3 H atoms in one pore and will be positive for 4H atoms. So, the configuration with 1H atom chemisorbed to each alternate N atom along the pore edges will be energetically stable. Due to the low energy barrier, the storage and release of

hydrogen will be very fast comparatively at low pressure and temperature. Thus, from our study, it is clear that the spill over mechanism facilitated by Pd nano particle cluster decoration can be well used to enhance the hydrogen storage capacity of g-C₃N₄.

5.5.2.1.3 Conclusion:

The hydrogen storage capacity of the new trend nitrogen rich carbon material g-C₃N₄; synthesized by a simple cost-effective method, is studied. Even though g-C₃N₄ is having very less surface area compared to its counterpart N-G, the hydrogen storage capacity is very high. A simple but novel method of decorating the metal nano particle over g-C₃N₄ is developed. By this method, the Pd decoration on g-C₃N₄ is done and its enhanced hydrogen storage capacity due to the spill over mechanism is studied. Considering its lower surface area, a higher storage capacity is observed for this novel material. Compared with high surface area materials, it will occupy considerably very less space for the same hydrogen content, which make it an attractive candidate for commercial hydrogen storage media.

5.5.2.2. Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ as a hydrogen storage material

It has been already proposed and proven that addition of a small amount of transition metal such as Pd to the porous carbon can form the synergic interaction, which can adsorb hydrogen by dissociative chemisorption followed by surface movement and storage of hydrogen at remote sites, otherwise inaccessible to the hydrogen molecule (spill over concept). Even though Pd in its nanoform is identified as the potential catalyst for hydrogen spillover and hence hydrogen storage, the high cost and limited supply are pulling it down from the target. Hence alloying Pd with cost effective metal such as Co is a worthy solution (Nair, A. a. S et al., 2015; Bhat, V. V et al., 2009; Konda, S. K. et al., 2015; Adams, B. D et al., 2011).

Among the porous carbon materials, graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄), a highly porous carbon structure having splendid amount of nitrogen, is already experimented as one of the best materials for physisorption of hydrogen (~2wt% for 4 MPa pressure) irrespective of its small surface area. On Pd nanoparticle decoration, the material has increased its capacity considerably; but still away from the target. Hence it is apparent that the spillover efficiency and cost effectiveness of the material can be improved by alloying Pd with Co. In addition, stability of the material can be improved by implementing alloy-based catalyst than pure Pd catalyst; since it can reduce the

corrosion due to hydrogen interaction. . It has been reported that among all the alloy combinations of cobalt with noble metals such a palladium or platinum, the ratio 3: 1 has the highest atomic ordering as well as appropriate geometrical features and electron density state (Koh, G. et al., 2012; Beaumont, S. K et al., 2014; Huesges, B. Z et al., 2013; Zhong, Z. Y et al.,2002; Squires, R. G. et al., 1963; Villarroel, M et al., 2008; Kauraala, K et al., 2004; Lim, Y et al., 2013; Manogaran, D et al., 2013; Oishi, K. et al., 2012; Zhang, Y et al., 2013). Hence in this work, the synthesis and the hydrogen storage properties of Pd₃Co alloy nanoparticles decorated graphitic carbon nitride (Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄) are discussed and the results are compared with those of pristine g-C₃N₄.

5.5.2.2.1. Characterizations

The convenient synthesis of pristine g-C₃N₄ powders were achieved through the simplest method; low temperature thermal condensation of melamine as discussed in chapter-2. Melamine is having the S- triazine ring structure as C₃N₆H₆. When at higher temperature, the thermal condensation happens, the crystalline form of melamine will completely transform into amorphous carbon nitride, which is having graphite like structure g-C₃N₄. The morphology will also change from granular to layer like structure with different sizes of flakes. The structure schematic of g-C₃N₄ matrix is as shown in Fig. 5.11(a). The structure consists of a network of tri- S- triazine rings, which can give rise to a porous network having plenty of nitrogen atoms. In particular, its peculiar porous nature and the heavy nitrogen content can make it as a unique gas-adsorbing medium (Zhang, Y et al.,2013). In order to introduce the alloy catalyst driven adsorbing mechanism, palladium-cobalt alloy nano particle cluster decoration is done over the pristine g-C₃N₄ matrix. The 3:1 ratio Palladium-Cobalt alloy (Pd₃Co) nanoparticles clusters were successfully immobilized over the g-C₃N₄ matrix through the normal Ethylene Glycol (EG) reduction technique with a slight modification according to the need. In the present synthesis method, we have used the non-aqueous medium, EG; which could act as reducing, stabilizing as well as dispersing agent so that the palladium-cobalt alloy nanoparticles can be formed from their corresponding precursors and can be distributed as the clusters over the g-C₃N₄ support (D. Berger et al.,2010; Chokratanasombat et al., 2012; Adekoya, J. et al., 2014). A structural schematic showing the cluster distributions over the g-C₃N₄ matrix is as shown in Fig. 5.11(b). In this figure the blue, cyan and ash color balls represent nitrogen atom, carbon atom and Pd₃Co nanoparticles respectively.

The normalized powder XRD patterns of g-C₃N₄ and Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ samples are as shown in Fig. 5.12. (A). g-C₃N₄ shows two major peaks at 27.2° and 13.1° with a ‘d’ spacing of 0.319 nm and 0.681 nm respectively. In Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄, the above-mentioned peaks are preserved in the same manner along with the prominent Pd peaks. This is an indication of the successful immobilization of the nanoclusters over the g-C₃N₄ matrix without restacking the g-C₃N₄ structure. In addition, Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ pattern shows the main characteristics peaks from face centered cubic (fcc) crystalline Pd (111), (200), (220), (311) and (222) planes indicating that the catalyst contains single phase fcc disordered structure (solid solution) (Tahir, M et al., 2013; Tahir, M et al., 2014).

Fig. 5. 11 Structural schematics of a) g-C₃N₄ and b) Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄

Also, the absence of any reflection corresponding to pure cobalt is an indication of perfect alloying. These results suggest that without needing any pre-modification, g-C₃N₄ matrix acts as a favorable support not only for mono- species such as palladium but also for binary phase like palladium- cobalt alloy nanoparticles because of the strong nitrogen content. This provides convenience and possibility, as expected, to

improve the catalytic activity. Here we have adopted the optimized value of 20 wt% for the catalyst loading. The average particle size from the XRD is determined from the full width half maximum of the Pd (111) peak using the Debye Scherer equation as 7.6 nm for Pd₃Co. The decreased particle size account for the increased surface area, which is in agreement with the BET results, is anticipated to increase the catalytic activity (Kaszkur, Z. et al., 2012; Gharibi, H et al., 2013).

Fig. 5. 12 (A) Normalized XRD patterns of a) g-C₃N₄ and b) Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ and (B) normalized Raman spectra of a) g-C₃N₄, and b) Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄

The normalized Raman spectra of g-C₃N₄ and Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ after background corrections are as given in Fig. 5.12. (B). Raman spectra of g-C₃N₄ are attributed to the vibrational modes of triazine rings.^[33, 34] The broad peak from ~ (1000-2000) cm⁻¹ is derived from the amorphous carbon. This indicates that the granular phases of melamine had changed to the amorphous g-C₃N₄, which is in agreement with the observed SEM- TEM images and XRD analysis. However, the strong fluorescent background of g-C₃N₄ makes most of the peaks ambiguous. But in Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄, the fluorescence is less and the peaks are more visible. Again, comparing the spectra of Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ with the reported spectra of Pd-g-C₃N₄, there are no visible changes in the observed Raman peaks, which indicate the formation of Pd₃Co alloy. The assemblies of peaks up to ~1700 cm⁻¹ are considered to be raised from the various vibrational (breathing) modes of triazine rings. Similar to graphite spectra, defects bands can be observed and are more intense in the Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄, which indicates the presence of Pd in its alloy phase. All the peaks of g-C₃N₄ are observed in Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄, confirming that the tri-s-triazine rings are not deformed during the catalyst

decoration and are more rigid than the C-C rings of graphite. This indicates the capability of g-C₃N₄ matrix as a favorable support to accommodate the catalyst in its mono- species form as well as alloy form. Also, the 2D bands are more prominent in the Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄, supporting the presence of Pd₃Co. The thermo gravimetric analysis of Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ in Fig. 5.13. (A) confirms the 20wt% Pd₃Co alloy catalyst decoration over the pristine g-C₃N₄ (Zinin, P. V et al., 2009; Liu, X. R et al., 2010; J. Li et al., 2012; Chu, P. K et al., 2006; Schmidt, C. L et al., 2010; S. Reich, C. et al., 2004).

Fig. 5. 13 - (A) Thermo gravimetric analysis plot of Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ and (B) EDX spectra of (a) g-C₃N₄ and (b) Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄

The EDX spectra shown in Fig. 5.13 (B) reveal the elemental composition of the samples. The pristine g-C₃N₄ is well enriched with nitrogen having a composition of C (47.91%) and N (52.09 %) while Pd₃Co-g-C₃N₄ shows a composition of Pd (14.90 %) and Co (4.80 %) in 3:1 atomic ratio with C (35.81 %) and N (46.02 %). From this data it is evident that the proposed 20 wt% of Pd₃Co alloy particles is distributed in g-C₃N₄.

The surface morphologies of the samples were analyzed using the scanning and transmission electron microscopy techniques (see Fig. 5.14 (A, B, C) and Fig. 5.14. S₁ and Fig. 5.14. S₂). The amorphous nature of the pristine g-C₃N₄ with numerous pores is evident from the SEM and TEM images shown in Fig. 5.14 (A). The Pd₃Co alloy nanoparticle decoration had not affected considerably in the morphological structure of the g-C₃N₄, which is confirmed from the SEM images of Fig. 5.14. (B) and is consistent with the observed XRD and Raman profiles. From a close observation of the TEM images, the presence of tri-s-triazine (C₆N₇) rings is quite clear in both g-C₃N₄ and

$\text{Pd}_3\text{Co-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ specimens. In Fig. 5.14. C (a), the marked yellow rings represent the Pd_3Co nanoparticle clusters.

Fig. 5. 14 (A)- SEM (a) and TEM (b) images of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and (B)- SEM images of $\text{Pd}_3\text{Co/g-C}_3\text{N}_4$.

Fig. 5.14 (C)- TEM images of $\text{Pd}_3\text{Co/g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ – a) showing the nanoparticle clusters and b) the enlarged view of a single cluster.

It is evident from the figure that nanoclusters of approximately <100 nm, are distributed randomly throughout the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ substrate. Fig. 5.14.C (b) shows the enlarged version of a single cluster. In this figure, one can observe the nanoparticles of size ~ 7 nm's are clustered together to form a bundle; which is in agreement with the calculations from the XRD patterns.

Fig. 5.14 S₁- The SEM images of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ (a, b) and $\text{Pd}_3\text{Co-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ (c, d)

The elemental mapping shows the uniform distribution of Pd and Co in the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ matrix as seen in Fig. 5.15.

The BET surface area and porosity analysis are one among the most effective tool for identifying hydrogen storage materials. The BET surface area and pore size distribution of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and $\text{Pd}_3\text{Co-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ samples were analyzed using nitrogen adsorption – desorption isotherms at 77K are shown in Fig. 5.16 (A). The surface areas of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and $\text{Pd}_3\text{Co-g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ are $\sim 28.8 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ and $36.6 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ respectively. The corresponding pore size distribution from BJH method is also exhibited in Fig. 5.16 (B), which shows the

range of pore diameter (2-130) nm. According to Bruner-Deming-Deming-Teller classification, the isotherms are of type IV with a hysteresis in the range of (0.45 -0.99) P/P_0 , which is the characteristic of a meso porous material. This is in well agreement with the observed SEM and TEM images.

Fig. 5. 14. S₂- The TEM images of Pd₃Co- g-C₃N₄ (a, b, c) and pristine g-C₃N₄ (d)

The pore size distribution is indicating the presence of mesopores (2-50 nm), which makes the materials as an efficient gas adsorbing media. In the case of Pd₃Co-g-C₃N₄, due to the lattice strain experienced during alloy formation, the surface roughness and hence surface area along with the pore size has increased.

Thus, we could observe the increased amount of macro pores in the material even though some of the mesopores were sealed by the Pd₃Co nanoparticles. The high surface area Pd₃Co alloy particles could accommodate more amounts of nitrogen molecules, which are reflected in the observed BET surface area. For an ideal hydrogen storage material, the pore size should be slightly less than the kinetic diameter of hydrogen molecule (2.8 Å) (Obregón, S et al., 2013; Langhammer, C et al., 2010).

Fig. 5. 15 The representative elemental mapping image of Pd₃Co-g-C₃N₄ sample.

Fig. 5. 16 (A) - BET surface area analysis of g-C₃N₄, and Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ samples – the nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms and (B) - Porosity analysis of g-C₃N₄ and Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ samples

5.5.2.2.2 Hydrogen storage studies

Fig. 5.17 (A) and (B) show the pressure-composition (P-C) isotherms of pristine g-C₃N₄ and Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ samples respectively. The P-C isotherms were recorded in the

pressure range of (0.1-3) MPa and the temperature range of 0-100⁰ C. It is evident from the P-C isotherms that the hydrogen storage capacity of the material increases as the temperature decreases, which can be attributed to the reduction in kinetic energy of gas molecules to encounter the barrier potentials. The desorption isotherms at room temperature indicate a high reversibility, ensuring the possibility of getting back almost 90% of the adsorbed gas at the time of desorption. From the isotherm study at 3 MPa pressure and room temperature, a capacity of 1.8 ± 0.1 wt% hydrogen is observed for pristine g-C₃N₄, which is enhanced to 5 ± 0.1 wt% for Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄.

Fig. 5. 17 Hydrogen pressure – composition isotherms of (A) pristine g-C₃N₄ and (B) Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄

It is interesting to note that comparing to the high surface area materials like MOFs, graphene and activated carbon, this one- step synthesized porous material g-C₃N₄ is having a very high hydrogen intake capacity irrespective of its small surface area. Hence for practical applications, the material may be occupying comparatively less volume for the same amount of stored hydrogen and hence will be useful for making compact devices.

Fig.s 5.18 (A) and (B) show the kinetics behavior of pristine g-C₃N₄ and Pd₃Co- g-C₃N₄ towards hydrogen. It is evident from the figures that pure g-C₃N₄ has a sluggish kinetics compared to Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄. In Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄, within a shorter time interval, the amount of stored hydrogen is increasing exponentially and reaches a saturation

level, which can be completely attributed to the catalytic activity of palladium cobalt alloy nanoparticle clusters and their synergic interaction with the g-C₃N₄ substrate.

A maximum storage capacity of 5.3 ± 0.1 wt% at room temperature for 3.3 MPa of hydrogen pressure is observed for Pd₃Co/gC₃N₄. By calculation it is evident that the chemical modification by alloy nanoparticles decoration has improved the capacity by more than 250%.

Fig. 5. 18 The kinetics curves of (A) g-C₃N₄ and (B) Pd₃Co/gC₃N₄ at 100⁰ C

Fig. 5. 19 (A) The variation of Isoteric enthalpy of hydrogen (Q_{st}) with excess amount of adsorbed hydrogen and (B) The variation in storage capacity with number of cycles; shows the stability of the material

Isoteric heat of adsorption (Q_{st}) or adsorption enthalpy (ΔH) is a direct indicator of the strength and heterogeneity of interaction between the adsorbate and the adsorbent. Like conventional heat of phase-transitions, isoteric adsorption enthalpy can be calculated from the Classius - Clapeyron equation $Q_{st} = - R [\partial \ln (P) / \partial (1 / T)]_n$. Fig. 5.19 (A) shows the variation of isoteric enthalpy of adsorption with the excess amount of adsorbed hydrogen for the pristine g-C₃N₄ and the Pd₃Co-g-C₃N₄. The slope of the Van't Hoff plot between the pressure and temperature at each concentration is used for the calculation. Here the desirable temperature range (25⁰C- 50⁰C) is considered with a concentration up to 2 wt%. For a very low hydrogen concentration, the ΔH_{ad} is increased from 6 kJ/mol of g-C₃N₄ to 12.5 kJ/mol of Pd₃Co-g-C₃N₄. Even though the calculated ideal enthalpies for a good hydrogen storage material are (20-30) kJ/mol, practically suitable target will be ~15.1 kJ/mol. So, in the present work, the strategy to strengthen the interaction between the substrate and hydrogen is done through alloy nano particle decoration. All these performance comparisons between pristine g-C₃N₄ and Pd₃Co-g-C₃N₄ points towards the highly improved affinity of the later material towards hydrogen, which can be uniquely attributed to the alloy catalyst nanoparticles, initiated hydrogen spillover.

A schematic showing the mechanism behind the improved hydrogen storage performance of Pd₃Co-g-C₃N₄ is given in Fig. 5.20 and Fig. 5.21. The mechanism can be explained by the metal alloy catalyst-initiated hydrogen spill over. Here, the Pd₃-Co alloy nanoparticle clusters could very well act as the catalyst spill over sites which could dissociate the H₂ molecule into H atoms and further successfully could diffuse the H atoms into the supporting matrix, where they can be stored. Compared to the reported Pd decorated g-C₃N₄, here the capacity and kinetics together with the enthalpy has improved well.

There is a sharp increase in the percentage of hydrogen adsorbed in Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ compared to pristine g-C₃N₄ as 1.38 ± 0.1 wt% to 3.6 ± 0.1 wt% at room temperature and 20 bars. i.e., the enhancement is found to be ~260%. As mentioned in previous study, the enhancement in weight percentage due to the catalytic activity is measured from the first principle as 2.4 wt%, which is almost 65% of the adsorbed hydrogen at this particular pressure and temperature. Therefore, the catalyst plays the most important role in this adsorption process.

Fig. 5. 20 Schematic representing the hydrogen adsorption mechanism in Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ structure.

The stability of the material has been estimated to be good from the performance after sufficient number of cycles (Fig. 5.19 (B)). The alloying of cobalt with palladium could reduce the hydrogen corrosion in palladium and hence improved the stability of the material after several cycles of hydrogenation. The hydrogen trapping of the g-C₃N₄ matrix is driven by the nitrogen sites as well as the unsaturated carbon atoms, i.e.; micro pores with high adsorption potential. Once the mechanism has started; the catalyst site will act a bridge for the path of hydrogen to the g-C₃N₄ substrate. The substrate will find the catalyst site as a source of hydrogen atoms.

5.5.2.2.3. Conclusion

A novel high capacity hydrogen storage material Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ is synthesized through a cost-effective method. Through the efficient alloying of Pd with Co, the cost of the material is reduced as well as the hydrogen uptake capacity is increased considerably due to the synergic interaction of Pd₃Co catalyst centers with g-C₃N₄ support material.

Fig. 5. 21 The detailed schematic showing the hydrogen storage mechanism in the material

However, having a low surface area, Pd₃Co/g-C₃N₄ shows a hydrogen uptake capacity of 5.3 wt% at 3 MPa pressure and at room temperature due to the excellent spillover mechanism initiated by Pd₃Co catalyst nanoparticles, which has improved the hydrogen uptake capacity of pristine g-C₃N₄ by about 65%.

5.6 Experiments in graphite-based systems:

5.6.1 Background and motivation:

The practical reach of multi-layered graphene is mainly based on the graphene derived nanostructures such as graphene oxides and reduced graphene oxides, graphene nano ribbons, graphite nano platelets, graphene nano fibers, multi walled carbon nanotubes, etc. or porous carbons which are generally manufactured as powders; and the drawback of the powdered medium is the limited packing density. One of the reported easy method to get these graphene derived multilayers is based on the exfoliation of graphene oxide (GO) and its chemical functionalization (W. C. Xu et al., 2007; C. Pohlmann et al., 2013; Sevilla, Marta et al., 2014; C. Dillon et al., 2001). The GO exfoliated graphene sheets got a capacity (GD) of 0.68 wt % and their chemical modification through nitrogen and palladium has improved the capacity (GD) to 4.3 wt% (G. Srinivas et al., 2010; B. P. Vinayan et al., 2013; S. K. Konda et al., 2016). However, in these works the VD is very poor; since they possess comparatively large surface area graphene –like sheets. Moreover, the synthesis method of these graphene

sheets and chemical modifications are multi step processes assisted by an intermediate product as GO. Thus, the cost of production is high and yield from the parental product graphite is low. In this scenario, instead we are introducing the highly hydrogen affinitive catalyst sites directly to the graphite layers and thus dissociate the hydrogen molecules locally in these sites followed by further adsorption of hydrogen atoms by the layers will improve the volumetric capacity (VD) as well as easiness of production.

5.6.2 Graphite as a catalyst supported compact hydrogen storage material

The present work presents graphite as a good catalyst support material for different nano catalysts which can effectively promote hydrogen reactions and hence hydrogen storage through various characterization techniques and hydrogen adsorption/desorption experiments. The following discussion mainly includes the studies on palladium cobalt nano particles decorated nitrogen rich graphite (Pd₃Co/N- Gr) and magnesium -nickel alloy nano particles supported nitrogen rich graphite (Mg₂Ni/N-Gr).

5.6.2.1 Pd₃Co/N- Gr as a high volumetric capacity material

It is already well studied that if nitrogen is combined with carbon, it can give a very good hydrogen adsorption capacity than the pure carbon material (A. A. S. Nair et al., 2015). Again, for introducing the hydrogen spill over catalyst sites, the noble metal palladium is the most favourable option. However, its high cost as well as corrosion against hydrogen will pull it away from the hydrogen economy. Thus, by alloying the cost-effective metals such as cobalt can incorporate the cost as well as corrosion effects. Hence, in the present work attempts are being done to improve the hydrogen storage capacity of pure graphite by introducing nitrogen sites as well as decorating with palladium cobalt alloy catalyst nano particles (A. A. S. Nair et al., 2016). The efforts have been done to reduce the complexity of synthesis through a single step catalytic chemical vapour deposition process, which could effectively produce the palladium cobalt alloy catalyst nanoparticles embedded nitrogen rich graphite (see chapter-2). For effective alloying of Co with noble metals such as Pd or Pt the 3:1 ratio is preferable; since it can give the proper geometrical features, highest atomic ordering and electron density state (Zhong, Z. Y et al., 2002; Squires, R. G ,1963; Villarroel, M et al., 2008; Manogaran, D et al., 2013; Oishi, K ,2012; Tahir, M et al., 2013; Tahir, M et al., 2014; Kaszukur, Z et al., 2012; J. Li et al., 2012). Hence, the present work discusses the

synthesis and hydrogen storage properties of palladium cobalt alloy catalyst nanoparticles decorated nitrogen rich graphite ($\text{Pd}_3\text{Co}/\text{N}-\text{Gr}$).

5.6.2.1.1 Characterizations

Through an easy and convenient single step synthesis process, the ‘as purchased’ graphite sheets were transformed into nitrogen rich, alloy catalyst nano particles embedded ($\text{Pd}_3\text{Co}/\text{N}-\text{Gr}$) hydrogen storage media. The proposed synthesis procedure should favour two processes namely decomposition of melamine into nitrogen groups as well as their subsequent doping within the layers of graphite and the reduction of Pd and Co from their corresponding precursors and their further nucleation as alloy nanoparticles on the nitrogen rich graphite substrate.

Fig. 5. 22 Structural schematics of as purchased graphite and $\text{Pd}_3\text{Co}/\text{N}-\text{Gr}$

When the well-mixed graphite powder with precursors was exposed to systematic heating procedure in a tubular furnace in presence of hydrogen and argon, the desired composition of nitrogen, palladium and cobalt were assimilated in the graphite matrix. As the temperature was going beyond 280°C , the melamine started decomposes into nitrogen functional groups; which can subsequently be accommodated to the SP^2 networks of graphite sheets. When hydrogen gas was allowed to the system, Pd and Co were released from their corresponding precursors. Again, when the temperature is

raised to 700⁰C, the Pd and Co were deposited in the nitrogen rich sites of graphite layers as nanoparticle clusters. Thus, the nitrogen sites will favour the deposition of catalyst nanoparticle nucleation. In order to investigate the role of nitrogen on the hydrogen adsorption, we have synthesized a sample without nitrogen (melamine), i.e.; palladium cobalt alloy catalyst nano particle decorated graphite (Pd₃Co/ Gr) and compared the hydrogen storage performance. A schematic showing the alloy catalyst distribution over the graphite layers is shown in Fig. 5.22. The successful immobilization of palladium cobalt alloy catalyst nanoparticles in 3: 1 ratio over the nitrogen rich graphite substrate is achieved through this method. Here we have adopted the optimized value of 20-wt% for catalyst loading. Each grain of the graphite can permit the decoration of the nanoparticles on the top and bottom layers as well as the edges of the middle layers. In Fig. 5.22, the cyan coloured balls represent the carbon atoms and the pinks balls represent the Pd₃Co nano particles. The inset images (round) are the TEM images of graphite and Pd₃Co/N- Gr.

Fig. 5. 23 (A) Normalized XRD patterns of a) Pd₃Co/N- Gr and b) graphite and (B) Energy Dispersive X- ray analysis of Pd₃Co/N-Gr

The normalized powder XRD patterns of graphite and Pd₃Co- N- Gr are as shown in Fig. 5.23 (A). The graphite hexagonal planes are revealed through (002) and (004) peaks. In Pd₃Co- N- Gr specimen, the palladium face centred cubic (fcc) crystalline lattice is exhibited through the signature peaks of Pd (111), (200), (220), (311) and (222) planes along with the graphitic (002) and (004) peaks. Here the Pd (111) peak is broader and shorter, indicating the nano phase of palladium. In addition, there are no reflections corresponding to the elemental cobalt; since the catalyst contains single face

fcc disordered structure (solid solution) which is an indication of the perfect alloying of Co in Pd lattice. These results clearly suggest the successful immobilization of palladium cobalt alloy nano particle over the graphite substrate. Moreover, the nitrogen rich graphite substrate is well appreciated to accommodate the catalyst nano phase in its binary alloy form without any structural modification. This is a good indication of projected catalytic activity towards hydrogen as estimated (Obregón, S et al., 2013; Konda, S. K et al., 2015; Adams, B. D et al., 2011). The average particle size is extracted as ~ 20 nm for Pd₃Co nanoparticle from the full width half maximum of Pd (111) peak using Debye Scherer formula; which is in agreement with the observed microscopic images.

Fig. 5.24 SEM images of (a) As purchased graphite (b) Pd₃Co/N- Gr and TEM images of (c) As purchased graphite (b) Pd₃Co/N- Gr

Again, the elemental composition and distribution of the sample are analysed using elemental mapping and energy dispersive X- ray analysis. The EDX spectra (see Fig. 5.23(B)) shows the composition of elements in the Pd₃Co- N- Gr sample. The extracted wt% for each element is as follows- C (61.30 %), N (19.02 %), Pd (14.75 %) and Co

(4.93 %). From this data, it can be concluded that the sample contains the proposed ~ 20-wt % of Pd and Co together in a 3:1 ratio.

Fig. 5. 24 (e) and (f) – SEM/TEM images showing the Pd₃Co nanoparticle distribution

Fig. 5. 25 The representative elemental mapping of the Pd₃Co/N- Gr sample.

The surface morphology of the sample is revealed through the microscopic images shown Fig. 5.24. The TEM and SEM images of graphite layers in the as purchased powdered sample are shown in Fig. 5.24 (a) and 5.24 (c) respectively. When treated through the catalytic chemical vapor deposition synthesis procedure as explained

previously, the pristine graphite layers became enriched with nitrogen as well as embedded with the catalyst nano particles. The SEM and TEM images in Fig. 5.24 (b and d) show the random distribution of the nanoparticles in the layers. From the Fig. 5.24 (e and f), the size of the embedded nano particles are estimated as ~ 20 nm which in agreement with the XRD pattern calculations. In order to confirm spatial distribution of elements in the sample, the elemental mapping of the images is done. The representative elemental mapping of the sample is as shown in Fig. 5.25. It is quite evident from the figure that Pd and Co nanoparticles are distributed randomly over the nitrogen rich graphite layers.

Fig. 5. 26 (A) - BET surface area analysis of samples – graphite and Pd₃Co/N- Gr -The nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms and (B) Porosity analysis of graphite and Pd₃Co/N- Gr samples

The gas adsorbing sites of the synthesized sample were analyzed through the BET surface area and porosity measurements. The data are recorded using the nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms at 77K as shown in Fig. 5.26 (A). The observed BET surface area of the Pd₃Co- N- Gr sample is 0.5939 m²/g; while for pure graphite it is 1.2021 m²/g. The BJH pore size distribution is also exhibited in Fig. 5.26 (B). The isotherms are observed to be of type IV with a hysteresis in the range of (0.45 -0.99) P/P₀; according to Bruner-Deming-Deming-Teller classification, which is the characteristic of a meso- porous material. The pore size distribution shows a range of pores between (2-120) nm with a maximum volume at (2- 50) nm which is meso- porous. These qualities make the present material as a good gas adsorbing media. It is observed that the specific surface area of graphite is decreased after the decoration of

catalyst nanoparticle. This can be attributed to the sealing of some pore by the catalyst nanoparticles.

Moreover, some sites, including the catalyst centers will be not approachable for nitrogen adsorption; can be active in hydrogen adsorption. Therefore, in practical, for hydrogen adsorption the surface area will be higher (Beaumont, S. K et al., 2014; Huesges, B. Z et al., 2013).

5.6.2.1.2 Hydrogen adsorption studies

As mentioned earlier, the hydrogen adsorption -desorption studies were performed in Sieverts apparatus using pressure reduction method by applying the Van der Waals corrections for the hydrogen gas. Consider the three conditions of the system, where an initial pressure P_i occupies the initial volume V_i with the number of moles n_i , an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} at the initial volume V_i with the number of moles n_1 and an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} at the cell volume V_c with the number of moles n_2 . Applying the Van der Waals correction coefficients ‘a’ and ‘b’ for hydrogen, these three conditions will be evolved as the following gas equations.

$$abn_i^3 + aV_i n_i^2 + (RT + P_i b)V_i^2 n_i - P_i V_i^3 = 0 \dots \dots \dots (5.2)$$

$$abn_1^3 + aV_i n_1^2 + (RT + P_{eq} b)V_i^2 n_1 - P_{eq} V_i^3 = 0 \dots \dots \dots (5.3)$$

$$abn_2^3 + aV_c n_2^2 + (RT + P_{eq} b)V_c^2 n_2 - P_{eq} V_c^3 = 0 \dots \dots \dots (5.4)$$

where T is the sample cell temperature and R is the universal gas constant.

The number of moles of hydrogen adsorbed can be calculated as follows:

$$\Delta n = n_i - (n_1 + n_2) \dots \dots \dots (5.5)$$

By knowing the value of Δn , the hydrogen concentration of the sample (wt %) for a given mass ‘m’ at an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} (gravimetric capacity) can be calculated as

$$Wt\% \text{ of } (H) = 2 \Delta n / m \dots \dots \dots (5.6)$$

Thus, it shows the mass of hydrogen in 100 grams of the stored material. By knowing the value of the bulk density (ρ) of the material, we can find the volumetric capacity,

i.e.; the amount of hydrogen present in the unit volume of the stored material as gram per litre (g/L).

The pressure - composition (P-C) isotherms of Pd₃Co- N- Gr were plotted for different temperatures as shown in Fig. 5.27(A). The isotherms were recorded in a temperature range of 25 – 100°C with a pressure range of (0.1 – 3) MPa.

Fig. 5. 27 Hydrogen pressure – composition isotherms of (A) Pd₃Co/Gr and (B) Pd₃Co/N-Gr

As the sample temperature is increased, the storage capacity is decreased as expected; since gas molecules will get enough kinetic energy to escape the barrier potentials. The desorption studies at room temperature show the high reversibility of the adsorption process. Here for comparison and study the role of nitrogen in the adsorption process, the P-C isotherms of the Pd₃Co –Gr specimen in Fig.5. 27(B) is also considered.

From the isotherm study of Pd₃Co- N- Gr sample, at 2 MPa pressure and room temperature, the storage capacity is estimated as 5.1 ± 0.1 wt% hydrogen. Comparing to the high surface area carbon materials like graphene, activated carbon, MOFs or chemically modified carbon materials, this capacity is quite high. For pure graphite or few layer graphene, the reported value is less than 1 wt % under the same conditions. For Pd₃Co- Gr sample at 2 MPa and room temperature, the capacity is 2.9 ± 0.1 wt%. A maximum storage capacity of 6.5 ± 0.1 wt% at 3 MPa pressure is observed in Pd₃Co- N- Gr specimen while it is 3.6 ± 0.1 wt% for Pd₃Co- Gr. These results support Pd₃Co- N- Gr as a potential gravimetric capacity material.

Table 5. 1. A comparative study of GD and VD for various reported materials

Material	Surface area (~ m ² /g)	Bulk density (~ g/cc)	GD (~ wt%)	Pressure (MPa)	VD (g/L)- (Calculated)	References
Pristine-graphene (ideal)	2600	Not defined	3.3 (ideal)	saturated	Not defined	F. Bonaccorso, 2015
Graphene-like nano sheets	300-750	0.1–0.5	0.68	1	3.4	G. Srinivas, 2010
Chemically modified Pd/Graphene derivative composites	300-700	0.1–0.6	4.4	4	24.0	S. K. Konda, 2016
Pd/Multi walled Carbon nano tubes	100-300	0.5-1	2.0	2	20.0	S. K. Konda, 2016
Pd-modified Activated/porous carbon	1000-3000	0.4–0.5	0.2-1.3	8- 10	6.5	S. K. Konda, 2016
Pd modified carbon aerogels	500-700	0.2- 0.4	0.11	1	0.44	S. K. Konda, 2016
Graphitic-carbon nitride	28	1.8	2.6	4	46.8	A. A. S. Nair, 2015
Graphitic-carbon nitride Pd composites	36	1.8	5.3	3	95.4	A. A. S. Nair, 2016
Pd-modified Graphite composite	1.5	2.2	6.5	3	143.0	present work

For calculating the volumetric capacity, the bulk density of graphite is taken as 2.2 (g/cc). Converting the gravimetric capacity to volumetric density, we can get a maximum capacity of 143 g/L at 3MPa pressure and room temperature. Comparing with the other reported high capacity carbon materials, the present material is having very high volumetric capacity. For the pristine single layer graphene, the main practical difficulty in making hydrogen storage device is that its volumetric density cannot be defined; being a quasi-2-dimensional system.

The other graphene derived materials such as reduced graphene oxides, nano tubes and activated carbons, carbon nitrides, etc., and their Pd modified forms are also facing the low volumetric capacity due to their high specific surface area. Table 5.1 contains the comparative study of the various reported carbon-based materials and their Pd modified forms in the view of GD and VD.

Fig. 5. 28 shows the variation of volumetric capacity with surface area for different carbon composites based on the reported data. Here the present material Pd₃Co- N- Gr shows the highest volumetric capacity with considerable gravimetric density. Thus, this material is suitable for the fabrication of compact hydrogen storage devices. Generally, the interaction between graphite and hydrogen is of interest in three important research areas: molecular hydrogen formation in space, hydrogen storage and hydrogen- wall interactions in fusion reactors. The permeation of hydrogen through graphite is described as molecular flow.

Fig. 5. 28 Variation of volumetric capacity with surface area for different carbon-based composites based on the reported data (see Table -5. 1).

Fig. 5. 29 (A) The kinetics of hydrogen adsorption in Pd₃Co/N-Gr and (B) the stability of Pd₃Co/N-Gr with number of cycles of hydrogenation.

The chemisorbed hydrogen in the graphite can combine to form H₂ molecule before desorption. Once the spill over will start, the atomic hydrogen will migrate from the catalyst site to the layers. The rate of diffusion is temperature dependent. The adsorbed hydrogen atom can form dimers. Here in this case, the nitrogen sites in the sample will contribute to the accumulation of H atoms. In the spill over process, a flux of hydrogen atoms will be released from the catalyst site due to the dissociative chemisorption of molecular hydrogen due to the interaction between Pd₃Co nano particles, first flows into the material in the vicinity of catalyst site like ‘a bridge’ and then continue to flow through the substrate. The unsaturated bonds resulting from SP² carbon are responsible for H adsorption and subsequent diffusion.

The temperature -programmed desorption (TPD) and density functional theory (DFT) studies have pointed out the temperature dependence of diffusion coefficients through Arrhenius equations $D = D_0 \exp(-E_a/k_B T)$. As temperature increases, the diffusion coefficient will increase. At lower temperature, the quantum effect will be dominating. In fact, molecular hydrogen is expected to diffuse faster in graphite layers than atomic hydrogen. It is found that diffusion coefficient is larger for H₂ than H. Typically, at 300 K, $D = 6.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ for H₂ and $D = 9.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ for H.

Fig. 5. 30 Schematic representing the hydrogen adsorption mechanism in Pd₃Co/ N-Gr Structure

Thus, when the hydrogen atoms will diffuse through the void space, they will come closer than a minimum distance and recombine. As time progresses, the adsorbed H atom will migrate from layer to layer as H₂ molecules. In short, the first H atom chemisorbed in the surface behaves as a surface defect for the subsequent adsorption of the second H atom. Thus, the trapping- detrapping mechanism continues (M. Bonfanti et al., 2007; F. Marinelli et al., 2003; N. Rougeau et al., 2006; L. Hornekær et al., 2006; Carlos P Herrero et al., 2010; M. Warrior, R et al., 2007; L. Chen, A. C. Cooper et al., 2007).

By calculation, it is clear that chemical modification has improved the capacity of pure graphite by more than 350%. Fig. 5.29 (A) shows the kinetic behavior of Pd₃Co- N- Gr towards hydrogen. As soon as the sample is exposed to hydrogen, the reaction is happening exponentially and reaches a saturation level. All these performances can be attributed to the catalytic activity of Pd₃Co nanoparticles and their synergetic interaction with the nitrogen rich graphite. The alloy nano particle decoration has not only improved the capacity of the material, but also contributed to the stability of the material. The alloying of Co with Pd could reduce the hydrogen corrosion in Pd, which could retain the capacity of the material after several numbers of cycles; see Fig. 5.29 (B). The catalytic performance of the Pd₃Co nanoparticles in the nitrogen rich graphite

can be modelled using the hydrogen spill over mechanism. Fig. 5.30 shows the schematics of the reaction mechanism.

The catalyst centers will attract the incoming H_2 molecules, split them into H atoms and pump them to the graphite layers through subsequent diffusion. Thus, the graphite layers can hold the H atoms. Once the mechanism is started, the catalyst centers will appear as a virtual source of hydrogen atoms to the underlying nitrogen rich graphite matrix. Comparing the performance of both Pd_3Co -N-Gr and Pd_3Co -Gr, we can infer the role of nitrogen in the catalytic activity of the material. The nitrogen sites could improve the catalyst nanoparticle decoration during the process of synthesis. Here it is estimated that almost 160% of the stored hydrogen is due to the nitrogen sites. During the hydrogen reaction process, the nitrogen sites can improve the physic-sorption of H_2 molecules into the graphite layers. Moreover, the nitrogen sites will accumulate the diffused H atoms as clusters in the graphite layers. Both these physiosorbed as well as chemisorbed hydrogen will be packed between the layers of the graphite, which will be responsible for its highly improved GD as well as VD.

Fig. 5. 31 Schematic view of the present work in Pd_3Co / N-Gr as a high volumetric capacity hydrogen storage material.

5.6.2.1.3 Conclusion:

A potential high volumetric as well as gravimetric capacity hydrogen storage material is developed through a simple one-step synthesis process. The present material Pd_3Co -

N- Gr could show a maximum gravimetric storage capacity of 6.5 ± 0.1 wt% and a volumetric capacity of 143.0 g/L under 3 MPa pressure and room temperature.

Following the similar procedure, the hydrogen adsorption/desorption properties of palladium cobalt alloy particles embedded boron rich graphite (Pd₃Co- B- Gr) has been examined. Pd₃Co- B- Gr is found to be having a gravimetric capacity of 5.3 ± 0.1 wt% at 25°C temperature and 3MPa hydrogen pressure.

5.6.2.2 Non-precious catalyst-based hydrogen storage- Mg₂Ni/N-Gr

Even though we have analyzed the possibilities of low surface area carbon materials as potential hydrogen storage candidates with high capacities- both volumetric and gravimetric; with the help of catalyst aided reactions, the noble metal-based catalysts are still a challenge for the bulk amount of industrial production. In this context, catalysts based on non-precious metals are successfully tested. The present discussion will be giving a brief outcome of the study based on magnesium-nickel alloy nano particles embedded nitrogen rich graphite (Mg₂Ni/N-Gr).

5.6.2.2.1 Hydrogen storage in magnesium hydride:

Even though MgH₂ is reported as an ideal candidate for reversible hydrogen storage, the thermodynamic stability is pulling it away from the mainstream storage as it translates as relatively high hydrogen desorption temperature and slow adsorption/desorption kinetics. The kinetics can be improved dramatically by doping the magnesium with transition metals or by ball milling or surface modification (i.e.; reducing the size of the grain size). The typical unfavorable thermodynamic parameters which contribute to the high hydrogen release temperature (above 300°C) are $\Delta H = 74.4$ kJ/mol and $\Delta S = 135.1$ J/molK, which originates from the enormous lattice energy $[\text{Mg}^{2+}\text{H}_2^{-1}]_{\alpha}$ $\Delta H = 2178$ kJ/mol, relative to the bulk Mg ($\Delta H = 147$ kJ/mol) (S. Harder et al., A.R. Vijay Babu et al., S.Orimo et al., Yong Li et al., Qian Li et al., D. R. Leiva et al., N. Hanada et al.).

It is theoretically proposed that reducing the particle size of Mg can do a substantial effect on the thermodynamic parameters and hence can make it favorable candidate for hydrogen storage industry. These insights lead to the synthesis of Mg nano particles.

5.6.2.2.2 Mg₂Ni/N-Gr:

Doping of Mg with transition metals can make it reasonable medium for hydrogen storage industry. Of the various transition metals having high hydrogen affinity, Ni is the most suitable one here as it is less costly than Pd and is well complementing with Mg to enhance its properties. Among all the Mg- based alloys, the inter metallic alloy Mg₂Ni is the most recommended one for hydrogen storage because of its high stability in ambient condition as well as high hydrogen uptake capacities with a fast kinetics of adsorption/desorption.

Again, we have already investigated the properties of nitrogen rich graphite as a high volumetric capacity hydrogen storage material. Hence, we have chosen the nitrogen rich graphite as the catalyst support matrix for the Mg₂Ni nano particles.

5.6.2.2.2.1 Characterizations:

As discussed in Chapter-2, through an easy and appropriate single step synthesis process, the ‘as purchased’ graphite sheets were transformed into nitrogen rich, alloy catalyst nano particle embedded (Mg₂Ni/N- Gr) hydrogen storage media. The ‘as purchased’ graphite powder constitute of two-dimensional sliding sheets. The present synthesis procedure is designed to favor two processes- decomposition of melamine into nitrogen groups as well as their subsequent doping within the layers of graphite and the reduction of Mg and Ni from their corresponding precursors and their further nucleation as alloy nanoparticles on the nitrogen rich graphite substrate. When the well-mixed graphite powder with precursors was exposed to systematic heating procedure in a tubular furnace in presence of hydrogen and argon, the desired composition of nitrogen, magnesium and nickel were assimilated in the graphite matrix. As the temperature was going beyond 280⁰C, the melamine started decomposes into nitrogen functional groups; which can subsequently be accommodated to the SP² networks of graphite sheets following which hydrogen gas was allowed to the system, Mg and Ni were released from their corresponding precursors. Again, when the temperature is raised to 700⁰C, the Mg and Ni were deposited in the nitrogen rich sites of graphite layers as nanoparticle clusters. Thus, the nitrogen sites will favor the deposition of catalyst nanoparticle nucleation. The successful immobilization of magnesium- nickel alloy catalyst nanoparticles in 2: 1 ratio over the nitrogen rich graphite substrate is achieved through this method. Here we have adopted the optimized value of 20-wt%

for catalyst loading. Each grain of the graphite can permit the decoration of the nanoparticles on the top and bottom layers as well as the edges of the middle layers.

Fig. 5. 32 (A) Normalized XRD patterns of a) $Mg_2Ni/N-Gr$ and b) graphite and (B) Energy Dispersive X- ray analysis of $Mg_2Ni/N-Gr$

Fig. 5. 33 TEM (a) and SEM (b) images of as purchased Graphite

The normalized powder XRD patterns of graphite and $Mg_2Ni- N- Gr$ is as shown in Fig. 5.32. (A). The graphite hexagonal planes are revealed through (002) and (004) peaks. In $Mg_2Ni- N- Gr$ specimen, since the catalyst contains single face disordered structure (solid solution) which is an indication of the perfect alloying of Ni in Mg lattice; the peaks are confirmed as the patterns from the alloy planes. These results

clearly suggest the successful immobilization of magnesium- nickel alloy nano particle over the graphite substrate. Above all, the nitrogen rich graphite substrate is good enough to accommodate the catalyst nano phase in its binary alloy form without any structural modification; which is an appreciable sign of the projected catalytic activity towards hydrogen as estimated.

Again, the elemental composition and distribution of the samples were analysed using elemental mapping and energy dispersive X- ray analysis. The EDX spectra (see Fig. 5.32 (B)) shows the composition of elements in the Mg_2Ni - N- Gr sample.

Fig. 5. 34 SEM (a) and (b) and TEM (c) and (d) images of $Mg_2Ni/N-Gr$

The surface morphology of the sample is explored through the microscopic images shown Fig. 5.33 and Fig. 5.34. The TEM and SEM images of graphite layers in the as

purchased powdered sample is shown in Fig. 5.33 (a and b) respectively. When treated through the catalytic chemical vapor deposition synthesis procedure as explained previously, the pristine graphite layers became enriched with nitrogen as well as embedded with the catalyst nano particles. The SEM and TEM images in Fig. 5.34 show the random distribution of the nanoparticles in the layers. From the Fig. 5.34 (c and d), the size of the embedded nano particles are estimated as ~ 8 nm which in agreement with the XRD pattern calculations. In Fig. 5.34(d), the marked portion (marked in red color arrow) shows the single alloy nano particle attached to the edge of the graphite sheet. In order to confirm spatial distribution of elements in the sample, the elemental mapping of the images is done. The representative elemental mapping of the sample is as shown in Fig. 5.35. It is quite evident from the figure that Mg and Ni alloy nanoparticles are distributed randomly over the nitrogen rich graphite layers.

Fig. 5. 35 The representative elemental mapping of the Mg_2Ni/N - Gr sample.

The gas adsorbing properties of the present sample were analyzed through the BET surface area and porosity measurements. The data are recorded using the nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms at 77K as shown in Fig. 5.36 (A). The observed BET surface area of the Pd_3Co - N- Gr sample is $1.470 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$; while for pure graphite it is $1.2021 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. The BJH pore size distribution is also exhibited in Fig. 5.36 (B).

The isotherms are observed to be of type IV with a hysteresis in the range of (0.45 - 0.99) P/P_0 ; according to Bruner-Deming-Deming-Teller classification, which is the characteristic of a meso- porous material. The pore size distribution shows a range of pores between (2-80) nm with a maximum volume at (2- 50) nm which is meso-porous. These qualities attribute a perfect gas adsorbing property to the present material. It is observed that the specific surface area of graphite is increased after the decoration of catalyst nanoparticle. This can be attributed to the uniform distribution of nano sized particles of the alloy catalyst which in turn improve the catalytic activity of the system as expected. However, some sites, including the catalyst centres will be not approachable for nitrogen adsorption; can be active in hydrogen adsorption. Therefore, in practical, for hydrogen adsorption the surface area will be even higher.

Fig. 5. 36 (A) - BET surface area analysis of samples – graphite and $Mg_2Ni/N-Gr$ -The nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms and (B) Porosity analysis of graphite and $Mg_2Ni/N-Gr$ samples

5.6.2.2.2 Hydrogen adsorption studies:

As mentioned earlier, the hydrogen adsorption -desorption studies were performed in Sieverts apparatus (see chapter-2) using pressure reduction method by applying the Van der Waals corrections for the hydrogen gas. The pressure - composition (P-C) isotherms of $Mg_2Ni- N- Gr$ were plotted for different temperatures as shown in Fig. 5.37. The isotherms were recorded in a temperature range of 25 – 100°C with a pressure range of (0.1 – 3) MPa. As the sample temperature is increased, the storage capacity is

decreased as expected; since gas molecules will get enough kinetic energy to escape the barrier potentials.

Fig. 5. 37 Hydrogen pressure – composition isotherms of Mg₂Ni/N- Gr

The desorption studies at room temperature show the high reversibility of the adsorption process. From the isotherm study of Mg₂Ni- N- Gr sample, at 2 MPa pressure and room temperature, the storage capacity is estimated as 4.1 ± 0.1 wt% hydrogen. Comparing to the high surface area carbon materials like graphene, activated carbon, MOFs or chemically modified carbon materials, this capacity is quite high. For pure graphite or few layer graphene, the reported value is less than 1 wt % under the same conditions. For Pd₃Co-N- Gr sample at 2 MPa and room temperature, the capacity is 5.1 ± 0.1 wt%; but here the catalyst cost is several times lesser. A maximum storage capacity of 5.6 ± 0.1 wt% at 3 MPa pressure is observed; which support Mg₂Ni- N- Gr as a potential gravimetric capacity material.

5.6.2.2.3 Conclusion:

Through a simple one-step synthesis process, a potential high volumetric as well as gravimetric capacity hydrogen storage material with non-precious catalyst is developed. The synthesis process is scalable and cost effective; since it modifies the raw material graphite through a single step process and uses the less expensive catalysts. The alloy catalyst mechanism and role of nitrogen in the hydrogen storage

capacity of graphite is explored. The present material Mg₂Ni- N- Gr could achieve a maximum gravimetric storage capacity of 5.6 ± 0.1 wt%. Following the similar procedure, we have examined the hydrogen adsorption/desorption properties of palladium cobalt alloy particles embedded boron rich graphite (Mg₂Ni- B- Gr) also. Mg₂Ni- B- Gr is found to be having a gravimetric capacity of 3.8 ± 0.1 wt% at 25°C temperature and 3MPa hydrogen pressure.

5.7 Summary:

In this chapter, the hydrogen storage performances of low surface area carbon materials such as graphite and graphitic carbon nitride are discussed with focus on high gravimetric capacity as well as volumetric capacity. Through cost effective and effortless one-step synthesis process, catalyst nano particles are deposited over the carbon supports to make use of the synergic interaction effects. The choice of suitable alloy catalyst nanoparticles could improve the GD and VD with kinetics and cycle life of the material; and reduce the cost of production and hydrogen corrosion effects. All the materials used in the present study are easily available, environment friendly and non-poisonous. Introduction of a novel efficient storage material g-C₃N₄ and its cost-effective catalyst modification is worth to the hydrogen storage industry. The non-precious alloy catalyst nano particles Mg₂Ni decorated nitrogen rich graphite can reduce the cost of production considerably. Comparing to the graphene and other high surface area materials-based studies, the present investigations could approach more to the ideal hydrogen storage material. The short summary of the investigations is presented in the following tables.

Table- 5.2: Hydrogen storage studies on g-C₃N₄ based systems.

Material	Storage Capacity (wt%)	Advantages
<i>g-C₃N₄</i>	<i>1.8 @ 25°C; 3MPa</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing a novel high capacity nitrogen rich highly porous hydrogen storage material g-C₃N₄ - cost effective, easy synthesis, environment friendly, high storage capacity
<i>Pd-g-C₃N₄</i>	<i>2.6 @ 25°C; 3MPa</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectively used the Pd catalyst nanoparticles to improve the storage capacity through an easy synthesis method.
<i>Pd3Co-g-C₃N₄</i>	<i>5.3 @ 25°C; 3MPa</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developed a potential hydrogen storage material-through a simple way of alloy catalyst synthesis, cost effectiveness as well as the reduction in the hydrogen-corrosion effect.

Table- 5.3: Hydrogen storage studies on graphite-based systems.

Material	Storage Capacity	Advantages
<i>Pd3Co – Gr</i>	<i>3.9 @ 25°C; 3MPa</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphite based easily available cost-effective material, which uses a single-step, simple alloy catalyst decoration method to improve the capacity and reduce corrosion. • Adopting simple and effective synthesis methods, effectively decorate the Nitrogen and Boron contents in the respective materials. • Thus, graphite based high volumetric capacity hydrogen storage materials are developed.
<i>Pd3Co –N- Gr</i>	<i>6.2 @ 25°C; 3MPa</i>	
<i>Pd3Co –B- Gr</i>	<i>5.3 @ 25°C; 3MPa</i>	
<i>Mg2Ni –N- Gr</i>	<i>5.6@ 25°C; 3MPa</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoiding the noble catalyst such as Pd/Pt and effectively using the alloy nano particle catalyst to reduce the total cost of the material as well as hydrogen corrosion. • Adopting simple and effective synthesis methods, effectively decorate the Nitrogen and Boron contents in the respective materials. • Cost effective material having high GD and VD
<i>Mg2Ni –B- Gr</i>	<i>3.8 @ 25°C; 3MPa</i>	

CHAPTER 6

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This chapter presents a detailed summary of the research work described in each chapter. The important conclusions drawn from each study is presented, and the scope and future of the investigations are discussed.

6.1. Summary and scope of the work

6.1.1 Novel experimental procedure for the observation of contact metal permeation

The present study has introduced a novel experimental procedure to observe the indirect contact metal permeation on to the surface of the carbon materials through container metal surface interfaces. The two major proposals of the experiment are (i) vacuum annealing and (ii) high temperature hydrogen treatment. The vacuum annealing is done to create SW defects in the form of corrugations in the samples and promote the container metal diffusion. The high temperature hydrogenation can cause container metal diffusion through hydrogen assisted reactions of container metals such as hydrogen embrittlement. Combination of both of these processes will promote high degree of metal permeation in the samples. The applied hydrogen will restructure the diffused metal particles in the surface of the samples. This method can be generalised to observe the contact metal permeation in other materials as well.

6.1.2 Contact metal permeation effects in carbon-based systems

Since the quality of contact can affect the device performance and any surrounding metal permeation can perturb the total response of the instrument, the effects of metal diffusion studies are fundamental. Considering the prospective of carbon-based systems to dominate the future device industry, we have considered various carbon materials such as graphene, graphite, graphitic carbon nitride, etc. for the experiments. The effect of indirect contact metal permeation is investigated through the most sensitive properties such as magnetization, charge transport, etc. In fact, the contact metal permeation will be affecting the entire physics of the material and hence one can study any other physical properties. The experimental results show that graphene is the most

sensitive carbon material to the approaching foreign species or any other kind of defects. This can be interpreted in two ways- graphene can be best used for any applications (including various sensors) because of its high sensitivity towards any applied form of energy (e.g.; high temperature) and foreign species reactions or in other way graphene-based devices are more sophisticated to be protected from the surrounding environment. Graphite is less vulnerable to the approaching impurities. Moreover, in general, any contact metal can easily permeate to the core of the device material and hence can affect the performance of the entire system. Our study shows that impurities like Fe and Ni from the surrounding environment (even if the system is alloy based) can easily diffuse into the carbon-based device and hence can influence the performance. This is proven with the experiments in SS alloy containers.

We have noticed from our experiments that as the adsorbed species are metals, which will be highly sensitive to acidic or basic or hydrogen environments; there are high chances to remove these diffused species. The electrochemical responses show that the impurities are sensitive to electrochemical reactions and hence can also be eliminated electrochemically using the techniques such as electrochemical cleaning or etching.

6.1.3 Morphological defects

The introduction of morphological defects was a challenge in the present experiment. Realizing the fact that the unintentional practical situations which could promote the metal permeation processes will definitely create the morphological defects, as surface modifications play a key role in attracting impurities. Thus, with the help of literature support, we have introduced surface modification in graphene through vacuum annealing. Morphological analysis of the samples show that SW defects are created due to the supplied thermal energy under high vacuum. Hence through the present investigations, it is proven that the morphological modifications such as curvatures can improve graphene reactivity and adatom adsorption. SW defect centers are appearing as the attraction sites to any approaching impurity. Thus, the diffused metal clusters are found to be deposited on the convex surfaces of the corrugations. It is also seen that graphite structure needs more energy to modify its surface and hence less sensitive to the normal surface modification defects.

Moreover, the presence of hydrogen atmosphere can promote metal permeation process, as most of the metals will be reactive to hydrogen atmosphere. It can be

summarized from the present experiments that hydrogen presence will increase the metal permeation rate considerably. In hydrogen environment, the metal permeation reaction will happen as a chain process, as the diffused metals in the material will attract more hydrogen towards them and hence will be diffusing more impurities. Hydrogen presence can induce embrittlement in the contact metals and aid the metal corrosion. Thus, if the material is facing the similar practical situations explained in the present experiment such as contact metals in presence of hydrogen atmosphere, the probability of metal permeation will be very high compared to the hydrogen free environment. Or in the reverse hypothesis, there is a scope to remove the diffused metals from the carbon material with the help of hydrogen, as hydrogen can cause detrimental changes to metals; which can be made into practice.

6.1.4 Magnetization interaction

The diffused impurities show noticeable changes in the magnetic response of the samples. The total magnetic behaviour of the system is appearing as the combined effect of different kind of adatoms with the base material. At very low temperatures, spontaneous magnetic properties of the frustrated systems are prominent. Even the hydrogen adsorption on graphene could also provide a feeble magnetic response, as hydrogenated graphene shows magnetism; which is difficult to distinguish from the other adatom adsorption contribution. In the experiments of TEG with SS container, the magnetic properties from the diffused Fe content is surpassing all the other effects. Neither the adatom permeation, nor the surface induced effects are influencing the graphite structure and hence its magnetic properties. In Pd- graphene/graphite-based system, synergic interaction effect on the adhesion site of three constituents, graphene-impurity adatom- Pd nanoparticle interface, provides a combined magnetic interaction to produce large hysteresis on the response. Accordingly, these investigations are of a basic need for magnetically active systems like spintronic devices or any other components which uses electromagnetic waves. The isolation of the device from the circumstances which can aid metal permeation reactions are very important. Experiments in the Pd black samples without any foreign metal permeation show the typical paramagnetic behaviour of the Pd system, while at very low temperatures, the contributions comparable to the reported response of porous structures are observed. The contact metal permeation from SS containers has introduced a prominent ferro magnetic contribution to the system. The super paramagnetic trend in the samples shows that unlike the graphene-Pd system, the particle size of the diffused Fe

components in the Pd black system is of extremely small, giving rise to the observed response. The temperature variation of magnetization study shows that the prominent magnetic outcome is the combination of Fe as well as Pd magnetism; giving rise a possibility of Pd-Fe nanoparticle alloys at their interfaces. Hence, in short, extreme care should be taken to isolate the device components from magnetically active impurity surfaces; as they can contribute a considerable perturbation in the device performance, even if available in a 'ppm' level.

6.1.5 Contact metal permeation effects on other accessory metals associated with the system

Not only the base material of the device, but any accessory metals associated with the base material can also be get affected by the metal permeation reactions. This is verified here using the experiments with Pd nanoparticles decorated in the TEG/graphite systems. It is observed the contact metal permeation has affected almost all properties of the system including morphology, charge transport, magnetic response, etc. The present experimental conditions of vacuum annealing and hydrogenation have changed the morphological distribution of the nano particles considerably. In Pd-TEG systems, the Pd-nano particles are appeared to be distributed along line of wrinkles formed by clustering the SW defects, rather than preferring a random uniform distribution throughout the sheet. The results have been verified using different levels of Pd loading in TEG. In the case of Pd-graphite system, as the SW defects are minimum, the nano particles are distributed randomly in the sheets. The individual Pd particles are of core-shell structure with diffused metal coating as outer shell and a Pd inner core, having a special ring morphology. As mentioned above, these special core-shell particles provide the interaction for the observed magnetism with large hysteresis. The catalytic activities of the system are also found to be influenced by the metal permeation process.

6.1.6 Novel Pd black structures

The formation of novel Pd black structures having unique qualities is an attraction of the present work. The observed structures are having high surface area- with a porous morphology compared to their bulk counterparts, distinguish them as materials having high catalytic activities. The special nucleation reaction induced by the present experimental conditions of vacuum annealing combined with hydrogenation has produced dendrite growths, which resembles 'fern forests'. Like any other material

system studied before, the metal adatoms permeation is affecting all the properties of these Pd dendrite structures as well. As mentioned before, the magnetic contribution from the adatoms show a super paramagnetic behaviour. By changing the container interface to Pd metal, we could observe the pure Pd black structures. Reaction temperature and hydrogenation can influence the morphology of the Pd black structures.

6.1.7 Low surface area carbon materials for compact hydrogen storage

As the efficiency of a hydrogen storage material is typically measured by two parameters- gravimetric density (GD) and volumetric density (VD), the present studies investigate the hydrogen storage performances of low surface area carbon materials such as graphite and graphitic carbon nitride, with focus on high gravimetric capacity as well as volumetric capacity. Through cost effective and effortless one-step synthesis process, catalyst nano particles are deposited over the carbon supports to make use of the synergic interaction effects. The choice of suitable alloy catalyst nanoparticles could improve the GD and VD with kinetics and cycle life of the material; and reduce the cost of production and hydrogen corrosion effects. All the materials used in the present study are easily available, environment friendly and non-poisonous. Introduction of a novel efficient storage material g-C₃N₄ and its cost-effective catalyst modification is worth to the hydrogen storage industry. The non-precious alloy catalyst nano particles- Mg₂Ni decorated nitrogen rich graphite can reduce the cost of production considerably. Comparing to the graphene and other high surface area materials-based studies, the present investigations could approach more to the ideal hydrogen storage material.

6.1.8 Novel graphitic carbon nitride based compact hydrogen storage

Through the hydrogen storage studies, we have introduced a novel high capacity nitrogen rich highly porous hydrogen storage material g-C₃N₄ through cost effective-easy synthesis. This material is environment friendly and shows a very high storage capacity with physisorption reaction. The typical observed storage capacity is 2.6 wt% at 25°C and 3MPa pressure. To improve the capacity by chemisorption utilising the catalyst spill over mechanism, Pd catalyst nanoparticles are successfully decorated in the g-C₃N₄ matrix through an easy synthesis method. The observed capacity of the Pd/g-C₃N₄ is found to be 5.3 wt% at 25°C and 3MPa. For further improvement of the cost

effectiveness, storage capacity as well as reduce the hydrogen corrosion, palladium-cobalt alloy nano particles are introduced into the system. Pd₃Co-g-C₃N₄ is showing a capacity of 5.3 wt% at 25°C and 3MPa hydrogen pressure.

6.1.9 Low cost, non- precious alloy nano particles-based hydrogen storage on graphite

Through this work, graphite based easily available cost-effective material, which uses a single-step, simple alloy catalyst decoration method to improve the capacity as well as reduce hydrogen corrosion effect is developed. Since it is a low surface area material, the volumetric capacity has improved considerably. By adopting simple and effective synthesis methods, we could effectively incorporate Nitrogen and Boron contents in the graphite matrix, which could improve the catalyst anchoring affinity as well as hydrogen interaction affinity and in effect the total hydrogen storage efficiency. The palladium cobalt alloy catalyst nano particles decorated graphite with nitrogen and boron incorporation has improved the capacities considerably. The hydrogen uptake capacities of Pd₃Co – Gr, Pd₃Co – N-Gr and Pd₃Co – B-Gr are 3.9 at 25°C; 3MPa, 6.2 at 25°C; 3MPa and 5.3 at 25°C; 3MPa respectively.

Again, avoiding the noble catalyst such as Pd/Pt and effectively using the alloy nano particle catalyst to reduce the total cost of the storage material as well as hydrogen corrosion; magnesium- nickel alloy catalyst particles are used. Adopting simple and effective synthesis methods, we could effectively decorate the Nitrogen and Boron contents in the respective graphite materials along with the magnesium -nickel alloy nano particles. The hydrogen uptake capacities of Mg₂Ni –N- Gr and Mg₂Ni –B- Gr are 5.6 at 25°C; 3MPa and 3.8 at 25°C; 3MPa respectively.

Analysis of the present results and comparing with the reported values, the present work can be a promising insight to the impending hydrogen energy technology.

6.2. Conclusions

- Through a novel experimental procedure, the indirect contact metal permeation in materials (particularly, carbon -based) through container metal interface is observed experimentally. The experimental conditions to promote metal diffusion are achieved through vacuum annealing, to create surface

modifications like SW defects and exposure to gaseous atmosphere such as hydrogen.

- The vacuum annealing has created clusters of SW defects on the graphene samples leading to the formation of highly corrugated graphene. The diffused metal clusters are found to be deposited on the convex surfaces of the corrugations. Thus, the reactivity of corrugated graphene is found to be increased.
- The studies on materials other than graphene such as graphitic carbon nitride, graphite, etc. shows that the present experimental procedure can be adopted to observe the contact metal permeation in other materials as well.
- The effect of contact metal permeation is analysed through the magnetic response of the system. The diffused Fe particles from the SS containers are dominating the magnetic behaviour of the entire system.
- The effect of contact metal permeation experiment on the formation and decoration of nanoparticle morphology is studied via Pd nanoparticles decorated TEG. Thus, it can be concluded that not only the main material of the system, but the other accessory metals associated with the system are also getting affected by contact metals.
- The contact metal permeation investigations on Pd-carbon system have observed a special morphological appearance of the symmetrical nano particles in the form of core-shell structure with an outer covering of contact metals.
- The introduction of SW defects in the Pd-TEG system has influenced the formation as well as decoration of the Pd nano particles.
- The impact of metal permeation on the magnetic properties of Pd nano particles decorated graphene/graphite shows the introduction of large hysteresis which may be arising from the interface of carbon- diffused metal -palladium synergic interactions.
- The synthesis of novel Pd black dendrite structures having unusual properties has been demonstrated as a consequence of the metal permeation investigations on the Pd systems without any carbon support.
- Magnetic response studies on the metal diffused Pd-black samples processed in SS containers show the superparamagnetic response.

- Investigation of hydrogen storage properties in new low surface area porous materials evolve g-C₃N₄ as the novel support material for the development of hydrogen storage composites.
- Effective alloying of cobalt with palladium nanoparticles has improved the storage capacity as well as reduced the total cost of the material and hydrogen corrosion.
- Low surface area graphite carbon composites provide good volumetric storage capacity and hence applicable towards the compact hydrogen storage device.
- In order to avoid the precious catalyst material such as Pd from the industry, effective use of Magnesium-Nickel alloy nano particles are considered, which could improve the storage efficiency as well as reduce the corrosion.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

PATENTS FILED

- 1) Dr. Ramaprabhu, Sundara and Ms. NAIR, **Asalatha A. S.**, “Palladium- Cobalt alloy Nano particle decorated Graphitic Carbon Nitride as a high capacity hydrogen storage material” [Indian Patent Application No.3497/CHE/2015, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India.]
- 2) Dr. Ramaprabhu Sundara, **Asalatha A. S.** and N. Anitha, “Metal free hydrogenated Graphene as a room temperature ferro magnet” [Indian Patent Application No.5188/CHE/2014, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India]
- 3) **Asalatha. A. S.**, R., Sangeeta V, Abinaya S. and Sundara Ramaprabhu, “Palladium- cobalt alloy nanoparticles embedded nitrogen rich graphite composite as a high volumetric capacity compact hydrogen storage material” [(IITM ICSR-IDF No. 1271; Filing Date: 08.07.2015)]
- 4) Dr. Ramaprabhu, Sundara and Ms. NAIR, **Asalatha A.S.**, “Hydrogenated palladium islands decorated thermally exfoliated graphene as room temperature magnetic material” [(IITM ICSR-IDF No. – 1270)]
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PAPERS IN REFERRED JOURNALS

- 1) **Asalatha. A. S. Nair**, R. Sundara, N. Anita, “Hydrogen Storage Performance of Palladium nano particle decorated Graphitic Carbon Nitride” *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2015, 40(8), pp 3259-3267
- 2) **Asalatha. A. S. Nair** and Sundara Ramaprabhu, “Palladium Cobalt Alloy Catalyst Nanoparticles Facilitated Enhanced Hydrogen Storage Performance of Graphitic Carbon Nitride” *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 2016, 120 (18), pp 9612–9618

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- 4) **Asalatha. A. S. Nair** and Sundara Ramaprabhu, “Observation of contact metal diffusion into graphene layers through containers and their effect in magnetic response experimented on reduced graphene oxide contained in the proximity of the metal/alloy surfaces.” *(to be communicated)*
- 5) **Asalatha. A. S. Nair** and Sundara Ramaprabhu, “Magnesium- Nickel alloy Nano particles decorated nitrogen rich graphite as a potential low cost compact hydrogen storage material *(to be communicated)*
- 6) **Asalatha. A. S. Nair** and Sundara Ramaprabhu, “Contact metal permeation effect in catalyst nano particle formation and decoration in graphene layers; experimental study based on Pd catalyst with hydrogen aided reactions.” *(to be communicated)*
- 7) **Asalatha. A. S. Nair** and Sundara Ramaprabhu, “Container metal diffusion studies in catalyst nano particle formation with graphite-based systems; observations based on Pd catalyst with hydrogen aided reactions.” *(to be communicated)*
- 8) **Asalatha. A. S. Nair** and Sundara Ramaprabhu, “Metal diffusion effect in formation and properties of novel catalyst structures, a study based on Palladium/Platinum systems” *(to be communicated)*
- 9) **Asalatha. A. S. Nair** and Sundara Ramaprabhu, “An experimental observation of contact metal permeation effect in g-C₃N₄ based systems.” *(to be communicated)*

WORK PRESENTED IN CONFERENCE

- 1) “High volumetric capacity compact hydrogen storage material using Graphite based composite – Pd₃Co/N-Gr”, **Asalatha A. S.** and S. Ramaprabhu, International Conference of Young Researchers on Advanced Materials (IUMRS- ICYRAM) 2016, December 11-15, IISc., Bangalore.
- 2) “Room temperature ferromagnetism in reduced Graphene Oxide (r-GO) through controlled Hydrogenation”, **Asalatha A. S.** and S. Ramaprabhu, International

Conference on Nanoscience, Nanotechnology & Advanced Materials (NANOS 2015)
;Gitam University, Vishakhapattanam, December 2015 India

- 3) “Synthesis of Graphitic Carbon Nitride composites and their Potential Application as High Capacity Hydrogen Storage Materials”, **Asalatha A. S.** and S. Ramaprabhu, International Conference on Recent Advances in Nano-Science and Technology - RAINSAT 2015, CSIR- Central Leather Research Institute and Sathyabama University, July 2015 Chennai, India. (*Best Paper Award*)
- 4) “Palladium Decorated Graphitic Carbon Nitride- A Novel High Capacity Hydrogen Storage Material”, **Asalatha A. S.** and S. Ramaprabhu, International Conference on Materials for Advanced Technologies ICMAT2015 & IUMRS-ICA 2015, 28 June- 03 July, Suntec Singapore Convention & Exhibition Centre, Singapore.
- 5) “Graphitic Carbon Nitride – an Effective Room Temperature Hydrogen Storage Material” **Asalatha A. S.** and S. Ramaprabhu, International Symposium for Research Scholars on Metallurgy, Material Science & Engineering (ISRS-2014), December 2014 IIT Madras volume-6, India.
- 6) “Hydrogen in solid states” **Asalatha A. S.** and S. Ramaprabhu, “Explain your research in 2 minutes”- RSD-2016, IIT Madras, India.

PARTICIPATION IN WORKSHOPS

- 1) National Workshop on Nano Science and Technology (NW-NST-2013), October 17 to 19 2013, organized by Mangalore Institute of Technology, Mangalore Karnataka.
- 2) NRB Research Dissemination Workshop Titanium Matrix Composites, 30 Aug- 2113, IITM, Chennai.
- 3) International Workshop in Coatings and Surfaces in Biomedical Engineering, 16-19 Feb. 2014, IITM Chennai.
- 4) Indo-US Workshop on Engineered Electrodes for Electrochemical Energy storage, 3- 4 April 2014, Chennai.
- 5) One-day seminar on “Exploring the current issues in sustainable energy”, 5 June 2014, IITM, Chennai.

- 6) One-day workshop for “Gaining preliminary training in Teaching”, Teaching Learning Centre IIT Madras, 24 February 2018, Chennai.

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DECLARATIONS:

This is the complete PhD thesis submitted to IIT Madras. Individual chapters appear in peer-reviewed publications, patents, and preprints. This is uploaded by the corresponding author for open access dissemination.

Data Availability:

Contains all experimental, computational, simulations, and theoretical analyses from doctoral research carried out at IIT Madras under supervision. No confidential data disclosed.

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*“Everything will be okay in the end.
If it is not okay, it is not the end “ _John Lennon*

Best Regards,

Dr Asalatha Appukuttan Nair Syamala Amma, PhD